

CODECO

Cognitive Decentralised
 Edge Cloud Orchestration

D13: CODECO Federated Operation and Toolkit v1.0

Work package	WP4 – CODECO Federated Operation and Open Toolkit
Internal number	
Task	Tasks 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4
Due date	29.07.2025
Submission date	29.08.2025
Dissemination Type	Public
Deliverable leaders and editors	ICOM (Konstantinos Karageorgos, Marinela Mertiri, Vasileios Theodorou)
Contributing Partners	FOR (Rute C. Sofia, Dalal Ali, Kaikang Huang); ICOM (Konstantinos Karageorgos, Vasiliki Stamou); ATH (George Koukis, Lefteris Mamatas, Vassilis Tsaoussidis); SIE (Jürgen Gesswein); I2CAT (Alejandro Espinosa, Rizkallah Touma); UPRC (Efterpi Paraskevoulakou, Panagiotis Karamolegkos); TID (Alejandro Muniz, Luis M. Contreras Murillo); UC3M (Borja Nogales), UPM (Javier Serrano, Alberto del Rio, David Jimenez); RHT (Ray Carrol, Josh Salomon); IBM (Luis Garcés-Erice, Peter Urbanetz)
Version	0.9
Reviewer 1	FOR (Rute C Sofia)
Reviewer 2	SIE (Jürgen Gesswein)

**Funded by
 the European Union**

Project funded by

 Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
 Confédération suisse
 Confederazione Svizzera
 Confederaziun svizra
 Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
 Education and Research EAER
**State Secretariat for Education,
 Research and Innovation SERI**

**Funded by
 the European Union**

Project Partners

Affiliated Entities

Funded by
the European Union

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report is an integral part of the CODECO *deliverable D13 - CODECO Federated Operation and Toolkit v1.0*. D13 consists of this report and a CODECO software release consisting of components of the CODECO open source "*Federated Operation Toolkit v1.0*", available in the [CODECO Eclipse GitLab repository](#). This release corresponds to an early release of the code. The final release will be provided in Deliverable D14 (CODECO Federated Operation and Toolkit v2.0), due in December 2025.

D13 and the software developed is a product of the work under development in CODECO Work package 4 - CODECO Federated Operation and Open Toolkit - and is a direct result of the work developed in *T4.4 - Open Federated Edge-Cloud Toolkit Development*, the task focusing on the implementation and testing of the CODECO Toolkit based on the software components developed in Tasks 4.1 to 4.3.

Keywords: Edge-Cloud continuum; orchestration; K8s; AI/ML; network; data; compute; context-awareness.

Document Revision History:

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributors
v0.1	15.06.2025	Proposal for a global ToC	Konstantinos Karageorgos (ICOM)
v0.2	30.06.2025	Integration of components, provided by partners	Konstantinos Karageorgos (ICOM)
v0.3	15.07.2025	Revision of the overall code and component structure	All partners involved
v0.4	29.07.2025	Integration of section 2; revision of the overall document; integration of missing PDLC content; first internal review	Rute C. Sofia (FOR)
v0.5	30.07.2025	Full revision	Rute C. Sofia (FOR)
v0.6	05.08.2025	Additional verification by component leaders	Jürgen Gesswein (SIE); Efterpi Paraskevoulakou; Panagiotis Karamelegkos (UPRC); Alejandro Muniz, Luis M. Contreras Murillo(TID); Ray Carrol, Josh Salomon (RHT); (Luis Garcés-Erice, Peter Urbanetz (IBM)
v0.7	07.08.2025	Internal revision 1	Rute C. Sofia (FOR)
v0.8	11.08.2025	Internal revision 2	Juergen Gesswein (SIE)
v0.9	19.08.2025	Verification by ICOM and release to Coordinator	Konstantinos Karageorgos (ICOM)
v1.0	29.08.2025	Final verification and submission to EC	Rute C Sofia (FOR)

Disclaimer

The information, documentation and figures available in this deliverable have been developed by the Horizon Europe CODECO project consortium, under the European Union grant Agreement number 101092696. The content does not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Copyright notice: © 2023 - 2025 CODECO Consortium

Funded by
the European Union

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	3
1 Introduction	11
1.1 Document Scope	11
1.2 Dependencies.....	11
1.3 Document Structure.....	12
2 CODECO Architecture and Federated Cluster Workflow Examples	13
2.1 Architectural Principles Overview.....	13
2.2 CODECO to CEI Continuum Mapping	16
2.3 Federated Cluster Operation Selected Challenges	18
2.4 CODECO FC Common Notions and Terminology.....	19
2.4.1 OCM as Underlying Technology, Constrains	19
2.4.2 CODECO Application-centric Orchestration	21
2.5 CODECO OSS Federated Toolkit Workflow Examples	25
2.5.1 CODECO Installation and Component Deployment.....	25
2.5.2 Deploying an Application across a Federated CEI Environment.....	28
2.5.3 Management of Applications during their Runtime	28
3 CODECO Components Specification and Implementation	30
3.1 ACM-FC: Automated Configuration Management	30
3.1.1 Component Description.....	30
3.1.2 Sub-components' Specification and Implementation	35
3.1.3 ACM-FC and Sub-components Code Structure.....	44
3.1.4 Next Cycle features	45
3.2 PDL-FC: Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-Awareness.....	46
3.2.1 Component Description.....	46
3.2.2 Sub-components' Specification and Implementation	51
3.2.3 Next Cycle Features.....	75
3.3 NetMA-FC: Network Management and Adaptation	75
3.3.1 Component Description.....	75
3.3.2 Sub-components' Specification and Implementation	76
3.3.3 Next Cycle features	87
3.4 MDM-FC: Metadata Manager	87
3.4.1 Component Description.....	87
3.4.2 Sub-components' Specification and Implementation	88
3.4.3 Next Cycle Features.....	100
3.5 SWM-FC: Scheduling and Workload Migration	101
3.5.1 Component description	101
3.5.2 Sub-components' Specification and Implementation	109
3.5.3 Next Cycle features	111
4 Continuous Integration, Testing, Deployment Preparation and Releasing.....	112
4.1 Testing Methodology	112
4.2 Deployment and CI/CD Methodology.....	113
4.2.1 Deployment.....	113
4.2.2 CI/CD Methodology.....	114
4.3 Integration and Testing Facilities	114
5 Summary and Next Steps	115
6 References	116
Annex I – CODECO Cross-Layer Metrics.....	117
Annex II – Release Versioning	120

List of Figures

Figure 1: The CODECO data-compute-network approach for CEI.	13
Figure 2: Functional representation of the CODECO K8s framework and its components. .	15
Figure 3: CODECO and relation to the CEI continuum, single cluster representation.....	17
Figure 4: CODECO examples for multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments across the CEI continuum.	18
Figure 5: CODECO components, positioning across federated clusters based on the Hub-and-spoke model of OCM.	23
Figure 6: Sequence diagram, setting up CODECO across federated clusters. Example for an environment with a single Hub and x Managed clusters.	27
Figure 7: Representation of ACM-FC across a single HUB and two MCs.....	31
Figure 8: representation of the CODECO Application Model. The user provides application and micro-service requirements in the Spec section; ACM-FC gathers status based on the CODECO monitoring and writes it in Status.	32
Figure 9: pre-release of the semantic definition of neighbourhood in CODECO.	37
Figure 10: Reconciliation loop for the Neighbourhood assigned MCs, based on the OCM ManagedCluster API.	38
Figure 11: Example Cluster Claim applied to cluster removal within the CODECO definition of neighbourhood.	38
Figure 12: ClusterClaim reflected in the Hub cluster.....	39
Figure 13: Neighbourhood Manager, ACM-FC sub-component functional representation. ...	39
Figure 14: Example for the initialization function of Prometheus rules.....	40
Figure 15: Method that updates the CAM status, based on periodic collection of metrics from Prometheus.	40
Figure 16: Thanos to ACM-FC and Prometheus interconnections.....	42
Figure 17: Example for a Thanos ConfigMap.	43
Figure 18: Example configuration of an external cluster label for a Prometheus instance in an MC.....	43
Figure 19: Example for cluster labels reflected in Querier UI.	43
Figure 20: Functional, high-level representation of the PDLC sub-components, and of their interactions.	47
Figure 21: Conceptual Architecture of the PDLC Component during the FC phase (Example with two MCs), including internal sub-components and communication Interfaces.....	48
Figure 22: Main interactions between the PDLC sub-components in the FC phase (example with MC1 and MC2).	50
Figure 23: Functional representation of PDLC-DP code components, and interfaces to other CODECO components, within each MC.....	52
Figure 24: Main interactions of the PDLC-DP component with the other MC CODECO components in the FC phase.	53
Figure 25: PDLC-CA workflow, FC operation.	57
Figure 26: PDLC-CA-FC, example for a cost scoring defined for node resilience.....	58
Figure 27: Pre-defined target profile greenness, with equation defined by the user, based on CO2 footprinting.....	58
Figure 28: PDLC-CA-FC example for defining a custom target performance profile.....	59
Figure 29: PDLC-DL-GNNs functional scheme.	61
Figure 30: PDLC-DL-GNNs sequence diagram.....	62

Figure 31. Subcomponents of PDLC-DL MARL and their interactions with other components of PDLC. 68

Figure 32. Sequence diagram showing the execution steps of PDLC-DL MARL and interactions between its subcomponents. 70

Figure 33. MARL communication process between PDLC-DL MARL components of different clusters. 71

Figure 34. Schema of the InfluxDB RL Bucket used as input to PDLC-DL MARL. 74

Figure 35: netma-nsm-mon sequence diagram. 78

Figure 36: netma-nsm-mon pod placement across control and service planes. 78

Figure 37: example of output for the probes generated by netma-nsm-mon. 79

Figure 38: Nemesis-FC functional scheme. 83

Figure 39: Operation sequence, Nemesis-FC within a MC. 84

Figure 40: Translation between ALTO maps and CODECO assets, nodes, clusters, links, etc. 84

Figure 41: MDM sub-components and APIs to other components. 88

Figure 42: Interaction between MDM subcomponents. 95

Figure 43: An application with workloads in two clusters. 101

Figure 44: Event-sequence diagram for a placement of an application. 103

Figure 45: A channel connecting workloads in two clusters has three parts as far as the latency is concerned. 104

Figure 46: Topology of the infrastructure for the SWM-FC example placement. 106

List of Tables

Table 1: ACM-FC sub-component Neighbourhood Manager code structure.	44
Table 2: ACM-FC to Thanos Monitoring PoC code structure.....	44
Table 3: ACM-FC sub-component ALM code structure.	44
Table 4: ACM-GUI sub-component for deploying applications and monitoring microservices	44
Table 5: ACM-FC next cycle features.....	45
Table 6: Comparison of PDLC Component Functionalities Between the Single Cluster (SC) and Federated Cluster (FC) Operation.	48
Table 7: Data output of PDLC-DP, examples.	54
Table 8: PDLC-DP Code Structure.....	54
Table 9: Summary of main PDLC-CA source code files.	59
Table 10: PDLC-DL-GNN.....	65
Table 11: PDLC-DL MARL modes available in single and multi-cluster CODECO operation.	71
Table 12. List of PDLC-DL MARL source code files and description.	72
Table 13: PDLC-FC next cycle features.	75
Table 14: Description of the main netma-nsm-mon source code files.....	80
<i>Table 15: Description of the main netma-nsm-npp source code files.....</i>	<i>82</i>
Table 16: Nemesys-FC main code files.....	85
Table 17: of the main MDM GraphDB source code files.	89
Table 18: Description of the main MDM Controller source code files.....	90
Table 19: Description of the main MDM API source code files.	90
Table 20: Main MDM K8s connector source code files.....	97
Table 21: Description of the main MDM Compliance connector source code files.....	98
Table 22: Description of the main MDM K8s connector source code files.	99
Table 23: MDM Next cycle features.	100
Table 24: CODECO Application Model Attributes, spec, and status, minimum subset of parameters.....	117
Table 25: CODECO metrics being collected by MDM.	118
Table 26: CODECO metrics being collected by NetMA.	119
Table 27: CODECO sub-components.	120

List of Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Meaning
ACM	Automated Configuration Manager
AD	Anomaly Detection
AD	Anomaly Detection
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALTO	Application-Layer Traffic Optimization
API	Application Programming Interface
APOC	Awesome Procedures on Cypher
ARM	Advanced RISC Machines
CA	Context-awareness
CAM	CODECO Application Model
CDN	Content Delivery Network
CEI	Cloud-Edge-IoT
CP	Change Point
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/ Continuous Deployment
CLI	Command Line Interface
CNI	Container Network Interface
CODECO	Cognitive, Decentralised Edge-Cloud Orchestration
CODEF	CODECO Experimentation Framework
CP	Change Point
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CR	Custom Resource
CRD	Custom Resource Definition
CSDG	CODECO Synthetic Data Generator
DBMS	Database Management System
DEV	Developer
DL	Decentralised Learning
DL	Deep Learning
eBPF	extended Berkeley Packet Filter
EC	European Commission
FC	Federated Cluster
FedGNNs	Federated GNNs
FIDO	Fast Identity Online
GNNs	Graph Neural Networks
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HE	Horizon Europe
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
ICMP	Internet Control Message Protocol
IP	Internet Protocol
IPAM	IP Address Management
JSON	Javascript Object Notation
K8s	K8s

Acronym	Meaning
KCP	K8s like Control Plane
KFP	Kubeflow Pipelines
KinD	K8s in Docker
L2	Layer 2
L2S-M	Link-Layer Secure connectivity for Microservice platforms
LPM	L2S-M Performance Measurements
MAPE	Mean Absolute Percentage Error
MARL	Multi Agent Reinforcement Learning
MDM	Metadata Manager
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MGT	Infrastructure Manager
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
MSE	Mean Squared Error
NetMA	Network Management and Adaptation
NSM	Network State Monitoring
OAS	Open API Specification
OCM	Open Cluster Management
OS	Operating System
OSS	Open-Source Software
PDLC	Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-awareness
POC, PoC	Proof Of Concept
PP	Preprocessing
PVC	Persistent Volume Claim
PPO	Proximal Policy Optimization
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
REST	Representational State Transfer
REST	Representational State Transfer
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
SC	Single Cluster
SDG	Synthetic Data Generator
SDK	Software Development Kit
SDN	Software Defined Network
STGNN	Spatio-Temporal Graph Neural Network
SWM	Scheduling and Workload Migration
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
UI	User Interface
UML	Unified Modelling Language
VLAN	Virtual Local Area Network
VM	Virtual Machine

Acronym	Meaning
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language

Acknowledgements

We thank all CODECO Partners involved in Work Package 4 for the commitment and involvement in the development of Deliverable D13.

1 Introduction

CODECO Work Package 4 (WP4) builds upon the foundations laid in WP3 to extend the CODECO framework beyond single-cluster orchestration towards a **federated, multi-cluster environment**. Since M19 and until M30 (June 2025), WP4 has focused on the design, development, and validation of the CODECO federated architecture, enabling decentralised coordination across geographically or administratively distinct clusters. This effort follows the architectural principles and component interfaces defined in earlier deliverables, in particular D10 (M18) and D12 (M18).

Deliverable *D13 – CODECO Federated Operation and Toolkit v1.0* introduces the first open-source version of the CODECO toolkit specifically designed for federated scenarios. This deliverable consists of this technical report and the corresponding software release published under the CODECO Eclipse GitLab Research project. The D13 release allows developers and research contributors to experiment with and build upon CODECO's federated capabilities, including inter-cluster communication, distributed lifecycle management, and cooperative resource scheduling.

Tasks 4.1 to 4.3 of WP4 are responsible for the specification, implementation, and interfacing of CODECO federated components with other parts of the architecture. Task 4.4 is dedicated to the overall system integration and validation of the federated toolkit and operates across all WP4 technical tasks. As with previous iterations of the CODECO framework, the work in WP4 follows an agile methodology, allowing for the continuous refinement of the components and their coordination as the federated architecture evolved.

The aim of D13 is to **provide early access to the CODECO OSS Federated Toolkit** for developers and contributors, in alignment with the open-source strategy of the project and in support of a sustainable, collaborative development ecosystem.

1.1 Document Scope

As explained, D13 contains the first release of the open-source CODECO Federated Clusters Toolkit, along with an explanation of its software architecture and implementation design. This deliverable builds on the previous versions of the CODECO Basic Operation Toolkit (D12), extending the framework to support federated clusters operation.

This deliverable provides:

- An explanation of the federated CODECO framework and implementation procedures for the Federated Clusters Toolkit.
- A description of the tools and methods adopted to support the implementation workflow, including coding guidelines to assist developers, installation instructions, and the core tools and programming languages used in the development of the federated CODECO components.

D13 is composed of the following parts:

- This report (software companion report).
- The first release of the CODECO Federated Cluster Operation Toolkit, available via the [CODECO Eclipse GitLab](#).

1.2 Dependencies

D13 is a self-contained document. However, if the reader seeks to further understand the CODECO operation and the previous development phases it is advised to check the CODECO

Deliverable D10 - Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Open-source Ecosystem Design [1], as well as the CODECO Deliverable D12 - CODECO Basic Operation Components and Toolkit Version 2.0 [2].

1.3 Document Structure

- **Section 1** introduces the overall deliverable scope, structure, and components.
- **Section 2** provides a summary of the CODECO architectural design and highlights the sub-components that are being released in this deliverable.
- **Section 3** provides the companion reporting for the use of the existing code, detailed per sub-component.
- **Section 4** describes the continuous system testing and the deployment framework that has been set in T4.4 to assist the overall project, as well as the continuous integration and released version of each subcomponent/feature developed in the second implementation cycle of CODECO.
- **Section 5** concludes the document, presenting next steps for the next phase of development of the CODECO OSS Toolkits.
- **Annex I** provides a revision of the CODECO monitored metrics, which have been proposed in D10 [1].
- **Annex II** provides a table with all the CODECO components and sub-components released in this phase, as well as links to the code

2 CODECO Architecture and Federated Cluster Workflow Examples

This section provides an overview of the CODECO architecture, to help the reader understand the CODECO federated toolkit code. The section provides a summary of a new CODECO deliverable, due in December 2025, which will cover the full design of the CODECO architecture. The section starts by explaining how CODECO operates across the Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI) continuum, and what is meant by federated cluster/multi-cluster environments across the CEI. It then provides operational workflows for the federated cluster toolkit.

2.1 Architectural Principles Overview

CODECO is a containerised application orchestration framework (TRL 4-5), independent and yet pluggable to Kubernetes¹ (K8s). CODECO aims at providing support for a flexible and cognitive *Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI)* infrastructure. The notion of infrastructure in CODECO considers different infrastructure perspectives, taking into consideration:

- the **networking** perspective, where the network is perceived both as the *underlay* and *overlay* infrastructure required to support the deployment of containerised applications across CEI;
- the **data observability** perspective, bringing input on the data dependencies that micro-services may have, and that is important to consider during the application deployment and re-deployment;
- the **computational** perspective, bringing input on the suitable nodes to serve an application.

CODECO addresses the orchestration across these three different perspectives in an integrated approach, which is named as **data-compute-network** orchestration.

Figure 1: The CODECO data-compute-network approach for CEI.

The motivation to develop such an orchestration framework relates with the current evolutionary aspects of the CEI continuum. In this context, applications (and their components) need

¹ <https://kubernetes.io/>

to be lightweight, highly portable, and mobile, to run anywhere and everywhere. Secondly, there is a need to handle large amounts of data often with very different features both in terms of computation (processing) and exchange (networking), including those with low latency demands. Thirdly, it is important to guarantee a smooth data flow, to allow for a smooth and secure integration end-to-end, across Edge-Cloud environments. Fourthly, real-time decision-making on where to compute and to store data must be supported.

As a cognitive and decentralised orchestration framework, CODECO embraces a next generation vision where data and services are stored and computed across the Internet whole-chain, in a holistic cooperation between Cloud and far Edge. Components of containerised applications, which in CODECO are addressed as *micro-services*, reside in isolated, self-sufficient containers, which can be deployed and executed in any underlying environment. A flexible and secure networking infrastructure provides adaptable interconnection that adapt to the needs and the surrounding environment of the services being run.

Relevant in CODECO is an adaptation based on application requirements (e.g., required bounded latency) and user requirements (e.g., compliance required with GDPR). A functional representation of CODECO and its open-source components is provided in Figure 2. Based on this functional level, CODECO offers the following aspects:

- **Automated configuration**, focusing on supporting application setup and application runtime across Edge-Cloud, by taking into consideration compute, network, and data aspects. The key aspects of this contribution are supported by the CODECO *Advanced Configuration and Management (ACM)* component.
- **Data as a resource**. CODECO addresses, via its *Metadata Manager (MDM)* component data as a resource in the sense that available snapshots from the overall Edge-Cloud infrastructure, integrating different perspectives (application, user, system, data, network) at different instants of the CODECO operational workflow can be provided to different CODECO components, to assist in detecting relevant changes.
- **Dynamic scheduling and workload migration**. Supported by the CODECO component *Scheduling and Workload Migration (SWM)*, CODECO brings in novel QoS models that consider data-network-compute requirements to provide a best match between applications and available infrastructure (nodes, their computational and data properties, as well as network nodes and links), and to schedule and re-schedule application workloads across single cluster and federated cluster environments, considering application and user requirements.
- **Context-awareness and privacy preserving decentralised learning**. CODECO relies on context-awareness to be able to achieve a joint data-network-compute orchestration, and on privacy-preserving decentralised learning and inference to best support readjustment of aspects such as the processing capability, computational resources, networking resources and interconnections in real-time. Context-awareness and decentralised learning are part of the CODECO *Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning (PDLC)* component.
- **Infrastructure adaptation based on a cross-layer data-compute-network approach**. Via the CODECO *Network Management and Adaptation component (NetMA)*, CODECO assists in adapting not just computational (node resources) but also the networking infrastructure interconnecting such nodes, having as starting point for the exposure of metadata within one cluster and across federated clusters, from far Edge to Cloud.

Figure 2: Functional representation of the CODECO K8s framework and its components.

The only interface of CODECO to the user, as shown in Figure 2, is the ACM component, which focuses on supporting application setup and runtime from the far Edge to the Cloud, considering the input provided by the user.

The user in CODECO is perceived as an **application developer (DEV)** or as a **cluster manager (MGT)**.

To setup CODECO, a user relies on the CODECO framework. ACM installs the entire CODECO framework, handling the overall CODECO configuration. The user can specify, via the CODECO **Application Model (CAM)**, the requirements of the application and of its micro-services. These requirements are relevant to allow CODECO to deploy the application across CEI in an efficient way.

Via CAM, the user specifies also **target performance profiles** that is used in CODECO (PDLC) to meet a specific level of **greenness**, or **resilience** during its operation.

Once CODECO is installed, all CODECO components can be used. The CODECO components have been devised to allow each component to work independently, with other future open orchestration frameworks, requiring little adaptation.

The **CODECO MDM** component provides data and system observability to the other CODECO components, treating data as an integral part of the application workload, and integrating observability perspectives from different categories, e.g., application perspective, system perspective, network perspective, at different points in the CODECO operational workflow.

SWM handles the scheduling and rescheduling of the application workload, based on the *CODECO Application Model (CAM)*. CAM is supported by ACM and provided by the user during application setup, based on the novel data-compute-network approach proposed by CODECO.

The currently available approach in SWM for handling placement decisions relies on a graph-based optimization approach which in contrast to the K8s filtering and score approach is expected to provide an optimal match between application requirements and available resources (computational, network, data). SWM is also a control plane component, co-located with ACM and the K8s control plane, in master nodes.

PDLC is at the heart of the CODECO orchestration. Based on the infrastructure data collected by ACM (via Prometheus), NetMA, and MDM, PDLC has two functions. Firstly, it provides an aggregated cost view of a specific target performance profile for the available infrastructure which can be used by other components and is currently being considered in SWM to further define the optimal workload placement. Secondly, it provides an estimate on the overall system stability based on privacy-preserving decentralised learning approaches. PDLC is currently envisaged to operate on both K8s master and worker nodes.

NetMA provides the network awareness to CODECO and handles also secure connectivity across pods. Network awareness is provided via network probing based on the sub-component Network State Management (NSM). Then, exposure of network metrics (across multi-cluster environments) is based on the ALTO protocol [3]. NetMA provides in addition **secure connectivity** via **L2S-M²**. Hence, NetMA is a component responsible for interconnecting the *Software-defined Networking (SDN)* world with K8s.

To be able to achieve a flexible orchestration, CODECO counts with monitoring across the three different CEI infrastructure perspectives. NetMA monitors the networking infrastructure; MDM monitors the data infrastructure; ACM monitors the system (computational nodes) infrastructure based on the K8s metrics server Prometheus^{3,4}. This approach allows to explore the integration of new metrics as well as of providing the collected metrics of CODECO to future orchestration frameworks.

The CODECO framework is deployed as an application: each CODECO component is based on a modular approach, integrating different sub-components that are expected to be built as one or more independent (dockerized) micro-services.

2.2 CODECO to CEI Continuum Mapping

As an orchestration framework, CODECO can operate at the Edge, Edge to Edge, Edge to Cloud, including far Edge to Cloud. The operation of CODECO relates with the management of an Edge-Cloud infrastructure which is based on the abstraction principles of K8s.

CODECO as a framework pluggable to K8s is developed to provide a flexible K8s operation considering mobile heterogeneous environments, and a reach to the far Edge. CODECO is developed in a way that allows it to operate in a single cluster or multiple clusters, across multi-tenant environments.

A cluster in this case is an abstraction from the K8s concept (rf. to section 2.1) which can be mapped solely to an Edge environment (including a far Edge environment), Edge-to-Edge, or Edge-to-Cloud. The principles of CODECO provide the capability to support Edge-to-Edge orchestration. The cluster abstraction concept always integrates a control plane (K8s master

² <http://l2sm.io>

³ <https://prometheus.io/>

⁴ The current version of CODECO considers Prometheus as basis for the metrics gathering and analysis. However, for multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments the consortium is also considering Thanos due to the higher availability, and extended storage capabilities.

node, rf. to section 2.1) and a service plane (K8s worker nodes). From an Edge-Cloud continuum perspective, a cluster is expected to integrate at least one Edge node. A representation on this potential mapping for single cluster operation is illustrated in Figure 3.

Cluster 1 provides an initial example for a centralised mapping, where the control plane of CODECO (and of K8s) resides in the Cloud, while K8s worker nodes being monitored and managed in CODECO are in the far and near Edge. As illustrated, CODECO components such as ACM and SWM (control plane of CODECO) would then reside in the Cloud, co-located with the K8s control plane. Sub-components of MDM, PDLC, and NetMA, the sub-components related with resource monitoring, would be located on the K8s worker nodes (far and near Edge in this example). While this representation places the CODECO control plane in the Cloud, it should be highlighted that it could also run in the near Edge or far Edge, as represented in **Cluster 2** for the near Edge. In this example, worker nodes are also running MDM, NetMA due to monitoring, and PDLC (learning at the Edge).

Cluster 3 provides a representation of the mapping of CODECO to the far Edge. CODECO can run on a single node or as represented, run on multiple nodes. The example here provided shows that in K8s worker nodes, NetMA is the only component active (network monitoring), while the other components are set to run co-located with the K8s control plane. MDM is not represented, to highlight that some components in CODECO are also optional. For instance, a user MGT may want to optimize the infrastructure just in terms of computational and networking resources, and hence, it is not required to run MDM.

Figure 3: CODECO and relation to the CEI continuum, single cluster representation.

Figure 4 provides a high-level representation of the CEI mapping of CODECO for multi-cluster environments. In this case, a cluster may be located at a single region (far Edge, near Edge) or span different areas (e.g. far Edge and Cloud; far Edge and near Edge; far Edge-near Edge-Cloud). Multi-cluster operation handled by CODECO takes into consideration different clusters as in K8s (independently of location) but brings to K8s CEI awareness in the sense that it

takes into the placement process data, network and computational awareness. This allows CODECO to best adapt to, for instance, far Edge environments, where devices may be constrained in terms of computational resources and networking resources. It allows CODECO also to react if the suitable nodes running the application do have the expected resources, but an abnormal pattern was detected with the data workflow (e.g., stale database) and with the networking resources (e.g., temporarily congested link).

Figure 4: CODECO examples for multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments across the CEI continuum.

2.3 Federated Cluster Operation Selected Challenges

Based on the analysed literature and projects, CODECO defines as the most relevant challenges to handle in FC orchestration the challenges presented next. For the description of the requirements, this section again follows following the IETF principles: The key words "MUST", "MUST NOT", "REQUIRED", "SHALL", "SHALL NOT", "SHOULD", "SHOULD NOT", "RECOMMENDED", "MAY", and "OPTIONAL" in this document are to be interpreted as described in IETF RFC 2119⁵.

- **Decentralization and Self-organizing cluster federation model.** The CODECO FC operation **MUST** be able to handle the Edge-Cloud continuum based on a model of self-organizing clusters. For this, the potential decentralization of the control plane **SHOULD** be studied and considered in terms of advantages and disadvantages for the overall design, where resilience, reduced energy consumption and improved QoS/QoE performance (e.g., lower latency) are the main target performance goals.
- **Visibility.** A key aspect to handle is the capability to handle resource sharing across multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments. Exposure of information (network exposure, but

⁵ S. Brader. "Keywords for use in RFCs to Indicate Requirement Levels." sIETF RFC 2119, March 1997.

also computational exposure) SHOULD integrate an expressive, eventually intent-based semantic abstraction and MUST consider a flexible approach to context-awareness exposure across clusters.

- **Mobility and Adaptive Networking.** At an inter- and intra-cluster level, networking aspects need to be handled from a K8s perspective and taking into consideration the internet administrative domain fabric (AS). It is RECOMMENDED to consider SLA management and approaches to allow for a flexible adaptation of the established overlay networking, taking into consideration underlay variability.
- **Application-oriented semantic composition and data aggregation.** The overall application scheduling and re-scheduling process MUST rely on an application-oriented semantic composition, for which the FC starting point is the CAM. This model will be further extended to integrate the devised approach for decentralization and cluster self-organization in CODECO.
- **Pro-active rescheduling, with focus on migration (instead of replication).** Current K8s based approaches focus on resource scaling and load-balancing. However, in mobile Edge-Cloud environments there are scenarios where migration is required. CODECO shall continue the debate on the advantages and disadvantages of considering migration instead of replication in the context of container orchestration.

2.4 CODECO FC Common Notions and Terminology

2.4.1 OCM as Underlying Technology, Constrains

The underlying technology selected to develop CODECO is the Open Cluster Management (OCM) solution, and the RedHat OCM project *Advanced Cluster Management*⁶. Traditionally, OCM operates in a centralized fashion, meaning it uses a **Hub cluster** to control multiple Spoke or Managed Clusters (MC). However, decentralized approaches can sometimes complicate the enforcement of consistent management policies across clusters. The lack of a single control point could lead to operational issues, such as performance monitoring difficulties, workload scheduling problems, and potential version mismatches during maintenance or upgrades.

OCM includes a mechanism for adding extensions or "add-ons," which can be used to enhance the functionality of the system, such as adding capabilities for security, monitoring, or application lifecycle management. These add-ons do not alter the core architecture of OCM, making them flexible and easily deployable.

Additional features discussed include:

- **Work distribution** via the Work API: This allows for resources to be applied to managed clusters from the hub cluster.
- **Content placement:** This feature enables dynamic placement of content and behavior, making the system adaptable to changing conditions.
- **Policy-driven governance:** OCM enforces policies across all clusters to ensure that security measures and configurations are consistently applied.
- **Disaster recovery and high availability:** The system automates recovery processes to maintain the availability of applications during disruptions.
- **Observability and monitoring:** OCM integrates with tools like Prometheus and Grafana to provide insights into cluster health, performance, and workload status.

⁶ <https://www.redhat.com/en/blog/using-the-open-cluster-management-add-on-framework-to-develop-a-managed-cluster-add-on>

The hub cluster is the central controller that oversees the managed clusters. The hub runs OCM and additional components that handle tasks such as cluster registration, deployment, and monitoring.

Several key modules of OCM are introduced:

1. **Registration:** This module manages the lifecycle of the managed clusters, with a registration controller in the hub and a registration agent in each managed cluster.
2. **Placement:** The placement module selects the appropriate managed clusters for workload deployment based on labels or cluster claims. It helps ensure that workloads are distributed across clusters based on specific criteria like resource availability.
3. **Manifest Work:** This module facilitates the dispatching of Kubernetes resources (e.g., services, deployments) from the hub cluster to managed clusters. It enables centralized deployment while maintaining visibility into whether the resources are applied correctly.
4. **Add-ons:** These are additional components that enhance the functionality of OCM by adding features like policy enforcement and advanced scheduling.

OCM's policies define the desired state for managed clusters. Policies compare the current state of resources in a cluster with the desired configuration and can either inform administrators or enforce changes to bring the cluster into compliance. This process is guided by compliance types, such as "must have," "must not have," or "must only have," which determine how strict the policy is in enforcing the desired state.

A configuration policy would, for example, define a namespace called "production" as a required resource. If the namespace does not exist, the policy can either inform the administrator or enforce its creation.

The role of policies in security governance is emphasized. Using OCM, organizations can define security and compliance rules at the hub level and automatically apply them to managed clusters. For example, policies could mandate encryption or specific software versions across all clusters. If any cluster fails to meet these standards, the policy controller flags the issue and takes corrective actions.

OCM environments can be monitored using Prometheus, which collects metrics from managed clusters, and Grafana, which is used to visualize this data. This setup enables centralized monitoring of cluster performance, including CPU and memory usage, with customizable dashboards for specific needs.

The OCM federated model allows for clusters to function independently but are nonetheless centrally managed. The multi-cluster deployment model within OCM does not function exactly like a single-cluster deployment, particularly in terms of workload management. The OCM deployment manifests wrap the standard K8s resources like deployments, services, and namespaces, allowing them to be applied to the right cluster via the OCM hub.

OCM's placement function is described as a matchmaking system, rather than a strict scheduler. This allows users to target specific clusters or nodes based on labels or custom scoring algorithms. However, the system does not inherently offer a scheduler that automatically decides where to place workloads. Instead, it relies on user-defined placements, which can be as specific as targeting clusters with certain labels or resource scores.

In a case where no extensions or custom labels are used, OCM requires the user to manually define where the workloads should go. The process involves creating a manifest work and a corresponding placement that specifies the clusters or nodes to target.

As a K8s tool, OCM does not handle directly the inter-cluster networking. It can rely on approaches such as Submariner⁷ to provide IP networking between pods and services interconnected across different clusters. OCM's role is mainly in the placement of workloads, while networking concerns are handled separately, often through additional tools or plugins that extend OCM's functionality.

In terms of monitoring, OCM supports Thanos, to assist the monitoring across clusters⁸. This support, which is relevant in the context of CODECO, is not part of the core OCM solution and is considered an add-on for users who require it.

In addition, the OCM Manifests are relevant to assist an adequate abstraction, when handling stateless deployments. The manifest work applies to a specific namespace and is deployed to the selected cluster as per the user's placement configuration. A manifest work, which could contain resources like a single pod, is deployed through OCM to a designated cluster, such as MC1. Placement strategies could allow the deployment to span multiple clusters, e.g., clusters A, B, and D. This flexibility can help align deployments with strategic objectives, ensuring that workloads are distributed according to specific requirements. The placement can be altered as needed, using tools like OCM to manage the distribution across clusters.

The approach to deployment also allows for real-time updates. If a new cluster (such as cluster C) is added to the placement, the workload will automatically be deployed to that cluster as well. The work agent, which monitors the clusters, handles the deployment, ensuring that resources are added or removed based on the updated manifest work.

2.4.2 CODECO Application-centric Orchestration

As a K8s-based framework, CODECO considers that the so-called Edge-Cloud continuum is becoming increasingly complex not just due to the integration of different networking technologies, but also to the need to support high portability of applications and mobility from the far Edge to the Cloud. In this vision, the overall far Edge to Cloud infrastructure is comprised of terrestrial and non-terrestrial environments, and composed of resources at a computational level, networking level, and data observability level. This means that CODECO proposes to manage the overall infrastructure from an **application perspective**, considering that applications and their micro-services are containerized.

The focus on the application brings a key architectural design difference between CODECO and K8s. While K8s is primarily concerned with managing clusters and infrastructure, CODECO introduces new tools for K8s to manage containerized applications more effectively, particularly in far-edge environments, by embracing an application perspective. The underlying difference is that CODECO adopts the vision of applications based on micro-services architecture patterns, **where application components can be distributed across multiple clusters that belong to different tenants** and that are scattered across Edge and Cloud, or simply reside on the Edge (including the far Edge). This differs from the traditional model in which each cluster hosts a full application stack. CODECO's approach to microservices allows

⁷ <https://submariner.io/>

⁸ <https://thanos.io/>

for more flexible deployment across heterogeneous environments, such as Edge-Cloud set-ups. This flexibility is particularly important as the number of mobile clusters and nodes increases, and as the Edge computing environment becomes more diverse.

DEV is a user deploying an application consisting of multiple micro-services (multiple Docker images) across the far Edge to the Cloud. DEV downloads CODECO from the [CODECO Eclipse GitLab](#)⁹ and follows the instructions to set up CODECO, including the specific assumptions and requirements:

- CODECO requires the Open Cluster Management (OCM)¹⁰ software to be installed.
- It is assumed that there is at least one OCM Hub cluster, and one OCM Managed Cluster (MC) registered under the OCM cluster.
- The explanations provided in this document shall refer to a composition of 1 Hub to 2 MC clusters. However, the CODECO architecture is being designed so that applications can be deployed across multiple Hub/MC clusters.
- CODECO can rely on different flavours of Kubernetes (e.g., MC cluster with K3s, MC cluster based on Kubernetes)
- Prometheus¹¹ and Thanos¹² need to be installed.
- CODECO as a framework can be used on a single cluster or for FC.
- To be considered by CODECO, clusters must first undergo an OCM Hub registration process. Registration allows the hub cluster to recognize and manage the new node.
- CODECO defines a notion of neighbourhood, i.e., a set of managed clusters where an application is mapped to.
- An application is only mapped to a single neighbourhood.
- A single MC can belong to more than one neighbourhood

An example on how the CODECO components is set across Hub and MCs is provided in Figure 5.

⁹ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

¹⁰ <https://open-cluster-management.io/>

¹¹ <https://prometheus.io/>

¹² <https://thanos.io/>

Figure 5: CODECO components, positioning across federated clusters based on the Hub-and-spoke model of OCM. Green arrows represent the user to CODECO logic; red arrows represent the CODECO observability interfaces. Orange arrows correspond to the Hub to spoke control plan communication between CODECO components; blue arrows represent the communication between CODECO components across the control plane of MCs.

When setting up CODECO, user DEV simply interacts with the CODECO operator provided by the CODECO component ACM.

Then, to deploy an application, user DEV needs to set, via the ACM user interface (see sections 2.5.2 and 4.3.1), an application semantic description, which is known as the *CODECO Application Model (CAM)*. Via this interface, user DEV defines aspects such as desired *Quality of Service (QoS)*, *Quality of Experience (QoE)*, or other desired performance levels that are expected for the application, based on the syntax provided in CAM. The current attributes considered in the CAM are provided in Annex I.

To orchestrate an application, it is assumed that CODECO will check possible resources across all MC handled by a Hub cluster and if required, it may consider MCs handled by other Hub clusters. This search may be too intensive (bandwidth, processing, time) and therefore, it is important to consider a partitioning approach that can assist in reducing the problem space to search for each application.

It is highlighted that from a code perspective, the CODECO FC operation toolkit will only support the deployment of an application across MCs managed by the same Hub cluster. However, from an architecture perspective, the overall design on how CODECO would operate will be made available in deliverable D10.1 (December 2025).

A relevant step to handle during the setup of an application is the definition of **neighbourhood** in CODECO. **In summary, neighbourhood is a semantic abstraction for a group of MC that is created at the application deployment setup time and re-evaluated periodically.** Hence, there is a one-to-one correspondence between an application and its neighbourhood: a unique set of clusters is selected **every time a new application is going to be deployed.**

The mechanism that provides a sweeping of the total existing clusters (based on the application requirements and selected target performance profiles provided in CAM by the user) is a plugin to the CODECO framework which is being defined as being interconnected with ACM, named **CODECO Neighbourhood Composer (CNC)** and which is part of the CODECO architectural design to be delivered in December 2025.

After the definition of neighbourhood, ACM sets the overall communication logic of CODECO to support the application deployment and management on the MC clusters selected to be part of the application neighbourhood.

- ACM-FC resides in the Hub cluster, and has a client (agent) in the control plane of each MC.
- MDM-FC resides in the Hub cluster and can be moved to any other MC control plane (only one instance per neighbourhood is required).
- PDLC resides in the control plane of the MCs.
- SWM has two instances, SWM-L1 and SWM-L2. SWM-L1 resides in the Hub cluster, and SWM-L2 resides in each MC.
- NetMA has a sub-component, the IDCO residing in the Hub cluster, and all other components residing in the MCs. The monitoring sub-components reside in all nodes (control plane and worker nodes).

The exposure of requirements and application/user information also triggers the operation of each CODECO component within the MC clusters belonging to a single neighbourhood. PDLC defines the processes for collecting available data (application requirements from CAM; network status from NetMA; computational status from Prometheus via ACM) and bringing cross-layer context-aware costs to the infrastructure; PDLC handles also learning to assist in a stable

infrastructure. Specifically, based on existing CODECO metrics collected and aggregated, PDLC generates a set of recommendations to improve the application assignment and passes such recommendations to SWM as node costs to be considered for scheduling optimisation (I-PDLC-SWM-1). NetMA triggers the definition of the network overlay when it receives the initial deployment from SWM (I-SWM-NET-1).

In parallel, three components start monitoring different metrics. NetMA captures network metrics at link and path level and exposes this information via specific CRs that are accessible to all components and used by PDLC and ACM.

Similarly, MDM captures data aspects (e.g., data compliance), generates a knowledge graph which can be queried via specific connectors developed to allow MDM to be fully integrated with CODECO and with different information sources.

ACM captures user preferences and eventually behaviour, which may be useful for adapting the overall K8s infrastructure at a later stage.

The next section provides the communication sequence for different stages of use of CODECO.

2.5 CODECO OSS Federated Toolkit Workflow Examples

The current version of the CODECO OSS Federated Toolkit builds upon the modular structure of the CODECO Basic Toolkit, extending the deployment and orchestration capabilities across multiple Kubernetes clusters. The purpose of this section is to walk the reader through the practical operation of the CODECO Federated Toolkit using typical workflow examples, from the CODECO setup to the deployment and runtime orchestration. The basis for the description and communication sequences provided in this section is Figure 5.

In the example presented, the user (DEV) prepares an application composed of multiple microservices and uses CODECO to deploy it across a group of clusters (neighbourhood), managed via the RedHat downstream project of OCM. All CODECO components are deployed via Kubernetes manifests and Helm charts, and their interactions are handled through Kubernetes *Custom Resource Definition (CRD)*.

Once the application is deployed, orchestration is handled automatically by the respective components, with ACM coordinating, PDLC performing decentralized learning, SWM optimizing placements, and NetMA and MDM providing input from the infrastructure. The behaviour remains consistent with the single-cluster phase, with the exception that orchestration is now scoped within a defined federated neighbourhood.

2.5.1 CODECO Installation and Component Deployment

To install the CODECO OSS Federated Toolkit, the user (DEV) downloads CODECO from the [CODECO Eclipse GitLab](#)¹⁰ and follows the instructions to set up CODECO.

The use of **OCM** plus considering a setup with **at least a Hub cluster and several MCs** are requirements to run the CODECO FC Toolkit.

The sequence diagram (see Figure 6: Sequence diagram, setting up CODECO across federated clusters. Example for an environment with a single Hub and x Managed clusters.) provided in the deployment flow of the CODECO platform across a Hub cluster (ACM-FC Hub) and multiple managed clusters (MCx). It is broken into two main phases:

1. Operator Deployment

- DEV (Application Developer):
 - Initiates the infrastructure setup with one Hub cluster and two Managed Clusters (MC1, MC2 abstracted as MCx)
 - Requests the deployment of the CODECO Operator on the Hub via the ACM-FC interface (GUI/CLI)
- **ACM-FC Hub:**
 - Deploys the CODECO Operator component
 - Initializes the CAM Engine for application model parsing
 - Initializes the CNC (CODECO Neighbourhood Composer) plugin to define cluster groupings (neighbourhoods)

2. CODECO Component Deployment

- **ACM-FC Hub:**
 - Triggers the deployment of CODECO components to the Hub and the MCx clusters
 - ACM-FC Hub deploys components to the Hub cluster as:
 - SWM-L1: Centralized scheduler with metrics collection on the Hub
 - NetMA IDC0: Hub-side network overlay controller
 - MDM-FC: Metadata management core service
 - ACM-FC Hub deploys components to MCx (MC1 & MC2):
 - SWM-L2: Distributed scheduler agents for each cluster
 - NetMA-FC: Probing and secure network overlay (control + worker planes)
 - PDLC-FC: Policy-driven logic controllers (control plane only)
 - MDM Connectors: Communication bridge between MDM-FC Hub and cluster local systems

At the same time, a monitoring loop is started by three components:

- NetMA-FC probing continuously captures network metrics (e.g., delay, jitter, energy) at both link and path level. These metrics are published as CRs and consumed by both PDLC and ACM.
- MDM-FC connectors collect and update data-related metadata such as compliance and locality. It builds and exposes a knowledge graph, which integrates with other components using custom connectors.
- ACM monitors user-defined preferences and potentially user behavior, which may later be used to adjust the CODECO control logic accordingly.

Figure 6: Sequence diagram, setting up CODECO across federated clusters. Example for an environment with a single Hub and x Managed clusters.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

2.5.2 Deploying an Application across a Federated CEI Environment

- To deploy an application, the user DEV interacts directly with the ACM-FC Hub component as provided in Figure 5.
- The process starts with the developer preparing the CAM for the application, based on YAML or on the ACM-FC GUI. Via this interface, user DEV defines aspects such as desired *Quality of Service (QoS)*, *Quality of Experience (QoE)*, or other desired performance levels that are expected for the application, based on the syntax provided in CAM. **The current attributes considered in the CODECO Application Model are provided in Annex I.**
- The CAM file describes the application's services and their runtime requirements, for instance, QoS, QoE. The user submits the CAM via the ACM GUI or CLI, and from there, ACM takes over the orchestration setup.
- When receiving the CAM description for the application, ACM-FC Hub queries the CNC to obtain a proposal for the application neighbourhood. The neighbourhood is fixed at deployment time but will be periodically re-evaluated.
- The next step is then to activate the overall logic of the CODECO framework **within the specific neighbourhood (N1)**.
 - ACM-FC Hub translates the CAM to the SWM-L1 Application Model
 - SWM starts by checking a possible placement
 - In parallel, ACM-FC Hub triggers and passes to PDLC-FC the location (master node identification) for the PDLC-FC agents that will interact within the neighbourhood.
 - PDLC-FC begins by collecting all relevant input data (CAM-defined requirements, network status from NetMA, compute metrics from Prometheus via ACM) and computes context-aware costs for each node and MC.
 - PDLC-FC also handles the learning logic. Based on the collected CODECO metrics, it generates scheduling recommendations and sends them to SWM as annotated node costs to be written in the SWM CRD "AssignmentPlan".
 - NetMA receives the initial deployment from SWM and sets up the required network overlay.

To orchestrate an application, it is assumed that CODECO will check possible resources across all managed clusters handled by a Hub cluster and if required (to do out of scope in this version of CODECO) it may consider MCs handled by other Hub clusters. This search may be too intensive (bandwidth, processing, time) and therefore, it is important to consider a partitioning approach that can assist in reducing the problem space to search for each application.

2.5.3 Management of Applications during their Runtime

Once the deployment is complete, CODECO enters the runtime support phase. At this point, the application is already deployed and running as a set of containers, each assigned to one or more pods, and placed across different MC clusters.

For example, let's assume Application Group A includes two microservices, a1 and a2. Based on the CAM and placement decisions, a1 is deployed on MC1 and a2 on MC2. Both clusters are managed under the same Hub (Hub1).

At this stage, we assume that each application is scoped within a single hub cluster (i.e., neighbourhoods are local to one hub), which keeps the system design simpler and avoids the complexity of cross-hub orchestration.

If a re-evaluation is needed at runtime—for example, due to performance degradation, resource exhaustion, or updated requirements—the ACM triggers the process by notifying the CODECO components. PDLC reacts by generating updated behaviour estimates and pushes them to SWM-L2 using the I-PDLC-SWM-2 interface (CR-based). SWM then initiates a new workload placement calculation. Once the new assignment is computed, SWM updates the relevant CRs (AssignmentPlan, ApplicationGroup) and PDLC observes the results (I-SWM-PDLC-1). There's no direct feedback channel—the CRs themselves serve as the coordination mechanism.

At the same time, ACM reports the overall system and application state to the user, relying on the CODECO metrics exposed via Prometheus.

3 CODECO Components Specification and Implementation

3.1 ACM-FC: Automated Configuration Management

3.1.1 Component Description

Like the ACM single cluster operation, [ACM-FC](#) acts as the entry point to the CODECO platform, encompassing three core roles: **CODECO framework configuration and deployment; user interfacing; application lifecycle management and monitoring coordination.**

As described in section 2.5.1, ACM-FC first role is to install, configure and maintain the CODECO framework. Users will deploy the CODECO framework by first installing the ACM component, which will subsequently install all other CODECO components as well as any ancillary dependencies (e.g. OCM, Prometheus). A key aspect of this role within a federated multi-cluster environment is to ensure that all components are properly configured on the necessary managed clusters, as well as ensuring that any subsequent clusters that are onboarded into the CODECO federated cluster environment are seamlessly configured, such that they can be automatically integrated into CODECO for deploying and managing applications.

ACM-FC also provides the core interface with the user via the CAM, an augmented application descriptor that facilitates more expressive application specification, as well as providing detailed user feedback as to the performance of the application across the multi-cluster. ACM-FC also provides the graphical user interface that provides the user with an intuitive interface to deploy and manage CODECO applications.

Finally, once an application deployment request has been created by the user, ACM is then responsible for managing the lifecycle of the application. Initially ensuring that the application is scheduled and deployed across the multi-cluster, orchestrating multiple other components to identify the appropriate clusters (SWM Scheduler) and then deploy the application to these target clusters (OCM). It also orchestrates application updates and removal based on user input. As part of the execution of the application, ACM also leverages the federated monitoring framework (Prometheus and Thanos) to monitor the state of each application and key performance metrics, that are then reported to the user via the CAM.

3.1.1.1 Architecture Overview

Figure 7: Representation of ACM-FC across a single HUB and two MCs.

ACM-FC integrates several sub-components, each with specific responsibility for delivering and managing critical ACM functions. ACM builds upon the open-source *Cloud Native Computing Foundations (CNCF) OCM* platform for managing federated clusters.

At the heart of ACM is the ALM (**Application Lifecycle Manager**) sub-component. This is responsible for monitoring for new, updated or removed CODECO Application CRs and then managing the state of the application in line with this. ALM works closely with SWM to trigger scheduling of the application to the appropriate cluster or node. In the federated cluster scenario, ALM leverages OCM to distribute the scheduled application to the target clusters. This work is currently in progress.

ALM also interfaces with the external **CNC** via the sub-component **Neighbourhood Manager**, such that the target neighbourhood clusters for a given application are captured, along with any required meta-data relating to the clusters. The Neighbourhood Manager is then responsible for distributing this information throughout the Neighbourhood, as well as general management of the Neighbourhood lifecycle (update and delete).

ALM also interfaces with the ACM-FC **Monitoring** component, to track and report on the performance of each application. Once an application has been deployed, the ACM-FC Monitoring component is notified and begins extracting coarse grained metrics relating to that specific application from the federated monitoring framework, based on Prometheus and Thanos. This data, collected via different CODECO components (ACM, MDM, NetMA) is populated into the CAM status object, which is discussed in more detail in the next section.

The **Multi-Cluster Configuration (MCC)** component is another key part of the ACM-FC architecture. This component is responsible for installing and configuring the entire CODECO framework across the federated cluster environment. The MCC leverages the OCM framework, particularly OCM Policies, which provide a governance framework for the multi-cluster. Specifically, MCC dynamically generates policies for all CODECO components, which ensures that they are installed and configured in the correct location, while also enforcing adherence to these policies throughout the life of the system. In other words, this ensures that the CODECO framework is constantly kept in the desired configuration state despite erroneous or malicious attempts to modify the component configuration. It also ensures that new clusters

added into the CODECO federated cluster environment are automatically onboarded and brought to the desired configuration state.

Finally, ACM as the entry point to the CODECO framework, also provides a **Graphical User Interface** where users can generate, deploy and monitor their CODECO Applications. Further details on the specific features of the UI are given in the subsequent sections.

3.1.1.2 The Federated CODECO Application Model

By design, the CODECO Application Model is largely agnostic to whether an application is for single-cluster or multi-cluster deployment. As such there are no significant modifications to the CAM from the previous single-cluster deliverables. However, we will review the model and outline any subtle changes that have occurred.

Figure 8: representation of the CODECO Application Model. The user provides application and micro-service requirements in the Spec section; ACM-FC gathers status based on the CODECO monitoring and writes it in Status.

The declarative spec section of the CAM contains the core definition of the application, where the application is comprised of multiple services (*codecoapp-msspec*) which can be interconnected via *serviceChannels*. *serviceChannels* consist of the id of another service endpoint as well as a *serviceClass* (*BestEffort* or *Assured*). There are further *advancedChannelSettings* that allow further (optional) specification of more fine-grained channel control.

The application **Spec** provides application requirements by the user, based on metrics defined in D10, and which have been revised as presented in Annex I. These metrics are the basis to select specific nodes and clusters for deployment.

The Status provides the user with information on the application monitoring and performance, as well as on the infrastructure performance. These values are reported as aggregates at the application level (*appMetrics*), service specific values (*serviceMetrics*) and for the nodes where the application micro-services are deployed (*nodeMetrics*). The metrics presented in Status are provided in Annex I. The values themselves primarily revolve around core compute metrics (e.g., CPU, memory, node energy consumption); network metrics (e.g., latency, link energy consumption), data observability (e.g., age of information). Derived from aggregated metrics collected by NetMA and further worked in PDLC, ACM-FC passes to the Status other metrics as described in Annex I.

To deploy an application, the user (DEV) can rely on YAML or on the CODECO ACM-FC GUI. This is a Web-based solution for deploying and managing CodecoApp resources within Kubernetes clusters through the ACM-FC operator. This interface eliminates the complexity of direct YAML manipulation and kubectl commands, providing users with a platform for application lifecycle management. The GUI integrates with the underlying ACM operator infrastructure, ensuring that all deployments maintain consistency.

When relying on YAML directly, there are two proposed ways to create the CAM for an application:

- **Method 1:** YAML Generator (form-based deployment). The YAML Generator provides a guided, form-based approach to creating and deploying CodecoApp resources. This method is recommended for new users and scenarios where you're creating applications from scratch.
- **Method 2:** YAML Upload (file-based upload).

3.1.1.2.1 Method 1: YAML Generator

1. Application Metadata: Identity & Namespace Context

The metadata section serves as the foundational identity for your application within the Kubernetes ecosystem. It defines how the application is named and scoped as follows

```
apiVersion: codeco.he-codeco.eu/v1alpha1
kind: CodecoApp
metadata
  name: my-app # Unique identifier in the cluster
  namespace: he-codeco-acm
```

Where:

- *metadata.name* defines a unique, Kubernetes-compliant name for the application.
- *metadata.namespace* scopes the deployment to a particular namespace, often preconfigured by the cluster administrator.

2. Microservice Specification: Defining Container Workloads

The *codecoappmsspec* section breaks down each microservice, allowing you to describe its networking needs and container configuration:

```
spec:
  codecoappmsspec:
    - nwbandwidth: "100Mbps"
  nwlatency: "50ms"
  podspec:
  containers:
    - name: web-server
      image: nginx:1.21
  ports:
    - containerPort: 80
  name: http
  protocol: TCP
  resources:
  limits:
    cpu: "500m"
    memory: "512Mi"
  requests:
    cpu: "250m"
    memory: "256Mi"
```

3. Real-Time YAML Generation & Validation

As users populate the form, the generator produces a YAML preview in real time. This preview reflects the current configuration and helps ensure the structure remains valid:

```
# Example
apiVersion: codeco.he-codeco.eu/v1alpha1
kind: CodecoApp
metadata:
  name: my-edge-app
  namespace: he-codeco-acm
spec:
  appName: "My Edge Application"
```

- **Key Features:**

- Syntax Highlighting for better readability.
- Live Validation flags structural or formatting issues.
- Immediate Feedback lets users correct errors before deployment.

4. Deployment Pipeline

Once the YAML is finalized, submitting it triggers an internal backend process that validates and applies the configuration to the Kubernetes cluster.

5. Observability & Post-Deployment Verification

Once deployed, the system provides visibility into application status and health:

- Custom Resources View: Displays registered CodecoApp resources.
- Pod Monitoring: Tracks the running state and readiness of pods.
- Log Access: Facilitates debugging by exposing logs directly from the GUI.

These features offer operational transparency and support quick troubleshooting.

3.1.1.2.2 Method 2: YAML Upload (File-Based Deployment)

The YAML upload method provides a flexible, file-based approach to deploying CodecoApp resources directly from existing YAML configurations. This method is recommended for experienced users and scenarios where you have pre-written YAML files, CI/CD integration requirements, or need access to advanced Kubernetes features not available through form interfaces:

File Input Methods: Direct Upload & Inline Editing

The upload interface supports multiple input methods to accommodate different workflows and user preferences:

Drag-and-Drop File Upload

Simply drag your “.yaml” or “.yml” file directly onto the upload zone. The system automatically reads the file content and populates the editor for review and modification.

File Browser Selection

Click the "Browse" button to open your system's file explorer and select YAML files from your local filesystem, network drives, or mounted volumes.

Direct Paste & Inline Editing

Use the built-in Monaco code editor to paste YAML content directly or compose configurations from scratch with full syntax highlighting and intelligent auto-completion.

3.1.2 Sub-components' Specification and Implementation

3.1.2.1 Application Lifecycle Manager

The ALM is the core component of the ACM responsible for managing the complete lifecycle of CODECO applications. ACM monitors for new, updated, or removed CodecoApp CRs and orchestrates their deployment, monitoring, and management across the federated cluster environment.

Controller Pattern

The lifecycle manager follows the Kubernetes Controller pattern, implementing a reconciliation loop that ensures the desired state matches the actual state of applications in the cluster.

```
// CodecoAppReconciler reconciles a CodecoApp object
type CodecoAppReconciler struct {
    client.Client
    Scheme *runtime.Scheme
}
```

Reconciliation Process

The reconciliation process follows these key steps:

1. **Resource Retrieval:** Get the CodecoApp CR from the cluster
2. **SWM Integration:** Create or update corresponding SWM Application resources
3. **Metrics Collection:** Query Prometheus for application and node metrics
4. **Status Update:** Update the CodecoApp status with current (coarse grained) metrics and state

Main Reconciliation Logic examples and links to code are available in References.

3.1.2.2 ACM-FC GUI

The [CODECO ACM-FC GUI](#) provides a web-based solution for deploying and managing CodecoApp resources within Kubernetes clusters. The GUI eliminates the complexity of direct YAML manipulation and kubectl commands, offering users an intuitive platform for application lifecycle management.

Architecture Overview

The CODECO GUI is implemented as a containerized two-tier web application that integrates seamlessly with the ACM operator:

- **Frontend Architecture**
 - *Technology Stack*: React 18 with PatternFly UI components
 - *Purpose*: Provides the user interface for CodecoApp management
 - *Code*: [gui/frontend/](#)
- **Backend Architecture**
 - *Technology Stack*: Node.js with Express.js framework
 - *Purpose*: Kubernetes API integration and business logic
 - *Location*: [gui/backend/](#)
- **Integration with ACM Operator**
- The GUI is deployed as part of the ACM operator ecosystem and shares the same namespace and RBAC permissions. It leverages the operator's service account to interact with Kubernetes resources.

Key Feature:

Our solution offers a comprehensive suite of features designed to streamline application management. The YAML Generator facilitates application creation through an intuitive form-based interface, while the YAML Upload feature provides flexibility with direct file upload and editing capabilities. For ongoing oversight, Application Monitoring delivers real-time status and metrics visualization. Furthermore, our Multi-cluster Support ensures seamless management across federated clusters via a unified interface.

In conclusion, the CODECO GUI represents a comprehensive solution for managing CodecoApp resources, providing both novice and expert users with the tools needed for effective Kubernetes application lifecycle management within the ACM operator ecosystem.

3.1.2.3 Neighbourhood Manager

The Neighbourhood Manager is a core component of ACM, responsible for managing dynamic cluster neighbourhoods within CODECO. These neighbourhoods are logical groupings of Managed Cluster resources associated with specific CODECO applications, which are proposed to be defined by an external component, the CNC. A single Managed Cluster may belong to multiple neighbourhoods as has been described in section 2.

The Neighbourhood Manager maintains the definition of each neighbourhood after creation and propagates this information to the relevant Managed Clusters, making it accessible to other CODECO components. It ensures consistency across the system by reflecting any updates to neighbourhood definitions in all associated clusters.

Upon deployment of a CODECO application, the [ACM controller](#) initiates a reconciliation loop that waits for the associated neighbourhood to be defined. This includes identification of its constituent clusters. As this functionality is not fully implemented yet, a hardcoded list of clusters and sample cluster claims are currently used, as shown below:

```

// Function to create neighborhood whenever user deploys codecoapp
managedClusters := []codecov1alpha1.ManagedClusterRef{
    {
        Name: "cluster1",
        ClusterClaims: []codecov1alpha1.ClusterClaim{
            {Name: "id.k8s.io", Value: "cluster1-unique-id"},
        },
    },
    {
        Name: "cluster2",
        ClusterClaims: []codecov1alpha1.ClusterClaim{
            {Name: "id.k8s.io", Value: "cluster2-unique-id"},
        },
    },
}
m, err := r.NeighbourhoodReconciler.CreateNeighbourhood(ctx, managedClusters, codecoAppCR)

```

Figure 9: pre-release of the semantic definition of neighbourhood in CODECO.

The ***NeighbourhoodReconciler.CreateNeighbourhood*** function creates a Custom Resource (CR) representing the neighbourhood. A sample neighbourhood CR can be found at [config/samples/codeco_v1alpha1_neighbourhood.yaml](#). This CR is then distributed to the relevant managed clusters via ACM-FC Hub, in communication with OCM.

To facilitate this, an *OCM Manifest Work* resource is created within the appropriate namespaces on the Hub cluster. This Manifest Work defines the neighbourhood CR and ensures its propagation and application to the corresponding managed clusters. Through this mechanism, each cluster is kept informed of its neighbourhood memberships. An example manifest work for the above list of clusters (cluster1, cluster2) can be found at [config/multicluster/example_manifestwork.yaml](#).

The Neighbourhood Manager also handles cluster removal and dynamic cluster updates. The [Neighbourhood controller](#) implements a reconciliation loop that is triggered by events related to managed clusters, such as deletions or metadata updates (e.g., labels, cluster claims). It leverages the OCM ManagedCluster API to retrieve and manipulate the relevant cluster resources as part of the neighbourhood management process.

```

// Reconcile handles ManagedCluster events and manages neighbourhood resources accordingly
func (r *NeighbourhoodReconciler) Reconcile(ctx context.Context, req ctrl.Request) (ctrl.Result, error) {
    logger := log.FromContext(ctx)
    logger.Info("Reconciling ManagedCluster", "cluster", req.Name)

    // Fetch the ManagedCluster instance
    managedCluster := &clusterv1.ManagedCluster{}
    err := r.Get(ctx, req.NamespacedName, managedCluster)

    if err != nil {
        if errors.IsNotFound(err) {
            // ManagedCluster was deleted
            logger.Info("ManagedCluster deleted, handling removal", "cluster", req.Name)
            return r.HandleRemovedManagedCluster(ctx, req.Name)
        }
        logger.Error(err, "Failed to get ManagedCluster", "cluster", req.Name)
        return ctrl.Result{}, err
    }

    // Handle ManagedCluster updates to check for cluster claims changes
    logger.Info("Handling ManagedCluster update", "cluster", req.Name)
    return r.HandleUpdatedManagedCluster(ctx, managedCluster)
}

```

Figure 10: Reconciliation loop for the Neighbourhood assigned MCs, based on the OCM ManagedCluster API.

Cluster Removal

When a Managed Cluster is removed from the Hub, the Neighbourhood Manager automatically deletes it from all associated neighbourhoods and cleans up any related resources, including the corresponding Manifest Work. This logic is encapsulated in the **HandleRemovedManagedCluster** function, which is part of the neighbourhood controller implementation.

Dynamic Cluster Updates

The Neighbourhood Manager continuously monitors and propagates changes across managed clusters. When new metadata such as labels or cluster claims relevant to CODECO is added or updated in a managed cluster, these changes are synchronized in real-time and reflected in the neighbourhood configurations.

[This](#) POC utilizes cluster claims, which are custom resources within managed clusters that define additional metadata.

```

apiVersion: cluster.open-cluster-management.io/v1alpha1
kind: ClusterClaim
metadata:
  name: id.k8s.io
spec:
  value: myCluster

```

Figure 11: Example Cluster Claim applied to cluster removal within the CODECO definition of neighbourhood.

After applying the *ClusterClaim* presented in Figure 12 to any MC, the value of the Cluster Claim is reflected in the Managed Cluster on the Hub cluster as exemplified in Figure 12.

```

apiVersion: cluster.open-cluster-management.io/v1
kind: ManagedCluster
metadata: ...
spec: ...
status:
  clusterClaims:
    - name: id.k8s.io
      value: myCluster

```

Figure 12: ClusterClaim reflected in the Hub cluster.

These claims are collected and updated in the status of the corresponding Managed Cluster object on the Hub. Any such update triggers the Neighbourhood Manager to reconcile the change, leading to the regeneration and redistribution of the associated Manifest Work resources across relevant clusters. This process is handled by the **HandleUpdatedManagedCluster** function, which ensures consistent propagation of updated cluster attributes system wide.

Figure 13: Neighbourhood Manager, ACM-FC sub-component functional representation.

3.1.2.4 Monitoring

In the single-cluster phase of CODECO, the monitoring subcomponent within ACM utilizes Prometheus to collect relevant metrics and update the status of CAM. The implementation leverages Prometheus recording rules to pre-compute frequently used or computationally expensive PromQL expressions. These rules generate new time series, effectively acting as a cache for query results, enabling faster and more efficient data access. The *PrometheusRule* CRD, managed by the Prometheus Operator, defines the recording rules for evaluation. Metrics are collected across multiple layers including pod-level, node-level, and service-level and are pushed to CAM to reflect the operational state of deployed CODECO applications.

3.1.2.4.1 Monitoring Rules Initialization

Prometheus rules are initialized from the [/prom_rules](#) ACM directory, which contains YAML-formatted rule definitions. The **InitializePrometheusRules** function orchestrates the process of reading these rule files and applying them as *PrometheusRule* CRs, as represented in Figure 14: Example for the initialization function of Prometheus rules.

```
func InitializePrometheusRules(r *CodecoAppReconciler) error {
    // Read the rules from the specified directory
    rules, err := readPrometheusRulesFromDir("/prom_rules")
    if err != nil {
        return err
    }

    // Apply the rules to the cluster
    return applyPrometheusRules(r, rules)
}
```

Figure 14: Example for the initialization function of Prometheus rules.

3.1.2.4.2 Metrics Collection

The monitoring subsystem employs a multi-level approach to metric collection:

- **Application-Level Metrics:** Aggregate metrics for each application using queries such as `count(pod:pod_info:current{created_by_name="<app-name>"})` for pod count.
- **Service-Level Metrics:** Granular workload-level metrics collected through pod-specific queries such as `pod:container_cpu:rate1m{pod="<pod-name>"}`. This enables detailed monitoring of individual service components.
- **Node-Level Metrics:** Infrastructure-level monitoring such as CPU usage: `instance:node_cpu:rate1m`

3.1.2.4.3 CAM Status Updates

Collected metrics are integrated into the [CodecoApp CR](#) status via updates, as explained in section 3.1.1.2. This is performed with the method `getMetricsFromPrometheus`, represented in Figure 15.

```
getMetricsFromPrometheus(codecoAppCR)
err = r.Status().Update(ctx, codecoAppCR)
if err != nil {
    fmt.Print("Error updating codecoAppCR")
    return ctrl.Result{}, err
}
```

Figure 15: Method that updates the CAM status, based on periodic collection of metrics from Prometheus.

3.1.2.4.4 Thanos

In the multi-cluster phase of CODECO, Thanos¹³ is employed to enhance the scalability and observability of monitoring systems across distributed Kubernetes clusters. Thanos extends the native capabilities of Prometheus by enabling cross-cluster data aggregation and introducing a global query layer, thereby supporting centralized monitoring and analysis across multiple clusters.

Unlike traditional Prometheus federation, which requires querying and transferring large volumes of data between individual Prometheus servers, Thanos provides a more efficient architecture. It enables direct access to distributed metrics from a single query endpoint, significantly reducing the operational load on individual Prometheus instances and improving system performance.

Thanos integrates seamlessly with Prometheus through the remote write interface, which allows Prometheus servers to send metrics to a remote storage endpoint rather than storing them locally. Thanos is supported by the Prometheus Operator simplifying deployment and management. Additionally, Thanos is interoperable with visualization tools such as Grafana¹⁴.

3.1.2.4.4.1 Thanos Components

Thanos is composed of several modular components, each designed to extend Prometheus in a scalable and distributed manner suitable for multi-cluster environments.

The *Thanos Query* component, commonly referred to as the *Querier*, provides a unified query interface that aggregates data from multiple Prometheus instances via the Thanos Receiver. It supports Prometheus's native query language (PromQL) and offers a global view of metrics across clusters, enabling centralized querying and analysis.

The *Thanos Receiver* provides a scalable remote write endpoint compatible with Prometheus. It enables Prometheus instances to push metrics data directly to Thanos without requiring a sidecar, making it suitable for environments where remote write is preferred over scraping. The Receiver can ingest data from multiple Prometheus sources and stores it locally using the *Time Series Database (TSDB)* format. It integrates seamlessly with the Querier to provide query access to the ingested metrics.

The Thanos Ruler is responsible for evaluating recording and alerting rules at a global level. Similar in function to Prometheus's native rule engine, it extends this capability across multiple data sources, allowing centralized definition and execution of rules over federated data. This is particularly useful in multi-cluster environments, where rules may depend on metrics from several sources.

3.1.2.4.4.2 Thanos Architecture in a Multi-Cluster Setup

A PoC (branch [acm-thanos-remote-write](#)) has been implemented by deploying a centralized cluster hosting core Thanos components, alongside two managed clusters configured with Prometheus instances that remotely write metrics to the central Thanos cluster. The primary Thanos components (Thanos Receiver, Thanos Ruler, and Thanos Querier) are deployed in the central cluster, along with Grafana for visualization.

¹³ <https://thanos.io/v0.10/thanos/getting-started.md/>

¹⁴ <https://grafana.com/>

Each managed cluster runs a local Prometheus server responsible for scraping metrics from its respective Kubernetes resources. This PoC utilizes the *kube-prometheus-stack*, a Helm chart that bundles core monitoring components including the Prometheus Operator, Grafana, and related exporters to provide a complete monitoring solution for Kubernetes environments.

Monitored data from each managed cluster is sent to the Thanos Receiver in the hub cluster via Prometheus remote write. The Receiver stores the incoming data locally. The Thanos Querier in the hub cluster handles queries by accessing this data from the Thanos Receiver.

The Thanos Querier UI provides a dashboard interface like that of Prometheus. It supports PromQL and serves as the central access point for querying aggregated metrics. ACM can query the Thanos Querier to retrieve metrics, which will then be reflected in the CAM status. Grafana will access the Thanos Query component to retrieve the required data for populating the dashboards. The Thanos Ruler is configured to write its rule evaluation results to the Thanos Receiver. It queries metrics from the Thanos Querier by referencing its endpoints through the Query Endpoints configuration. A functional representation of the interconnection to ACM-FC is provided in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Thanos to ACM-FC and Prometheus interconnections.

3.1.2.4.4.3 Ruler Configuration

Ruler requires the Rules to be passed via *ConfigMap*:

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: ConfigMap
metadata:
  name: thanos-ruler-rules
  namespace: monitoring
data:
  alert_down_services.rules.yaml: |
    groups:
    - name: example-recording-rules
      interval: 30s
      rules:
      - record: instance:cpu_usage:avg
        expr: avg(rate(node_cpu_seconds_total[5m])) by (instance)
      - record: cluster_cpu_average
        expr: avg(container_cpu_usage_seconds_total) by (cluster)
```

Figure 17: Example for a Thanos ConfigMap.

Thanos uses external labels, defined in each Prometheus instance, to identify the source of time series data. Among these, the cluster label is commonly employed to distinguish between different Prometheus servers running in separate environments. This labelling enables Thanos to aggregate metrics from multiple Prometheus instances into a unified global view. The cluster label is configured as an external label within the Prometheus configuration (rf. to Figure 18) and is automatically included in all-time series data and propagated to Thanos components such as the Querier (rf. to Figure 19).

```
## External labels to add to any time series or alerts when communicating with external systems
##
externalLabels:
  cluster: "test"
```

Figure 18: Example configuration of an external cluster label for a Prometheus instance in an MC.

The screenshot shows the Prometheus Querier UI. At the top, there is a search bar with the query `avg(node_cpu_seconds_total) by (cluster)`. Below the search bar, there are two checkboxes: Use Deduplication and Use Partial Response. Below the checkboxes, there are two tabs: **Table** and Graph. The Table tab is active, and it shows a table with two columns: the first column contains labels like `{cluster="stage"}` and `{cluster="test"}`, and the second column contains numerical values like `1794.96578125` and `1797.4242968750004`. Above the table, there is a navigation bar with left and right arrows and the text "Evaluation time".

Labels	Value
{cluster="stage"}	1794.96578125
{cluster="test"}	1797.4242968750004

Figure 19: Example for cluster labels reflected in Querier UI.

3.1.3 ACM-FC and Sub-components Code Structure

The Neighbourhood Manager PoC, available via the [CODECO ECL GitLab](#), has the structure described in Table 1:

Table 1: ACM-FC sub-component Neighbourhood Manager code structure.

File	Function
config/crd/bases/codeco.he-codeco.eu_neighbourhoods.yaml	Neighbourhood CRD
config/multicluster/example_cluster_claim.yaml	Example cluster claim
config/samples/codeco_v1alpha1_neighbourhood.yaml	Sample Neighbourhood CR
controllers/neighbourhood_controller.go	Neighbourhood Controller

The Thanos monitoring PoC has the code structure summarized in Table 2: ACM-FC to Thanos Monitoring PoC code structure.

Table 2: ACM-FC to Thanos Monitoring PoC code structure.

File	Function
deploy/central-cluster-thanos/thanos-remotewrite	Thanos Receiver and Querier configuration
deploy/central-cluster-thanos/thanos-ruler	Thanos ruler configuration
deploy/central-cluster-thanos/grafana	Grafana deployment
README.md	Readme

ALM code structure is described below in Table 3.

Table 3: ACM-FC sub-component ALM code structure.

File	Function
UML-Diagrams/ ApplicationModel_Update.svg	Unified Modelling Language (UML) diagram of the application model
prom_rules	Directory containing Prometheus rules YAML files
prom_rules/example.rules.yaml	An example Prometheus rule file
controllers/ codecoapp_controller.go	Contains logic for reconciling CODECO CR
config/samples/ codeco_v1alpha1_codecoapp_ver3.yaml	Sample CODECO CR YAML file
config/crd/bases/codeco.he-codeco.eu_codecoapps.yaml	CODECO CR definition
README.md	Instructions on how to deploy and run.

Table 4: ACM-GUI sub-component for deploying applications and monitoring microservices

File	Function
gui	Web-based interface for the CODECO ACM
gui/frontend/src/App.js	Main React application component orchestrating the containerized two-tier web application
gui/frontend/src/components/Navigation.js	Navigation interface for intuitive platform access eliminating kubectl command complexity

gui/frontend/src/pages/Yaml/YamlGenerator.js	YAML Generator feature providing form-based interface for application creation and lifecycle management
gui/frontend/src/pages/Yaml/YamlUpload.js	YAML Upload feature offering direct file upload and editing capabilities for flexible deployment
gui/frontend/src/pages/Monitoring/MonitoringDashboard.js	Application Monitoring component delivering real-time status and metrics visualization
gui/backend/	Node.js with Express.js framework handling Kubernetes API integration and business logic
gui/backend/index.js	Backend server integrating with ACM operator ecosystem and Kubernetes API for resource management
gui/backend/deployment/deployment.yaml	Backend deployment configuration for containerized deployment within ACM operator namespace
gui/README.md	Comprehensive documentation for the web-based solution supporting both novice and expert users

3.1.4 Next Cycle features

Table 5: ACM-FC next cycle features.

Sub-component	Feature enhancements
ALM-SWM integration	One of the core areas of focus in the next cycle is the integration between ACM-FC and SWM-FC, specifically for a multi-cluster environment. To date, the ALM component manages the lifecycle of the application by instructing SWM to schedule a CODECO app <i>within a single cluster</i> . Given that the architecture of SWM will change for the MC context, including the addition of the Neighbourhood concept, we must now modify this integration point to consider the updated SWM architecture. Similarly, as ACM/OCM already considers a mechanism to deploy resources across multiple managed clusters, our intent is to support SWM in leveraging this mechanism as part of its multi-cluster scheduling.
CAM	Handling of dependent resources (configmaps/secrets/roles/etc) of CODECO applications Support for Replica sets in CAM In phase 2 we plan to enhance our CAM is to integrate a ReplicaSet option for the user. This will allow our applications to maintain a desired number of pod replicas, ensuring high availability and resilience. By incorporating ReplicaSet management directly into the app model, we gain tighter control over scaling behavior and automated recovery in the event of pod failures.
ACM-FC support for non-K8s systems	An additional CODECO concept that has not yet been addressed is the ability for CODECO to manage non-Kubernetes devices. We are currently designing a solution for this problem based on the newly released FlightCtl project (https://github.com/flightctl/flightctl), also known as RedHat Edge Manager, which is designed to manage fleets of (non-Kubernetes) edge devices. Our solution proposes to adapt FlightCtl to allow for tighter native integration into Kubernetes, enabling CODECO to deploy and manage CODECO applications on these non-native K8S devices from within a Kubernetes-native platform

3.2 PDLC-FC: Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-Awareness

3.2.1 Component Description

PDLC in the FC phase integrates AI-driven capabilities to analyse the infrastructure and application deployment dynamic data behaviour, extract meaningful insights, and identify patterns, having as main goal to support the CODECO scheduler (or any future variation of scheduling applicable to the CODECO principles) in the informed decision-making for optimal application workload allocation.

Within a single-cluster operation [1][2], PDLC provides recommendations on the nodes where the application micro-services should be deployed. It focused on analysing solely the nodes' behaviour and providing deployment recommendations based on the target performance profiles selected by the user, such as greenness or resilience.

In FCs, PDLC extends this concept based on a Multi-Agent Decentralised Learning (MARL) instantiation, where PDLC FC Agents run on the control plane of MCs, as represented in Figure 5.

PDLC in the –FC phase, consists of the same components that were already provided in [PDLC](#) (single cluster Toolkit):

- [Data Processing \(PDLC-DP\)](#) is responsible for the collecting of Prometheus metrics (derived from NetMA, ACM, MDM) and for its normalization.
- [Context Awareness \(PDLC-CA\)](#) is responsible for creating aggregate costs for nodes and clusters, based on user defined profiles such as greenness or resilience.
- [PDLC Decentralised Learning based on GNNs \(PDLC-DL GNNs\)](#) provides estimations for the usage of the infrastructure, based on computational and networking metrics.
- [PDLC Decentralised Learning based on Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning \(PDLC-DL RL\)](#) provides intelligent application placement recommendations (nodes, cluster) based on the processed data and detected patterns.

3.2.1.1 Functional Overview

A functional representation of PDLC is provided in Figure 20. The metrics periodically provided by ACM, MDM, and NetMA to Prometheus are obtained by DP and normalized so that they can be used by different PDLC-FC sub-components. PDLC-CA relies on these metrics (including user-defined metrics) to generate node and cluster aggregated costs. Such aggregated costs are used by PDLC-DL RL (which becomes MARL), together with the estimation inputs on infrastructure metrics provided by PDLC-DL GNNs. The output (recommendations) is passed to the SWM L2 CRD AssignmentPlan.

Figure 20: Functional, high-level representation of the PDLC sub-components, and of their interactions.

PDLC as represented in Figure 5 is placed in the control plane of MCs. Its interactions are confined to exchanging information and performing collaborative learning exclusively with other PDLC components that belong to the same defined neighbourhood, in strict alignment with established security and privacy requirements.

Figure 21 depicts the evolution of the PDLC component in the FC phase, and its conceptual architecture, highlighting the functionally enhanced sub-components during the FC phase. It also presents the corresponding interfaces that represent the communication mechanisms with other CODECO components, ACM, MDM, NetMA, and SWM.

In the FC phase, PDLC does not undergo a complete transformation in its logic or structural nature; rather, it is functionally enhanced to incorporate global knowledge from the broader federated cluster ecosystem. This enhancement ensures highly secure information exchange across clusters while addressing the challenges posed by heterogeneous, multi-tenant environments—where both diverse regulatory compliance legal frameworks and data communication aspects introduce additional layers of complexity.

The critical need for robust security, coupled with the goal of minimizing single points of failure that can create bottlenecks during the training process, necessitates a shift toward a fully decentralized architecture. Unlike traditional federated learning models, which often follow centralized or hierarchical designs, the proposed approach adopts a non-centralized and non-hierarchical structure in which all the PDLC components within a federated environment operate independently within their respective clusters yet remain aligned in pursuit of shared objectives. The major enhancements introduced during the FC phase are the following: i) the implementation of efficient data management mechanisms required by the heterogeneous environment; and ii) the integration of a continuous process governed by security-driven rules to enable cross-cluster learning. These advancements aim to generate more robust recommendations for application workloads deployed and executed across federated edge–cloud continuum ecosystems. These changes are reflected in the extended functionalities of PDLC during the FC phase. While the core PDLC FC sub-components remain unchanged in terms of their structural entities, modifications are introduced and are presented Table 6.

Figure 21: Conceptual Architecture of the PDLC Component during the FC phase (Example with two MCs), including internal sub-components and communication Interfaces.

Table 6: Comparison of PDLC Component Functionalities Between the Single Cluster (SC) and Federated Cluster (FC) Operation.

Sub-component	Description	SC	FC
PDLC-DP	Data Preprocessing	Collects cross-layer metrics from CODECO components (ACM, MDM, NetMA), performs preprocessing operations, and stores formatted data as CSV-formatted files using a PVC.	Collects the same metrics from CODECO components via Prometheus and performs enhanced preprocessing, and stores data in PDLC DB for more structured and scalable storage. It also handles Kubernetes secrets and config maps needed for the rest of PDLC's sub-components.
PDLC-DB	Database	Not available; pre-processed data is stored directly in CSV-formatted files into a PVC.	Newly introduced component enabling improved data management and aggregation. Incorporates robust privacy-preserving mechanisms for initialization, read/write access, and secure

Sub-component	Description	SC	FC
			data sharing (solely within the cluster).
PDLC-CA	Context-Awareness	Retrieves the processed DP normalized data from the PVC, applies cost aggregation formulas for target profiles greenness and resilience providing a final aggregated cost to each node.	Retrieves data from PDLC-DB and applies more advanced heuristic formulas for CAM defined target performance profiles (greenness, resilience, etc). Supports user-defined metrics. Provides aggregated costs for the user selected target profiles, for nodes and clusters. The resulting node and cluster costs are passed to PDLC-DL and can be directly used by SWM, or any other Kubernetes-compatible scheduler.
PDLC-DL (GNNs)	Infrastructure forecasting using Graph Neural Networks	Utilizes pre-processed data in CSV-formatted files from the PVC along with network topology to forecast CPU and memory usage. These forecasts are used as input for the PDLC-RL model to enhance workload recommendation accuracy.	Retrieves compute data from PDLC DB and the network topology from a Kubernetes Config-Map. Adds support for dynamic model selection to accommodate varying numbers of nodes in federated environments. Supports learning parameters exchange among GNNs (FedGNN functionality) across the clusters to enhance the robustness of the forecasted values.
PDLC-DL (MARL)	Reinforcement Learning-Based workload recommendation engine	Uses inputs from PDLC-DP (via PVC in the form of CSV-formatted files), the performance profiles from PDLC-CA, and forecasts from PDLC-DL (GNNs) to trigger an inference-based RL agent. Outputs workload recommendations to the CODECO-SWM component in the form of CRs.	Uses same inputs as SC phase, but model is extended to MARL where multiple decentralized RL agents are incorporated, enabling distributed learning across federated clusters. Moreover, an auction-based algorithm is utilized to evaluate and recommend inter-cluster workload placements. Also, the MARL model is trained online, improving its performance over the time

3.2.1.2 Sequence Diagram and Operational workflow

The PDLC component in the FC phase introduces a continuous workflow in which all sub-components interact in a coordinated and adaptive manner. Figure 22 depicts the sequence diagram illustrating this persistent execution process, emphasizing the seamless integration of decentralized intelligence and secure information exchange among the various elements of the CODECO architecture.

Figure 22: Main interactions between the PDLC sub-components in the FC phase (example with MC1 and MC2).

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

The sequence in Figure 22 begins with PDLC-DP, which initiates with the real-time collection of cross-layer data from Prometheus, data which has been provided by the monitoring sub-components in ACM-FC, NetMA-FC, and MDM connectors.

Following a series of data pre-processing operations, this data is forwarded to the PDLC-DB sub-component (InfluxDB¹⁵), which functions as the main data repository. Each MC therefore holds an instance of PDLC-DB. PDLC-DB supplies the required pre-processed data to both PDLC-CA and PDLC-DL (GNNs) to support their individual functionalities. PDLC-CA produces performance profiles (*CAResults*), while PDLC-DL (GNNs) generates forecasts for future resource consumption (*GNNResults*). These outputs collectively form a comprehensive situational snapshot of the current and anticipated state of the cluster. With respect to the PDLC-DL (GNNs), learning parameters are exchanged at designated time intervals to facilitate collaborative learning. Once a model completes its training session, its weights—secured through encryption techniques—are distributed to the GNNs residing within the peer PDLCs.

Subsequently, the PDLC-DL (MARL) module is activated. It consolidates the outputs from PDLC-CA and PDLC-DL (GNNs), along with the required pre-processed metrics from PDLC-DP, to initialize its decision-making pipeline. The PDLC-DL MARL-agent drives intelligent decisions related to workload adaptation and resource optimization. When new workloads are introduced, the PDLC-DL MARL agent coordinates with peer PDLC-MARL agents across other federated clusters to assess potential candidates capable of accommodating these workloads. Once the workload recommendations are estimated, they are communicated to SWM (L2) component, which is responsible for executing the workload migration across the federated infrastructure.

As illustrated in Figure 31 the data acquisition, the learning part on both the GNNs and MARL, and the decision-making processes are designed to operate in continuous loops. This reflects the iterative and adaptive nature of PDLC's operational workflow, ensuring real-time data capturing, learning, and recommendation estimation. Such a distributed and dynamic architecture enables the PDLC component in the FC phase to maintain high levels of responsiveness, resilience, and coordination across heterogeneous clusters in the edge–cloud continuum, while maintaining its distributed nature and its ability to align efficiently with diverse multi-tenant clusters.

3.2.1.3 PDLC FC Interfaces

In the FC phase, PDLC interacts with all other CODECO components, reflecting its integrative role and functional scope. It engages with the ACM to retrieve compute-related metrics, with NetMA to collect network-related data, and with MDM to obtain data-centric metrics. Furthermore, as PDLC is responsible for generating intelligent-driven recommendations, it also establishes communication links with the SWM component to deliver these outputs.

3.2.2 Sub-components' Specification and Implementation

3.2.2.1 PDLC-DP

The [PDLC-DP](#) sub-component is relevant for the decentralised learning embodied in PDLC-DL.

In the FC phase, PDLC-DP retains its core functionalities, with the primary enhancement being the integration of InfluxDB. Both of its modules continue to serve their original purposes. The use of a dedicated databases instead of a PVC improves the component's autonomy and

¹⁵ <https://www.influxdata.com/products/influxdb/>

privacy by removing reliance on Kubernetes-native PVC resources and ensuring that all processed data remains securely contained within the component itself. As a result, each PDLC instance within a cluster is provisioned with its own InfluxDB instance, which is exclusively responsible for storing cluster-specific data following the completion of the relevant preprocessing operations. This InfluxDB instance is instantiated and initialized during the deployment of the entire PDLC component. The *Gatherer* module is responsible for creating the InfluxDB instance and generating the associated access credentials—specifically, the username, password, and access token—which are mandatory during the initial setup of any InfluxDB instance. These credentials are dynamically generated and securely stored within Kubernetes Secrets, ensuring that they remain inaccessible to any external entity. Access to the InfluxDB instance for read and write operations is strictly granted to designated PDLC sub-components: PDLC-CA, PDLC-DL-GNNs, and PDLC-DL-MARL. Also, the Gatherer still collects the specific metrics composing the topology (overlay and underlay) and stores it within a Kubernetes ConfigMap, because it is not preferable to be saved in InfluxDB due to its structured schema.

A functional representation of PDLC-DP is provided in Figure 23. The *Gatherer* collects, via the MC Prometheus instance, the metrics provided by the Monitoring CRs in ACM, MDM (Connectors) and NetMA.

The collected data is stored in the local database. The database data structure is provided in Annex I.

The *pp_module*, which is triggered upon the arrival of new data from the *Gatherer* and subsequently performs specialized data processing operations to prepare the data for further handling by the remaining PDLC sub-components.

Figure 23: Functional representation of PDLC-DP code components, and interfaces to other CODECO components, within each MC.

3.2.2.1.1 Sequence Diagram and Operational workflow

In the SC phase, the PDLC-DP-PP module persistently stores the results of each pre-processing cycle—generated from data ingested by the PDLC-DP-Gatherer—in structured CSV files within a dedicated PVC. While this file-based approach suffices for localized SC deployments, it becomes limiting in the FC phase, where scalability, performance, and federated data coordination are essential. To address these demands, the PVC is replaced with a DBMS, offering enhanced capabilities for data management and aggregation. Given the inherently time-series nature of the metrics handled by PDLC-DP, InfluxDB—a specialized NoSQL TSDB—has been selected as the optimal storage backend. Its support for high-throughput ingestion, efficient time-based querying, and retention policies makes it particularly suited to the operational needs of PDLC and its sub-components. Figure 24 provides the PDLC-DP sequence flow in the FC phase.

Figure 24: Main interactions of the PDLC-DP component with the other MC CODECO components in the FC phase.

3.2.2.1.2 Implementation details

During the FC phase, the primary modifications to the PDLC-DP component involve the initialization, connection, interaction with the InfluxDB instance and the proper data storing into it. All other operations related to pre-processing remain unchanged. Regarding InfluxDB, at this stage, the Gatherer is responsible to continuously collect the cross-layer metrics as it is reported in ANNEX I as well as initializing the InfluxDB instance. The latter is achieved by deploying InfluxDB as a dedicated pod, which is part of the PDLC-managed pod collection. InfluxDB offers three supported methods for completing its initial setup: (i) through its dedicated UI, (ii) using the InfluxDB CLI, or (iii) via the provided REST API. For the PDLC component the third option is selected to reflect the automation of the process. The initial setup requires the creation of the following components: an organization with a user-defined name, a bucket similarly with a user-defined name, an admin authorization that includes: a specified username and password, an API operator token and read and write permissions for all resources within the InfluxDB instance. Therefore, all these essential elements must be initialized as part of the PDLC setup process. The Gatherer module is responsible for generating and configuring these elements. Specifically, the Gatherer uses the InfluxDB REST API to dynamically generate the required credentials—including bucket names, organization names, usernames, passwords, and tokens—without relying on static prefixes. The credentials are

not static and are created in the time of initialization while also being securely stored in Kubernetes Secrets, from which they can be accessed by the other PDLC sub-components. With the replacement of the PVC by InfluxDB, the management and aggregation of cross-layer metrics collected from the CODECO components have been significantly improved. This enhancement is not limited to management efficiency alone but also extends to privacy protection, as the overall design increases the security levels of the component in line with its name and intended purpose—privacy-preserving by nature. To support the specific requirements of each PDLC sub-component, dedicated data collections (each one for each PDLC sub-component) are initialized accordingly. Following InfluxDB principles, the term *bucket* functions as a logical database, while the term *measurement* serves a similar role to a table in traditional databases but is specifically designed to store and organize time-series data. Table 7 depicts the buckets, and the measurements used to serve all the PDLC sub-components along with the proper operations and privileges.

Examples for the data worked by PDLC-DP towards each PDLC sub-component are listed in Table 7.

The measurements listed in Table 7 represent the data with which each sub-component interacts to perform its functionality. The data handled by the PDLC-DP sub-component, which are configured with read privileges for the rest of the PDLC sub-components, maintain the same features as in the SC phase.

Table 7: Data output of PDLC-DP, examples.

Measurement name	Description
test_node_metric	Node-related resource metrics exploited by the PDLC-DL
test_integration_metric	Pod-related resource metrics exploited by the PDLC-RL
context_metrics	Cross-layer node-related metrics exploited by the PDLC-CA
cpu_memory_metrics	Node-related resource metrics exploited by the PDLC-DL GNNs

3.2.2.1.3 Code structure

Table 8 provides a description of the CODECO PDLC-DP main source files that received modifications to adapt in the FC phase of CODECO.

Table 8: PDLC-DP Code Structure.

File	Function
src/pp_module/ca.py	Handles data pre-processing for the PDLC-CA component to calculate performance profile scores. The pre-processed data is now written directly to the InfluxDB pod under the context_metrics category.
src/pp_module/gnn.py	This script pre-processes data for the PDLC-DL (GNNs) component to generate CPU and memory forecasts. The core logic, including normalization and dynamic min-max calculations per time window, remains unchanged. The output is placed in the MC PDLC-DB under cpu_memory_metrics .
src/pp_module/rl.py	This script pre-processes data for the PDLC-DL (MARL) component to generate node and neighbourhood clusters' recommendations. The logic remains unchanged from previous versions. The only change is that results are now stored in the InfluxDB pod under test_node_metric and test_integration_metric .

File	Function
src/pp_module/utilities.py	This script contains a set of support functions that are utilized by the src/pp/module/ca.py , src/pp/module/gnn.py , and src/pp/module/rl.py scripts to facilitate data management operations related to storing pre-processed data in the InfluxDB pod.
src/gatherer.py	This file corresponds to the internal logic of the <i>Gatherer</i> that is responsible for gathering the metrics collected by CODECO. Once the dataflow is initialized the gatherer creates queues for providing the data to the preprocessing module using threads, each one for each PDLC subcomponent.
src/influx_class.py	This script introduces a class to provide management of the InfluxDB setup and secure handling of access credentials.
src/server.py	The additions with this script have to do with its usage of <i>the influx_class.py</i> file.
src/pdlc-deployment.yaml	The PDLC_DP deployment YAML file remains unchanged with respect to its core functionality and configuration. The only additions introduced are the deployment of a dedicated InfluxDB pod and the definition of the corresponding InfluxDB service, which enables internal communication between the PDLC-DP component and the InfluxDB instance for time-series data storage. These additions do not affect the main operation of the PDLC-DP component.
src/pdlc-dp-role.yaml	The specific YAML file for the PDLC-DP component remains unchanged with respect to its intended access permissions and overall functionality. It continues to provide the necessary resource access within the Kubernetes environment to support the component's operation. The recent additions to the deployment, specifically the inclusion of an InfluxDB pod and its corresponding service for time-series data storage, do not alter the ClusterRole configuration, as these additions operate independently of Kubernetes API resource permissions.

3.2.2.1.4 Selected Technologies

The PDLC-DP sub-component has been designed and developed entirely by using the Python programming language (version 3.10+). The respective additional packages that were used during the component's development are listed below along with their relevant description:

- **influxdb-client:** library is the official Python client for interacting with InfluxDB, a popular time-series database designed for efficiently storing and querying high-frequency, timestamped data such as resource metrics, logs, or IoT data.
- **prometheus-client:** library that consists of multiple modules which assist in connecting to a Prometheus host, fetching the required metrics and performing various aggregation operations on the time series data.

3.2.2.1.5 Pre-requisites

Rf. To README.md of the [PDLC-DP](#) code for a detailed list of requirements:

- At least a Hub and an MC need to be set.
- CODECO-FC and respective requirements need to be installed.
- Prometheus monitoring tool for scraping the cross-layer and custom metrics derived by the ACM-FC Agent, MDM-FC Connectors, and NetMA-FC components.
- The PDLC-DP components (Gatherer and Preprocessing modules) are to be installed as a standalone service. During this phase of the project, the PDLC-DP also initializes the

PDLC-DB component (InfluxDB). Once initialized, the PDLC-DP expects to receive metrics from the Prometheus instance located in the respective MC, to collect cross-layer and custom metrics.

3.2.2.1.6 Installation Guide

A detailed installation guide is available with the code of [PDLC-DP \(readme\)](#).

3.2.2.1.7 Input-Output

The PDLC-DP ingests metrics from the Prometheus instance. These metrics are provided by the ACM-FC Agent, MDM-FC connectors, and NetMA-FC of the respective MC. The component processes these inputs to generate pre-processed metrics, tailored to the specific requirements of each PDLC sub-component (PDLC-CA, PDLC-DL-GNNs, and PDLC-DL-MARL). The resulting datasets are stored in the PDLC-DB (InfluxDB) within the corresponding InfluxDB buckets and measurements.

3.2.2.2 PDLC-CA

[PDLC-CA](#) is a PDLC sub-module responsible for computing *cost perspectives* for nodes and clusters, based on target performance profiles selected by the user in CAM, during the deployment phase.

The PDLC-CA version integrated into CODECO-FC relies on inputs from other CODECO components (e.g., computational parameters such as CPU, memory; network parameters such as bandwidth, latency, link energy; data metrics such as data compliance, data size) via from Prometheus. The existing parameters are combined to serve a selected performance profile, such as optimising the infrastructure for greenness, resilience or for target performance profiles defined by the user in CAM. The performance profile, which is currently defined statically in the code, will be an attribute of the CODECO application model selected by the user DEV during the deployment of an application. The reader should check D10 for an explanation on the computational principles and rationale behind the PDLC-CA operation (single cluster mode).

3.2.2.2.1 Sequence Diagram and Operational Workflow

The PDLC-CA component is responsible for computing context-aware cost metrics that guide workload placement across clusters in the CODECO architecture. Figure 25 provides the overall operational workflow. The process is implemented through a series of Python scripts that interact with external systems such as InfluxDB and the Kubernetes API. The workflow is orchestrated by the `main.py` script, which acts as the central controller for the pre-processing and evaluation pipeline.

The process begins with `main.py` invoking `influx_handler.py` to retrieve the most recent node-level metrics from InfluxDB. These metrics are stored in the `context_metrics` measurement and typically include values such as network delay, energy usage, and compliance indicators. Once retrieved, the data is passed back to `main.py`, which then delegates to `cost_evaluator.py` to fetch the cost evaluation profiles. These profiles define how different metrics should be weighted and normalized and are stored in a Kubernetes ConfigMap. `cost_evaluator.py` accesses the Kubernetes API to read this configuration and returns the necessary profile data to `main.py`.

With both raw metrics and cost profiles available, `main.py` calls `process_and_store_costs()` in `cost_evaluator.py`, which performs the core computation. This involves applying predefined cost equations to the input data to derive node- and cluster-

level scores. These scores represent how suitable each node is for hosting workloads, considering the current context.

Finally, the computed scores are passed back to `influx_handler.py`, which writes them to the InfluxDB time-series database under a dedicated PDLC-RL bucket. This makes the data available for downstream consumers, such as PDLC-DL or even the SWM scheduler or other CODECO orchestration components, enabling them to make informed placement decisions based on real-time, context-aware information.

Overall, the PDLC-CA component operates as a modular, stateless evaluator that transforms raw system metrics into actionable cost profiles used throughout the federated CODECO platform.

Figure 25: PDLC-CA workflow, FC operation.

3.2.2.2.2 Implementation details

The PDLC-CA-FC implementation consists of a modular Python-based pipeline that retrieves context metrics, evaluates node and cluster cost profiles, and stores results for orchestration decisions in the CODECO framework.

The PDLC-CA-FC branch provides a clean, modular implementation of the context-awareness engine for federated CODECO environments. It separates concerns between:

- Control logic (`main.py`)
- Data access (`influx_handler.py`)
- Cost modelling (`cost_evaluator.py`)

The **configuration setup** is based on the [pdlc_ca_configmap.yaml](#) ConfigMap, which can be used by user DEV to define metrics to use (e.g., delay, energy), weights, normalization rules. It can also be used to consider scoring-based on user-defined metrics.

3.2.2.2.3 Pre-defined Target Performance Profile Scoring: Resilience and Greenness

PDLC-CA-FC provides a way to rely on the CAM defined target performance profiles, and to consider new profiles.

The pre-defined profiles are resilience and greenness. The way the aggregated score to define resilience or greenness is provided can be changed by the user, by providing new equations

based on available, normalized CODECO metrics. An example for a specific aggregated cost profile for node scoring (resilience) is provided in Figure 26, and for greenness (where the queries were defined by the user) is provided in Figure 27. In this example CO2 is assumed to be custom-defined metrics (see section 58), and *avgNodeEnergy* is a CODECO pre-defined metric, collected by ACM-FC. Their normalized forms are referenced with the *normalized_* prefix.

```
profiles:
  - name: Resilience
    equation: "normalized_avgNodeFailure * normalized_uNodeNetFailure * 1 / oNodeDegree"
```

Figure 26: PDLC-CA-FC, example for a cost scoring defined for node resilience.

```
profiles:
  - name: UserDefined
    equation: "cm_normalized_co2 * normalized_avgNodeEnergy" # Mixes custom and built-in metrics
```

Figure 27: Pre-defined target profile greenness, with equation defined by the user, based on CO2 footprinting.

3.2.2.2.4 User-defined Node and Cluster Scores

In addition to the pre-defined target profiles and respective heuristics, a user can define additional target profiles and change the scoring functions applied to pre-defined target performance profiles.

To ensure consistent behaviour, only specific metrics are available in normalized form and can be safely used in profile cost equations. In the current code version, metrics available that start with the prefix *normalized_* can be used in profile equations.

Examples of normalized metrics that can be used to generate user-defined aggregate costs for nodes and cluster:

```
normalized_avgAppCpu
normalized_avgAppMemory
normalized_avgNodeEnergy
normalized_avgNodeFailure
normalized_oNodeNetFailure
normalized_uNodeNetFailure
normalized_uNodeBandWidth
normalized_uLinkEnergy
uNodeDegree # **not normalized**
```

Note:

- Do **not** use the reserved profile names *Greenness* and *Resilience*, as they are pre-defined examples.
- When creating **custom metrics**, avoid reusing any metric names or equations defined in Annex I.

An example for a defined custom target profile is provided in Figure 28. If developers want to define custom metrics to be used in the aggregated score equations along with their Prometheus queries and normalization ranges, they must follow the format provided in Figure 28. Specifically:

- *name*: Logical name of the metric (referenced as *cm_normalized_<custom_metric_name>* in profile equations)

- *promQL*: The raw Prometheus query for the metric must include **instance label**, which identifies the Kubernetes **node name**
- *min, max*: Required to enable proper normalization of the raw metric value.

```

custom_metrics:
  # CO2 footprint metric (example; requires exporter pushing node_co2{instance} to Prometheus)
  - name: co2
    min: 0
    max: 20000
    promQL: 'avg by (instance)(irate(node_co2{instance}[5m]))'

```

Figure 28: PDLC-CA-FC example for defining a custom target performance profile.

3.2.2.2.5 Implemented Strategies for Cluster Scoring

In the context of federated application placement (e.g., within CODECO), cluster-level ranking is required to evaluate how well a cluster meets a desired performance profile.

In the current PDLC-CA-FC implementation, two strategies are considered to provide cluster level scoring based on node scores:

- **Strategy 1, average of node scores.** This method computes the mean score across all nodes in the cluster. It assumes that all nodes contribute equally to the overall performance of the cluster. The cluster score reflects the overall suitability, smoothing out variations across nodes. It is appropriate when the application workload needs to be distributed across multiple available nodes, and emphasizes the average performance scoring, over extremes (min, max). It is more suited for general purpose application deployment.
- **Strategy 2, Norm of score vector.** This strategy treats the node scores as a vector in N-dimensional space and computes its Euclidean norm (L2 norm). It captures both the magnitude and variance of the individual node scores. Clusters with many high-performing nodes will naturally rank higher. It emphasizes the aggregate strength of the most “popular nodes” (in terms of nodes in the cluster), penalizing low-performing nodes. It is therefore considered suitable for resource-intensive or bursty application deployment.

3.2.2.2.6 Code Structure

The PDLC code structure is represented in Table 9.

Table 9: Summary of main PDLC-CA source code files.

File	Function
Main.py	The entry point script that coordinates the entire CA processing loop.
Influx_handler.py	Manages InfluxDB connections
	Data extractor, it fetches the normalized metrics from the data_CA.csv file stored in the PDLC shared volume and makes the metrics available as a return of the function <code>get_metrics()</code> .
cost_evaluator.py	Calculates normalized cost profiles
configmap.yaml	Enables user defined cost computation rules (weights, metrics)
ca-controller-deployment.yaml	Deploys the module as a pod in the Hub cluster

3.2.2.2.7 Installation Guide

A [detailed installation guide is available with the code of PDLC-CA \(readme\)](#).

3.2.2.2.8 Selected Technologies

PDLC-CA has been implemented in Python 3 Input and output are based on YAML (CRD).

3.2.2.2.9 Pre-requisites

Rf. to the [README of the](#) PDLC-CA code for a detailed list of requirements:

- At least a Hub and an MC need to be set.
- CODECO-FC and respective requirements need to be installed.
- InfluxDB (PDLC-DB) MUST be accessible
- Prometheus (for metrics)
- Kubernetes ConfigMap: `performance-profiles`
- Kubernetes Secret: `influxdb-token`
- InfluxDB buckets:
- CA: for reading input metrics # Generated by PDLC-DP
 - RL: for writing evaluated costs

3.2.2.2.10 Inputs and outputs

- Input of PDLC-CA corresponds to CODECO metrics and user-defined custom metrics, both normalized from, provided via PDLC-DP in influxDB.
- Output of PDLC-CA is provided in InfluxDB.

3.2.2.3 PDLC-DL - GNNs

PDLC-DL-GNNs in the FC phase subcomponent, consists of a Spatio-Temporal Graph Neural Network (STGNN), is responsible for producing node-level resource-usage predictions, specifically CPU and memory utilization, and storing them in PDLC-DB (InfluxDB). These forecasts are then provided as supplementary input to the PDLC-DL-RL (which is extended to MARL) sub-component, where they are used to inform and improve the workload placement decisions. As shown in Figure 29, the GNN model provides predictions for each node's resource usage within a cluster. PDLC-DL-GNNs is composed of three main components: (i) the Decentralized Federated Training, (ii) the Controller, and (iii) the Inference API. The Decentralized Federated Training component is responsible for training the GNN model in a decentralized, privacy-preserving manner. The Controller orchestrates data retrieval and triggers inference requests at regular intervals, while the Inference API performs resource forecasts. Specifically, every minute the **Controller** reads from PDLC-DB (InfluxDB) the new values of CPU and memory usage per each node, which the PDLC-DP subcomponent gathers, normalizes and stores. The **Inference API** uses the latest historical observations, as well as the cluster topology, so that it can consider both the spatial and temporal dependencies of the nodes. Based on this input, the appropriate model is fetched from the Model Registry, and predictions are produced for 5-, 15- and 30-minute horizons. These forecasts are stored into InfluxDB under dedicated measurements so that the PDLC-DL (MARL) sub-component can retrieve them and use them as input. The models stored at the Model Registry are provided by the **Decentralized Federated Training** subcomponent. The latter ones are considered as enhancement in comparison with GNNs module provided in the SC phase, and its purpose is to orchestrate secure, peer-to-peer exchanges of encrypted model parameters among neighbouring clusters, ensuring privacy-preserving and scalable training without centralized data sharing. Bringing these elements together, Figure 29 illustrates how **FedGNNs** are integrated into the broader PDLC architecture during the FC phase. Each cluster contributes data for

training through a decentralized federated learning approach, coordinated by the PDLC-GNN module. Although training occurs across multiple clusters, the orchestration of model updates and storage of trained weights is handled centrally to ensure consistency and scalability. The Controller regularly retrieves data from PDLC-DB (InfluxDB) and invokes the Inference API to generate resource usage forecasts, which are then stored back in PDLC-DB (InfluxDB). These forecasts are used by the PDLC-MARL module to support adaptive workload placement decisions. This architecture enables secure, scalable, and collaborative GNN-based forecasting without requiring centralized access to raw data, preserving privacy across clusters.

Figure 29: PDLC-DL-GNNs functional scheme.

3.2.2.3.1 Sequence diagram and operational workflow

The workflow associated with the PDLC-DL-GNN subcomponent in the FC phase, is illustrated in Figure 30 and involves continuous coordination between the GNN Controller and the Inference service. The GNN Controller is responsible for periodically retrieving monitoring data, specifically CPU and memory metrics, from the “GNN” InfluxDB bucket. These metrics, written by the PDLC-DP subcomponent under the “cpu_memory_metrics” measurement, are fetched every minute for all nodes in the local cluster. Based on this data, the Controller constructs an appropriate request body and sends it as an API call to the Inference Service every minute. On the receiving end, the Inference Service continuously monitors the current cluster topology. Upon receiving an inference request, it identifies and loads the appropriate pre-trained GNN model from the Model Registry. Model selection is based on several factors: (i) the number of active nodes in the cluster, (ii) the target metric (CPU or memory), and (iii) the requested forecast horizon (5, 15, or 30 minutes). Once the Inference service is executed, the resulting forecasts are stored in the “RL” InfluxDB bucket under the corresponding measurements: “forecasts5”, “forecasts15”, and “forecasts30”, respectively. The pre-trained models are stored in the Model Registry component. The models are dependent on the number of nodes and, therefore, for the OSS CODECO Federated Toolkit, the existing pre-trained models currently correspond to 2 up to 8 node cluster topologies. Within the Federated Cluster (FC) phase, model training adopts a decentralized federated learning approach, enabling peer-to-peer training without raw data exchange. Each cluster performs locally training of the GNN model with respect to its own private data. During intermediate stages of training, each cluster exchanges masked model parameters (weights) with its immediate neighbours. These weights

are securely aggregated using a privacy-preserving scheme, and local training proceeds with updated parameters. This train-and-aggregate cycle is repeated iteratively until certain conditions are met.

Figure 30: PDLC-DL-GNNs sequence diagram.

3.2.2.3.1.1 Component description with new features and extensions

In the FC phase, the PDLC-DL-GNN sub-component retains its core functionality, to support PDLC-MARL by providing accurate forecasts, enabling it to make smarter, more context-aware node recommendations. This phase prioritizes key system qualities, scalability, mobility, security, and resilience, which are especially critical in complex multi-cluster environments. To address these needs, the architecture evolves toward Decentralized Federated GNNs, that enable collaborative learning across clusters without centralized data sharing. Security is a primary concern. In traditional centralized learning architectures, data is collected at a central point, exposing sensitive infrastructure and workload information to potential privacy risks. A decentralized approach eliminates this risk entirely; raw data remain within its originating cluster. Local training is performed independently, and only encrypted model parameters (weights)

are shared across clusters, ensuring that privacy is preserved by design. Scalability is achieved through fully distributed training. Each cluster maintains and trains its own GNN model using local data, avoiding the bottlenecks of maintaining a centralized global model. Model updates are handled in a peer-to-peer fashion; each cluster communicates only with its immediate neighbours. This local scope reduces communication overhead, and the system naturally scales as more clusters are added. Moreover, training occurs in parallel across all clusters, and aggregation is performed locally during federated learning rounds. This design ensures that the learning process remains fast, resilient, and scalable, even as the number of clusters increases. Mobility is handled through the inherent adaptability of GNNs to dynamic network topologies. In the CODECO environment, clusters and nodes may not be static. When a node rejoins the network, GNNs can dynamically fetch the appropriate pre-trained model, allowing it to re-integrate seamlessly into the federated learning process without having to retrain from scratch, preserving both learning continuity and system responsiveness. If the specific model is not available, the MLOps component will trigger model re-training, the latter will also be triggered in cases of performance drop. Resilience is addressed at multiple levels. At the system level, the architecture is built to avoid any single point of failure. Since all learning and communication occur in a peer-to-peer fashion, a failure in one cluster does not cause the collapse of the entire learning process. GNNs also promote local autonomy, even if global synchronization stalls or fails, each cluster retains its local GNN model and can continue making forecasts. At the model level, the architecture supports online federated re-training, which enables GNNs to adapt to slow data drift over time. This prevents performance degradation associated with outdated models. Additionally, through model versioning and rollback mechanisms, if a model update causes instability or starts propagating faulty behaviour, the system can detect this and revert to a trusted version.

3.2.2.3.2 Implementation details

The primary modifications involve establishing robust interaction with the InfluxDB instance and adapting the training component to support decentralized federated training within the PDLC-DL-GNNs framework. The transition from using PVC to utilizing InfluxDB for data storage and retrieval primarily revolves around the implementation of specialized Python scripts that leverage the proper influxDB library to establish communication. These scripts are responsible for handling the interactions between the system's sub-components—namely the training, controller, and inference modules—and the InfluxDB instance. Specifically, the scripts are designed to perform precise queries on the appropriate InfluxDB buckets and measurements to retrieve the necessary monitoring data required for the training and controller components. Additionally, they handle the storage of the forecasting results generated by the inference module, ensuring that all time-series data flows smoothly and is persistently stored in the correct format and location within InfluxDB. This modification enables a more streamlined and centralized approach to data management across the system.

Model training procedure

To preserve data locality while enabling collaborative learning across multiple clusters, we implement a decentralized federated training pipeline for our Spatio-Temporal Graph Neural Network (STGNN) models. Each participating cluster trains its own STGNN locally and shares only encrypted hidden-layer weights via a secure, API-based model exchange protocol. These shared weights are aggregated in a privacy-preserving manner and redistributed, allowing all clusters to benefit from broader knowledge without exposing raw data.

Model Structure and Training

Each cluster independently trains a model using a hybrid architecture consisting of:

- A **Graph Convolutional Layer (GraphConv)** for spatial feature extraction across nodes.
- A **LSTM Layer** for temporal modelling of time-series data per node.
- A **Dense Layer** to output multi-step forecasts.

This is implemented via the LSTMGC class in training.py, which combines the GCN and LSTM in a single module. The GCN uses a flexible aggregation strategy (e.g., mean, sum), and neighbour topology is encoded via the GraphInfo class.

Hidden Weight Extraction and Aggregation

Rather than sharing full model checkpoints, we isolate and extract only the trainable hidden-layer weights using:

- `get_hidden_weights(model)`: extracts GraphConv and LSTM weights.
- `aggregate_hidden_weights(weights_list)`: averages each layer type independently across all cluster models.
- `set_hidden_weights(model, aggregated)`: apply the new aggregated weights to a local model.

This minimizes data transfer size and enforces privacy by avoiding exposure of model-specific output layers or embeddings.

Secure Weight Masking with Diffie-Hellman and PRG

A major extension of our decentralized pipeline is the integration of secure weight exchange using encryption. Before sharing any model weights, each cluster applies a masking scheme that prevents the exposure of raw weights, even during transmission and aggregation. This is done using the following components:

- **Diffie-Hellman Key Exchange.** Each cluster independently generates a private/public key pair using `generate_dh_keypair(p, g)` where p is a large prime (shared among all participants) and g is a primitive root modulo p . Clusters then exchange public keys and compute pairwise shared keys via `derive_shared_key(private_key, peer_public_key, p)`.
- **Pseudorandom Mask Generation (PRG).** Using the derived shared keys, a deterministic pseudorandom generator (PRG) creates noise tensors of the same shape as the model weights: `prg(shared_key, shape, seed)`. This ensures consistent noise generation between any two clusters using the same shared key and seed.
- **Asymmetric Noise Masking.** The masking function `mask_model_weights(weights_dict, shared_key_row, cluster_id, n_clusters)` adds or subtracts PRG-generated noise to/from each weight tensor. The noise is asymmetric and pairwise balanced, this design ensures that during aggregation, the total noise cancels out. Only the original average of the weight remains, while individual model weights are protected during transmission.

Federated Training Orchestration

The federated training orchestrates the following:

- **Local Model Training.** Each cluster trains its own model independently on local data. Once training is complete, the model weights are extracted and securely masked as described above.

- **Model Weight Collection via API.** Instead of accessing model files via shared volume mounts, they are collected via a Flask-based APIs (STGNN_api/), issued as HTTP requests. Each peer cluster exposes a /upload-weights endpoint that accepts zipped masked model weights.
- **Aggregation.** This collected hidden weights are aggregated using a layer-wise averaging strategy. This results in a new set of shared weights representing the consensus across all clients.
- **Redistribution.** The aggregated weights are injected into the local STGNN model instance. The updated model is saved and can be redeployed for inference.

Model Exchange via API

Each cluster hosts a Flask server that exposes:

- POST /upload-weights accepts compressed model weight files (e.g., trained_stgnn_model_cpu_weights.zip) and unpacks them locally.

Example exchange workflow:

- Cluster A finishes training, encrypts and masks its weights, and sends them via API to Cluster B.
- Cluster B receives multiple peer weights (A, C, D ...), aggregates all received weights with its own, and updates its local model.

This process can be repeated for multiple rounds.

3.2.2.3.3 Code structure

The PDLC-DL-GNN sub-component main source code files are briefly summarized in Table 10.

Table 10: PDLC-DL-GNN

File	Function
Controller	
timeseries_data.py	Module that retrieves data from InfluxDB every minute and stores it locally.
Inference	
app.py	Code that implements the Inference Service API, detects the number of nodes in the topology dynamically, selects the appropriate models based on the number of nodes, makes the predictions, writes the forecasted values in the appropriate files and stores them into InfluxDB.
Training	
download_dataset.py	Code that downloads data from InfluxDB to be used for training.
Federated Training	
training.py	Code that defines the STGNN model architecture, including custom GraphConv and LSTMGC layers. Implements core utilities for federated learning, including weights extraction, aggregation,

	and secure encryption protocols based on Diffie-Hellman key exchange and pseudorandom masking.
main.py	Code that aggregates the hidden layers masked weights (Graph-Conv and LSTM) from several pre-trained STGNN models trained on different topologies and saves the aggregated model.

3.2.2.3.4 Selected technologies

- **Python:** programming language, version 3.10+.
- **InfluxDB:** an open-source time series database designed for high-performance storage, querying, and analysis of time-series data.

3.2.2.3.5 Pre-requisites

- At least a Hub and a MC need to be set.
- CODECO-FC and respective requirements need to be installed.
- In terms of data the PDLC-DB (InfluxDB) component is required to retrieve the input monitoring data and to store the output forecasts.
- The Cluster Topology ConfigMap (to identify the set of nodes and their relationships within each cluster) and the Neighbourhood Topology ConfigMap (to identify the set of clusters and their relationships within each neighbourhood) need to be available.
- The pre-trained models must exist in the Model Registry component.

3.2.2.3.6 Installation Guide

To deploy and test the GNNs subcomponent:

1. Deploy the Inference API Server

In the `gnn_inference.yaml`, specify the environment variables, where indicated by the commands.

```
cd STGNN_controller/inference
kubectl apply -f gnn_inference.yaml -n {namespace}
```

This file includes both **Deployment** and **Service** specifications. Once applied, a pod, a deployment, and a service are created in the K8s cluster.

Docker image: `hecodeco/pdlc-dl-gnns-stgnn-inference:3.0.0` (available on Docker Hub)

2. Deploy the Orchestrator

In the `gnn_controller.yaml`, specify the environment variables, where indicated by the commands.

```
cd STGNN_controller/orchestrator
kubectl apply -f gnn_controller.yaml -n {namespace}
```

This file includes a **Deployment** specification. Once applied, a pod, and a deployment are created in the K8s cluster.

Docker image: hecodeco/pdlc-dl-gnns-stggn-controller:3.0.0 (available on Docker Hub)

3. Deploy the Training Pod

In the **gnn_training.yaml**, specify the environment variables, where indicated by the commands.

```
cd STGNN_training
kubectl apply -f gnn_training.yaml -n {namespace}
```

This file deploys a **training pod** for running GNN model training tasks in the cluster.

Docker image: hecodeco/pdlc-dl-gnns-stggn-training:3.0.0 (available on Docker Hub)

4. Deploy the Federated Training Pod

In the **gnn_federated_training.yaml**, specify the environment variables, where indicated by the commands.

```
cd STGNN_federated_training
kubectl apply -f gnn_federated_training.yaml -n {namespace}
```

This file deploys a **federated training pod**, for federated training across clusters.

Docker image: hecodeco/pdlc-dl-gnns-stggn-federated-training:3.0.0 (available on Docker Hub)

3.2.2.3.7 Input-Output

The input data of the GNN inference service is retrieved from the “GNN” InfluxDB bucket and specifically the “*cpu_memory_metrics*” measurement. It includes the timestamp of the given values, the names of each node, the normalized CPU and memory values, as well as the minimum and maximum values with which the normalized values were calculated for both CPU and memory.

The output of the GNN inference service is stored in the “RL” InfluxDB bucket, using three dedicated measurements: “*forecasts5*”, “*forecasts15*”, and “*forecasts30*”, corresponding to forecast horizons of 5, 15, and 30 minutes, respectively. Each entry in these measurements includes the forecast timestamp, the name of each node, and the denormalized CPU and memory forecast values. In addition to this, the same forecast data is also written to local files located in the ‘outputs’ directory, specifically forecasts5.csv, forecasts15.csv, and forecasts30.csv., these files serve as auxiliary outputs for debugging, traceability, or offline analysis purposes.

3.2.2.4 PDLC-DL-MARL

The PDLC-DL-MARL component has been developed to enhance the models previously presented in deliverables D10 and D12. A significant advancement in this work is the expansion of the single-agent models to a multi-cluster environment through the application of MARL.

An auction-based algorithm is utilized within the MARL framework to combine the knowledge of locally trained agents, which in turn allows for the straightforward scalability of the original solution. MARL was selected as the methodology for this multi-cluster expansion for several compelling reasons:

- **Facilitates Expansion from Existing Reinforcement Learning Models:** MARL builds directly upon the established RL models within the CODECO project. It does so by employing an architecture inspired by Independent Proximal Policy Optimization, which allows for a seamless transition from a single-agent to a multi-agent system.
- **Offers Enhanced Robustness and Privacy:** The methods inherent to MARL provide robust and privacy-enhancing capabilities, which are well-suited to the requirements of the CODECO project.

Figure 31 presents the conceptual design of the PDLC-DL (MARL) component in the Federated Cluster (FC) phase. To extend the capabilities of the existing PDLC-RL component, all subcomponents have been enhanced to operate effectively in a federated environment. The component retrieves its input data from an InfluxDB instance, which is populated by the PDLC-DP module.

After data ingestion, the component supports both training and inference at runtime, enabling a flexible framework for reinforcement learning–based pod allocation optimization in cloud environments. A newly introduced **RL-controller** manages both inference and training workflows. This central controller oversees security validation, connection management, and runtime mode transitions across the PDLC-DL-MARL system.

Figure 31. Subcomponents of PDLC-DL MARL and their interactions with other components of PDLC.

The PDLC-DL-MARL (FC) component has been enhanced with improved implementations and new features while retaining its core functionalities. Significant modifications have been focused on three primary areas: (i) Training Controller, which allows for Online Training, (ii) data ingestion through InfluxDB instead of flat files for more efficient and secure data access, and (iii) the implementation of a MARL algorithm in the inference controller which enables competition among multiple clusters, thereby scaling the solution to a FC environment.

From an architectural point of view, we have made changes to both training and inference controllers with the addition of the connection to the influxDB in both cases.

3.2.2.4.1 Training Controller Enhancements

The trainer controller has also undergone substantial revisions. While the fundamental logic of the training loop is preserved, we now provide a fully integrated framework that enables the online training of Reinforcement Learning agents within the CODECO environment. This training can be initiated either from scratch or by using a pre-trained model as a baseline. Like the inference mode, the training environment connects to InfluxDB for data input and writes node recommendations to a custom resource. Models used have incorporated padding and action

masking to reduce the number of training processes needed in case of changes in the architecture:

- **Padding added to the model input and output:** our models had a weakness where models had to be retrained for different architectures given that the number of nodes was not the same as in the model. This posed a threat for the resilience of our models and scalability of the solution, for this reason we have added padding, allowing all models created by our framework to work with clusters with up to 20 nodes.
- **Action masking:** The number of possible actions has been increased to accommodate the padding introduced to our models; illegal actions are masked automatically by adding the following logic to our environment:

3.2.2.4.2 Inference Controller Enhancements

The fundamental logic of the inference controller and its pipeline remain consistent; the model continues to generate node recommendations for incoming pods and suitable re-allocations. A key architectural change is the replacement of CSV-formatted file inputs with a direct data stream from the InfluxDB database, which is managed by the PDLC-DP.

Furthermore, the component's multi-cluster capabilities are now handled by an auction-based algorithm that facilitates pod allocations between different clusters. This algorithm leverages the q-value, a core concept in RL. The q-value, defined as $Q(s,a)$, is an action-value function that calculates the expected return of taking a specific action a from a given state s and adhering to the current policy thereafter. This q-value is shared among agents to determine which cluster is best suited to allocate the pod.

Sharing the q-value offers distinct advantages over other MARL techniques that often require sharing model weights or parameters:

- **Enhanced privacy preservation:** The q-value does not reveal sensitive information about the internal workings of each agent. In environments where AI models must share parameters, attackers can exploit this process to manipulate model behaviour. By sharing only the q-value, our approach mitigates this risk and supports the design of a secure and private communication protocol.
- **Effective Solution Estimator:** The q-value serves as a reliable estimator of a solution's quality. This is crucial in a real-world scenario where the actual reward for an action is unknown until after the action is completed. It also gracefully handles situations where an action (a pod allocation) is skipped because another cluster performed it.
- **Secure Transmission:** To further bolster security, the q-value sharing process incorporates two key features. First, all transmitted data is encoded using Base64 encoding, and encrypted using AES-128-CBC with the decryption key stored securely as a Kubernetes secret. Second, a known secret is appended to all communications to function as a data integrity check. Upon receipt and decryption, the PDLC-DL-MARL component can verify if the data has been compromised and halt the pipeline if necessary.

3.2.2.4.3 Sequence Diagram and Operational Workflow

The sequence diagram in Figure 32 illustrates the workflow of the three controllers and shows the interaction between the PDLC-DL-MARL component and other CODECO components.

Figure 32. Sequence diagram showing the execution steps of PDLC-DL MARL and interactions between its subcomponents.

Figure 33 shows the communication process of the PDLC-FC-MARL model. When a new pod arrives, each PDLC-FC-MARL agent within the application neighbourhood calculates a **Q-value** for the best allocation action. The agents then encrypt and multicast their Q-values to each other. After receiving all values, the agent with the highest Q-value allocates the pod.

Figure 33. MARL communication process between PDLC-DL MARL components of different clusters.

3.2.2.4.4 Implementation details

PDLC-FC-MARL can operate in two distinct working modes, resulting in four possible operational combinations as detailed in Table 11. It should be noted that Multi-Cluster Training will be finalized based on experimentation within the framework of CODECO (M36, D14). Careful navigation in this topic needs to be considered due to the possibility of breaking the Markov property in the environment, thus affecting model performance.

Table 11: PDLC-DL MARL modes available in single and multi-cluster CODECO operation.

Modules	Single Cluster	Multi Cluster
Inference	Performs inference without the MARL logic (auction-based algorithm).	Performs inference and considers other agents within the same neighbourhood.
Training	Trains a model Online within Single Cluster operations.	Not available in this deliverable.

3.2.2.4.5 Code Structure

Table 12. List of PDLC-DL MARL source code files and description.

File	Description
co-deco_online_rl_env.py	Self-contained gymnasium environment, prepared for Online Training and connected to the CODECO APIs (via InfluxDB and connection to SWM CR).
inference_controller_FC.py	Code containing the inference logic detailed in the sequence diagram X.
influx_utils.py	Code containing functions to connect and extract data from the InfluxDB.
rl_controller.py	Code containing the controller for the MARL component, it ensures safety and connection checks are met before starting the component. After that the control flow of the component is engaged, allowing for changes in mode (from training to inference or single to multicluster operations) without restarting the component.

3.2.2.4.6 Selected Technologies

PDLC-FC-MARL is developed using **Python 3.12.7** and leverages a variety of libraries and tools, depending on the execution mode. A comprehensive list of all required dependencies is available in the accompanying `requirements.txt` file included in the codebase:

- **Inference:** During the inference phase, the primary libraries employed are StableBaselines3 and StableBaselines3-Contrib. Connectivity with other CODECO components is managed through the `influxdb-client` and `Kubernetes` libraries, facilitating robust data exchange and system orchestration. For prospective Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning (MARL) communications, the cryptography library is designated for secure message encryption and safeguarding shared values.
- **Training:** The training mode leverages a Gymnasium¹⁶ environment for model optimization. This framework is intricately connected to CODECO's APIs via InfluxDB for data acquisition and CRD writing for result persistence, thereby enabling real-time data-driven model training. The library suite for training mirrors that of inference, as the training paradigm encapsulates inference functionalities alongside dedicated model training logic.

The CODECO Online Environment is created inheriting from the Gymnasium base Environment, this environment has been created as a point of improvement from the one presented in Deliverable D11. Additionally, Pytorch¹⁷ is used to implement inference and training logics outside stable baselines3 default functions (for example, custom extraction of q-values).

3.2.2.4.7 Pre-requisites

Depending on the execution mode the pre-requisites of our framework will be different, the user can specify if the component is deployed by using the InfluxDB as the data input or synthetic data to test the component. The synthetic data mode has no prerequisites, as its purpose is to facilitate isolated testing of the MARL pipeline. In contrast, the InfluxDB mode requires a Kubernetes cluster with a configured PDLC component for the MARL system to function correctly.

3.2.2.4.8 Installation Guide

The MARL component is highly dependent on other CODECO components. For testing purposes of the component, we have created a mode where synthetic data is ingested in substitution of missing CODECO components, allowing for testing of the complete Online Training

¹⁶ <https://gymnasium.farama.org/>

¹⁷ <https://pytorch.org/>

and Inference Pipelines. To use this component to its full capabilities it is recommended that it is deployed with the full version of PDLC-FC. To install the component, the user can use the docker files or to install locally and execute it via python.

To facilitate the installation of the component in a Python environment, the following steps are recommended:

- **Virtual Environment Setup (Optional but Recommended):** It is advisable to install the component within a virtual environment to ensure dependency isolation and maintain reproducibility. Users may choose either venv or conda for this purpose. For example, using venv:

```
python3 -m venv .venv
```

- **Dependency Installation:** Once the virtual environment is activated, all required Python packages can be installed using the provided requirements.txt file:

```
pip install -r requirements.txt
```

This installation procedure ensures that the component is correctly configured with all necessary dependencies, providing a stable environment for development or deployment.

The entry point of the component is `rl_controller.py`, to switch in between CODECO connectivity and synthetic data connectivity (to test the full pipeline) an additional parameter must be passed when launching the controller, a value of **0** indicates that the component will operate with a direct connection to its CODECO interfaces. Conversely, a value of **1** signifies that the component will use synthetic data, a mode intended for component testing while integration is being finalized:

This will execute MARL connected with CODECO:

```
python rl_controller.py 0
```

This will execute MARL connected with synthetic data:

```
python rl_controller.py 1
```

For additional details regarding setup, configuration, and usage, please refer to the accompanying README.md in the respective [PDLC-FC-MARL repository](#) file provided with the source code.

3.2.2.4.9 Input-Output

All inputs used in our model are standardised via the usage of InfluxDB. For this version of the code to work, data must be provided by the PDLC DB component in the format that can be seen in Figure 34. In this figure we can see the MARL bucket which will contain 6 measurements in total:

- **Test_integration_metric:** measurement with the necessary data for incoming pods that the component is going to provide node_recommendations for, containing the name of the incoming pod, along with the namespace and the requested cpu and ram by the application.

- **Test_node_metric:** measurement with the cpu and ram available per node in the cluster, used to get the necessary information for the state of the MARL component.
- **Greenness_resilience_custom_metric:** measurement with the values provided by PDLC-CA which will be used both as input and as a part of the reward of the models used.
- **ForecastsX:** measurements with forecasts for 5, 15 and 30 minutes. Output provided by GNNs and used as the input of the models.

Figure 34. Schema of the InfluxDB RL Bucket used as input to PDLC-DL MARL.

This version of the model’s framework provides three different outputs:

- Trained models are currently stored locally within the MARL pod. In the future, we plan to integrate MinIO for more efficient model storage and retrieval
- Comprehensive debugging messages are provided to help in the incoming integration phase of the project and in checking the correct functioning of the full pipeline of the framework.

- Allocation proposals in the CR file provided as input. This is done through an attribute added to the SWM CR that indicates how likely a pod should be allocated to a node. For that purpose, a vector of size number of nodes for each pod that needs allocation is used, and for each node the degree of certainty of the pod being allocated to it is given. This is done through an attribute added to the SWM CR that indicates how likely a pod should be allocated to a node. For that purpose, a vector of size number of nodes for each pod that needs allocation is used, and for each node the degree of certainty of the pod being allocated to it is given.

3.2.3 Next Cycle Features

As the project advances into its final development phase, this section formally outlines the planned optimizations, feature extensions, and final adjustments required across all PDLC sub-components. The overarching objective is to ensure that each sub-component is comprehensively refined and fully aligned with the system’s functional and performance requirements, ultimately supporting the delivery of a stable, production-ready release. A summary of next cycle expected features for PDLC-FC and its sub-components is provided in Table 13.

Table 13: PDLC-FC next cycle features.

Sub-component	Feature enhancements
PDLC-DP	Future enhancements will focus on improving the normalization process to deliver more accurate normalized values. This will involve close collaboration among the CODECO components—ACM and NetMA—to define the minimum and maximum values for each feature that requires normalization.
PDLC-DB	This sub-component currently hosts only InfluxDB, and its management is handled by PDLC-DP. The planned enhancement involves integrating a dedicated server responsible for synchronizing multiple InfluxDB replicas. As a result, PDLC-DP will no longer manage the creation and administration of InfluxDB secrets. These responsibilities will be transferred to the PDLC-DB sub-component.
PDLC-CA	Validation and further improvement of the scoring functions (cluster, node) Integration of time-variant cluster scoring functions. Integration and customization for additional custom-defined metrics, based on the CODECO use-cases.
PDLC-DL (GNNs)	Future enhancements for this sub-component include refining the modelling of both inter- and intra-cluster topology by incorporating channel characteristics such as bandwidth into the topology matrices. Additionally, the forecasting capabilities of the system could be expanded beyond CPU and memory to include other critical resource metrics such as energy consumption and latency.
PDLC-DL (MARL)	Future changes of this sub-component will focus on improving the performance of the training and inference aspects, focusing on training times and performance of the provided node_recommendations. Additionally, we envision the implementation of a connexion with MinIO for model management, decentralized training for multiple clusters and the parameter sharing in between agents for MARL.
MLOps	In the final project phase, MLOps will be integrated with MARL and GNN to enable real-time retraining, automated model management, and deployment—creating a fully automated, adaptive, and reliable closed-loop system.

3.3 NetMA-FC: Network Management and Adaptation

3.3.1 Component Description

NetMA is a network management and adaptation solution that automates the setup of inter-connections for flexible Edge-Cloud operations, while addressing the integration of internet-working control and supporting the needs of diverse network environments (fixed, wireless, cellular) that are expected to be managed by CODECO. This CODECO component handles

aspects such as network softwarization, secure data exchange, network performance monitoring and integrated network capability exposure through standard-based mechanisms and Kubernetes APIs.

NetMA and its sub-components, along with the main interfaces towards other CODECO components, are represented in Figure 38. It currently considers the following sub-components:

- **Secure Connectivity (L2S-M)**. Secure Connectivity will extend its capabilities to support secure inter-cluster communication across CODECO workloads. The component is currently in its design phase, so the implementation details are defined but not yet disclosed.
- **Network State Monitoring (NSM)**. This sub-component allows the use of different network probing mechanisms to bring network status to CODECO. Network status is captured at an underlay and overlay perspective, also from an individual link and path perspective. Updates in this context relate with improvements to the existing single-cluster operation. Inter-cluster monitoring will be provided as a next cycle feature.
- **Network exposure system (Nemesys-FC)**. Nemesys brings the networking metrics (underlay and overlay) captured by NSM into Prometheus and exposes them in the CODECO system (via ACM) and will also be responsible for the inter-cluster exposure aspects.

3.3.2 Sub-components' Specification and Implementation

3.3.2.1 Secure Connectivity

To be provided in the next cycle.

3.3.2.2 NSM

3.3.2.2.1 NetMA-nsm-mon

Within the sub-component NSM, [netma-nsm-mom](#) (**monitoring**) is dedicated to active network monitoring (probing), bringing network management state at a link (underlay) level to CODECO.

netma-nsm-mon has been based on the existing open-source code of the [K8s netperf](#) licensed under Apache 2.0. and focuses on bringing active network probing to CODECO. The metrics considered were provided in Deliverable D10 and are again presented in Annex I.

The current implementation provides CODECO with the following networking metrics: i) bandwidth; ii) latency; iii) packet loss; iv) jitter; v) node degree; vi) link failures; vii) link energy; and access to other interface statistics.

- **Periodic Probing**: Probes are configured to run at set intervals, evaluating link/channel performance (underlay).
- **Metric Collection & Aggregation**: Raw probe results such as RTT, jitter, energy consumption are aggregated and averaged.
- **Exposing Custom Resources (CRs)**: Collected metrics are made available via Kubernetes CRs, enabling consumption by other NetMA components such as PDLC (learning) and SWM (scheduling).
- **Integration with Nemesys**: collected metrics are integrated with the NetMA Nemesys component.

3.3.2.2.1.1 Sequence Diagram and Operation Workflow

Netperf has been improved based on the original k8s-netperf code and has been upgraded to provide a better integration with Kubernetes, and upgraded with additional services, to provide the collection of a more extensive set of metrics. It currently relies on Netperf, iPerf, ping, tcpdump to collect latency, bandwidth, packet loss, node degree, link failure number, and link energy consumption.

The overall operation sequence can be tested in KinD based on the `deploy.sh` script. Assuming an environment with at least one MC cluster, and the use of KinD the first step is to ensure that the control plane of the MC is not tainted—by default, the control plane nodes are tainted to prevent workloads from being deployed there. However, as a monitoring mechanism, netma-nsm-mon requires untainting the nodes, so that the test pods based on Netperf can also run on the master nodes. A summary of the operation workflow is as follows (rf. to the sequence diagram provided in Figure 35 and placement of the netma-nsm-mon pods in Figure 36):

- **Deployment via Kubernetes:**
 - A [Cronjob](#) deploys the [network_probe.py](#) container at scheduled intervals.
 - k8s-netperf pods are deployed across nodes for network endpoints.
- **Metrics Collection:**
 - `network_probe.py` uses `kubectl exec` to run netperf, iPerf, ping, and optionally tcpdump within pods.
 - Gathers metrics including latency (TCP_RR), bandwidth, packet loss, node degree, link failure, or energy usage per link.
- **Storage & Exposure:**
 - Results are written to a flat key-value file like `netperfMetrics.txt`.
 - The file is then uploaded as a Kubernetes ConfigMap (e.g., `netperf-metrics-nodeX`), enabling cluster-wide visibility.
- **Consumption by NetMA Components:**
 - ConfigMaps are read by Nemesys.
 - Other CODECO modules (e.g., PDLC for learning & forecasting, SWM for scheduling) access these metrics via the Kubernetes API CRDs,

Figure 35: netma-nsm-mon sequence diagram.

Figure 36: netma-nsm-mon pod placement across control and service planes.

3.3.2.2.1.2 Implementation Details

The core probing operations are supported by two files:

- `network_probe.py`, which deploys the netma-nsm-mon on all available nodes (control, worker) within a cluster. This file is executed via the Kubernetes Manifest `cronjob.yaml`.
- `Netperf.py`, which is used by `network_probe.py`.

The script `network_probe.py`:

- Discovers Kubernetes nodes, pods, and services.
- Identifies netperf-compatible pods deployed on each node.
- Runs latency, bandwidth, packet loss, energy consumption, tests between all node pairs.
- Collects link layer metrics
- Writes the results to the Kubernetes ConfigMap `netperf-metrics`.

Node identification is performed at an IP and network interface:

```
local_ip = get_local_ip()
interface = get_interface(local_ip)
node_name = get_node_name(local_ip)
```

Latency measurement:

Probing functions have been implemented in a modular way, allowing to provide different scenarios, e.g., `measure_latency(...)` is currently set for TCP_RR (`netperf -t TCP_RR` for latency metrics (P50, P90, P99)). And provides results such as:

```
netperf.p90.latency.milliseconds.origin.nodeA.destination.nodeB=4.12
```

Node degree:

To measure the node degree, function `measure_node_degree(...)` pings the neighbour nodes and counts successful replies as “degree”:

```
node.degree.of.nodeA=3
```

Link failure:

Link failure is supported by `measure_link_failures(...)`. It pings all other nodes every 30s for N minutes, recording how many times each node failed to respond.

Link energy:

`measure_link_energy(...)` Uses `tcpdump` + known MAC/IP mappings and analyzes packet sizes and computes **energy cost** based on modeled constants:

```
link.energy.consumption.from.nodeA.to.nodeB.during.2=4021.45.micro-watts
```

These tests are run between every pair of nodes using dedicated host-network pods (usually 1 per node). Each result is written as a simple key-value pair as shown in Figure 37, `network_metrics.txt`.

```
netperf.p90.latency.milliseconds.origin.nodeA.destination.nodeB=12.3
iPerf.bw.Gbits.Sec.origin.nodeA.destination.nodeB=5.3
```

Figure 37: example of output for the probes generated by netma-nsm-mon.

The `network_metrics.txt` file are then uploaded as a K8s ConfigMap on each node, via the method `create_or_update_configmap(configmap_name, namespace, file_path)`.

Access to node and interface statistics:

`asyncio.run(main())` is used to access the local node and interface kernel statistic. The runtime workflow is as follows:

- Identify local node and interface.
- Run:

- (Async) link energy measurement (tcpdump)
- (Optionally) link failure
- Run latency, bandwidth, and packet loss tests.
- Measure node degree.
- Write results to file `network_metrics.txt`
- Upload metrics to Kubernetes ConfigMap.

3.3.2.2.1.3 Code Structure

The main source code files of [netma-nsm-mon](#) are summarized in Table 14.

Table 14: Description of the main netma-nsm-mon source code files.

Dir	Sub-dir-file	Function
	Deploy.sh	Script to support the deployment in a kind environment (standalone usage of netma-nsm-mon)
	Kind-config.yaml	
k8s-netperf	Netperf-netperf-2.7.0	Netperf files, v2.7.0 cleanup and running
	Dockerfile	Defines how the k8s-netperf container is built Install Netperf, iPerf, dependencies, etc. Prepares the runtime environment for network benchmarking
	k8s-netperf.yaml	Defines Kubernetes objects: DaemonSet (host-networking), Pods for testing across nodes and CNIs. Contains ConfigMap references, security context, scheduling constraints, etc.
	run.sh	Automates Netperf/iPerf; orchestrates the probing; parses and reports metrics
Monitoring		
	Dockerfile	Defines a container image for running the network_probe.py script. It is designed to run inside Kubernetes and includes both the Python runtime and kubectl CLI to interact with the cluster.
	cronjob.yaml	Defines a Kubernetes CronJob responsible for periodically running a network probing automation container (network_probe.py). Default is set for 8 minutes; container is netperf-automation:2.0
	netperf.py	Basis for the bandwidth and latency tests, deployed and used in network_probe.py.
	netperfMetrics.txt	Output of the netma-nsm-mon pods, to be used to upload the node ConfigMaps.
	network_probe.py	Main script providing the overall setup and execution of the netma-nsm-mon pods.
	serviceaccount.yaml	Provision the necessary Kubernetes RBAC (Roles & RoleBindings) so the automation component can read cluster metrics, watch CRDs, and access pods/nodes.
	test-automation.yaml	Describes a Pod, Job, or Deployment which orchestrates test workflows. This will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trigger probes (e.g. via netperf ICMP or TCP). • Collect results from NetworkState CRs generated by netma-nsm-mon. • Publish output, to be provided to nemesys

3.3.2.2.1.4 Selected Technologies

The current version of netma-nsm-mon has considered the following technologies:

- **K8s netperf**¹⁸. K8s Netperf is a benchmarking tool designed to measure various aspects of networking performance, focusing on bulk data transfer and request/response performance using TCP or UDP with the Berkeley Sockets interface. It supports tests over IPv4 and IPv6, and can be used on multiple platforms, including Unix, Linux, and Windows. It provides an effortless way to test network performance between pods using various metrics. To deploy, apply the provided YAML file which sets up daemon sets and pods to measure host-to-host, pod-to-pod (intra- and inter-node), and pod-to-service (ClusterIP) performance. It is currently used for network latency testing based on the TCP protocol.
- **iPerf3**. In the current netma-nsm-mon version it is used for bandwidth and packet loss testing based on the UDP protocol.
- **ICMP Ping**. It is currently used for connectivity testing to monitor node degree and link failure states.
- **TCPdump**. TCPdump is a powerful command-line packet analyzer used for network troubleshooting and security auditing. It captures and displays the contents of network packets transmitted over a network in real-time, allowing users to diagnose network issues and understand the data being transferred. TCPdump supports filtering criteria to capture specific types of traffic, making it a versatile tool for network administrators and security professionals. It can analyse protocols such as TCP, UDP, and ICMP, providing detailed insights into network activity. Used for packet capture and analysis to calculate link energy.
- **Python asyncio**. Python's asyncio for asynchronous operations, ensuring simultaneous and orderly recording of multiple network parameters.

3.3.2.2.1.5 Pre-requisites

- An active cluster with at least two worker nodes.

3.3.2.2.1.6 Installation Guide

The overall set up of netma-nsm-mon can be found in its [readme](#).

3.3.2.2.1.7 Inputs and Outputs

- Input to netma-nsm-mon are the networking underlay metrics being monitored, provided in Annex I.
- Output are the generated networking metrics (ConfigMap).

¹⁸ <https://github.com/vtrocelab/netperf-2.7.0/tree/master>

3.3.2.2.2 NetMA-nsm-npp

3.3.2.2.2.1 Code Structure

The main source code files of netma-nsm-npp are summarized in *Table 15*.

Table 15: Description of the main netma-nsm-npp source code files.

File	Function
Dockerfile	Creates a Docker image for the probe.
daemonset.yaml	Configuration file for deploying probing mechanisms in the different nodes of a cluster. One probe is deployed for each node. If additional nodes are created on-demand, new probes will be created.
data_communication.py	Source file to handle different configuration options to expose the metrics gathered for the probe.
network_probe.py	Main source file of the probe, which contains the logic of the measurements, and the execution of the communication and exposure of the metrics.

Pre-requisites

There are three types of dependencies to be handled to deploy this component:

- Hardware dependencies: There are no specific hardware requirements beyond those already defined for the installation of the CODECO Framework. The component has minimal computational footprint and can run on standard control-plane or worker nodes.
- Software dependencies: this code requires to have installed Kubernetes, Docker and Python 3.x in the machines to be deployed. Additionally, a server (such as Apache or Nginx) must be installed and configured in each node, as the system exposes an HTTP endpoint on port 80. This setup ensures that the NSM's exposed endpoints are reachable and compliant with standard HTTP communication patterns expected by the framework.
- Libraries dependencies: There are some needed libraries to be installed to make this code run (python [requirements.txt](#)).

3.3.2.3 Network Exposure: Nemesys-FC

Nemesys-FC serves as the North-Bound Interface (NBI) within the NetMA component, responsible for gathering and formatting topology and performance data from both overlay and underlay network probes. This processed information is then exposed to other CODECO components, such as the PDLC and ACM, enabling seamless integration and communication across the system. In multi-cluster environments, Nemesys instances must federate by exchanging topological data with their counterparts in each cluster, forming a Peer-to-Peer (P2P) mesh that ensures traceability and a unified network view.

To facilitate this exchange, an ALTO server is implemented, collecting inter-cluster performance metrics and generating cost maps using Dijkstra's algorithm. Each Nemesys periodically shares and receives metrics like latency, bandwidth, packet loss, and energy from its peers, allowing the creation of a comprehensive and consistent network map. The main metric, typically latency, guides optimization decisions, while multi-cost maps allow for a realistic representation of network paths by capturing multiple metrics simultaneously. This federated information is formatted according to the cluster's CRD and made available to the PDLC for topology and performance management.

3.3.2.3.1 Sequence Diagram and Operation Workflow

To support these functionalities, a modular architecture has been adopted for the sub-component. This design includes two dedicated modules responsible for reading information from the overlay and underlay network probes, respectively. Although the overlay and underlay networks coincide—since they reference the same node pairs—the design enables integration of both views into a unified multi-metric graph.

As illustrated in Figure 39, this graph structure incorporates multiple performance metrics, with overlay latency selected as the primary metric.

The main module of Nemesys, the ALTO core, will retain this view and create a second one to which it will add the information received from the federation API. It is also responsible for creating the maps that will be exchanged and subsequently formatting the CR.

The ALTO Core also communicates with the federation API to send it the local network map after each update. This map is the information exchanged between the federation members, forwarding just the local views and its updates. Figure 39 provides the workflow sequence diagram for Nemesys.

Figure 38: Nemesys-FC functional scheme.

Figure 39: Operation sequence, Nemesys-FC within a MC.

The relationship between internal ALTO Maps and the federated map is illustrated in Figure 40. The federated map is constructed from a collection of one to N ALTO Maps, where N represents the number of clusters in the federation. Each ALTO Map consists of three sub-maps, generated from a combination of a network map and an overlay graph.

These graphs are built using network data provided by the previously described modules. The data includes a set of nodes and links, along with their associated properties and capabilities, enabling the creation of detailed and context-aware ALTO representations across the federation.

Figure 40: Translation between ALTO maps and CODECO assets, nodes, clusters, links, etc.

3.3.2.3.2 Code Structure

The [Nemesys-FC code](#) is distributed and following the structure defined in the previous section. That is translated into 2 folders with the modules ([modulos](#)) and the APIs ([api](#)) and an additional document with the ALTO Core. Also, there are some additional documents that help as complements.

Table 16: Nemesys-FC main code files.

Dir	File	Function
Nemesys-FC	alto_core.py	Document that contains the main part of the ALTO code, including the main capabilities defined in the RFC7285, but it needs the ampliations to manage the different complements and the functionalities to be deployed, such as the multi-metrics and the multi-graph.
	alto_logger.py	It contains an adapted version for a logger class. To be used for the system to save registers of the events occurred during the code execution. The log files are stored in a folder call logs/, located in the same path as this file.
	config.yaml	Stores configuration settings for the application in YAML format. This file is used to manage environment-specific variables, credentials, or other customizable options outside the codebase.
	LICENSE	States the legal terms under which the project's code can be used, modified, and distributed. In this case is an Apache 2 License (open source).
	Dockerfile	Contains instructions for building a Docker image of the application. It specifies the base image, environment setup, dependencies, and commands to run the application in a containerized environment.
	requirements.txt	Lists Python package dependencies required to run the project.
kuberfiles	kuberfiles/01_netma-fed-topology-crd.yaml	CRD where the multi-cluster topology is defined. It is launched in a deployment phase, and the different instances (the CRs) are created during the running phase.
	kuberfiles/02_nemesys-fc-deployment.yaml	Manifest with the definition of the deployment of the code as well as the different permissions and handlers needed to run the code in a Kubernetes Pod.
modulos	modulos/alto_module.py	Abstracted class used to define how the topology_X.py classes should be structures and the functions to be used to exchange information with the alto_core.py.
	modulos/topology_kubernetes.py	Class that implements the integration between nemesys FC and the probes (overlay and underlay) basing their work in Kubernetes and Prometheus tools. It exports the obtained values to the alto_core.py file.
	modulos/topology_ietf.py	Class that implements a topology importer from a file that follows the IETF format. Used to do some tests to validate the topology integration and exchange.
api	api/web/alto_gui.py	Graphic unit to show in an interactive way how the network is connected and the optimal paths.

Dir	File	Function
	api/web/api_http.py	REST API that extends the services defined in the RFC7285. It uses http instead of https by commodity as the pass from HTTP to HTTPS is well defined and therefore it does not bring any new advantage to this PoC code.
	api/web/federation.py	Class that implements a topology importer from a file that follows the IETF format. Used to do some tests to validate the topology integration and exchange.
	api/crd_exporter.py	Document that transforms the ALTO maps into CR updates.
	api/prometheus_exporter.py	Document that transforms the ALTO maps into Prometheus updates

3.3.2.3.3 Dependencies and pre-conditions

There are four types of dependencies to be handled to deploy this component:

- Hardware dependencies: There are no hard dependency in terms of capacity or CPUs, being the same requirements as defined to install the CODECO Framework.
- Software dependencies: this code requires to have installed Kubernetes, Docker and Python3 in the machines to be deployed.
- Libraries dependencies: There are some needed libraries to be installed to make this code run. Currently, there is no hard dependency with the versions, but these are the ones that we are currently using (can be updated if needed):
 - dash==3.0
 - kubernetes==31.0
 - networkx==3.2
 - pandas==2.2
 - requests==2.25.1
- Configuration dependencies: Nemesys FC need to have CODECO framework installed, with at least one federated probe (overlay or underlay) available. This component would also need to count with the Kubernetes permissions requested in the `02_nemesys-fc-deployment.yaml` manifest.

As this component depends on having other CODECO components installed it would also inherit their dependencies as could be to have the CNI plugins updated, to have access to the sockets or to have a machine with at least 4 virtual cores. These dependencies can vary according with the framework installed therefore this is just a reminder to check also the related dependencies.

Other preconditions are the presence of network performance metrics and having reachability with the other clusters (and being able to identify the services in the inter-cluster management).

3.3.2.3.4 Installation guide

The installation of this [sub-component is automatized](#), being needed to deploy the dependencies and preconditions and then apply the following kuberfiles:

```
cd nemesys-fc/  
kubectl apply -f kuberfiles/01_netma-fed-topology-crd.yaml  
kubectl apply -f kuberfiles/02_nemesys-fc-deployment.yaml  
cd ..
```

3.3.2.3.5 Interfacing with other components

The Nemesys FC will receive information from other remote Nemesys FC and locally from the network federated probes and the overlay monitoring component.

3.3.3 Next Cycle features

For the following months we are continuing defining the interactions and development of the subcomponents, starting with the final definition for the probes and the network exposure. The next table adds a list of the adaptations to be added during the next cycle:

ID	Description
Nemesys-FC	Final adaptation of Nemesys FC code according to the final definition of the probes and the multicluster environment characteristics.
Nemesys-FC	Adding a multi-cost management for the Nemesys FC adaptation.
Secure connectivity	Secure Connectivity will extend its capabilities to support secure inter-cluster communication across CODECO workloads. The component is currently in its design phase, so some implementation details are defined but not yet disclosed. In the single-cluster release
NSM	Adaptation to multi-cluster environment of netma-nsm-mon; integration of passive probing (as alternative to active probing); definition of metric aggregation
Secure connectivity	Finalization of the implementation for multi-cluster design and support to SWM.

3.4 MDM-FC: Metadata Manager

3.4.1 Component Description

The CODECO MDM component collects, links, and enriches metadata related with the applications to be deployed across Edge-Cloud. This metadata assists in better characterizing the application deployment across Edge-Cloud. MDM is therefore a CODECO component that acts as a gateway between the data world (data workflow) and the Kubernetes infrastructure (compute).

MDM and its sub-components are illustrated in Figure 41, simplified using a single Hub cluster and two managed cluster, which may or may not belong to the same neighbourhood. Note that MDM is a distributed system, and its components may be deployed across multiple Kubernetes clusters if configured appropriately. MDM collects metadata from any “native system” that has information on the data, including data stores, catalogues, pipelines that copy and transform data, use-case specific functions that analyse the data, or any other relevant system. For this purpose, MDM relies on **connector interfaces** for each specific data type (I-

MDM-E-1). Connectors are deployed on each managed cluster with the API of the corresponding hub cluster where they report to. MDM offers an interface to PDLC (I-MDM-PDLC-1) on the hub cluster which all PDLC instances on the corresponding managed clusters use to gather information about those clusters.

Figure 41: MDM sub-components and APIs to other components

An MDM connector interfaces to a native data system or CRD and pushes metadata into a knowledge graph through the native (internal) MDM API. By adding new connectors or expanding the graph model, the system can be extended to collect any required metadata.

MDM is event-based, relying on Apache Kafka¹⁹. MDM relies on the Kafka event queue, a log of metadata events that occur for an Edge-Cloud setting managed with CODECO. Events describe changes that have happened and correspond to insert/update/delete of metadata entities and relationships.

MDM materializes (subsets of) the event queue in the knowledge graph to meet the needs of other CODECO components.

MDM is implemented by three components:

- **MDM API:** Implements the REST APIs that allow metadata to be pushed into the graph database and the graph to be queried.
- **Graph Database:** Stores the metadata graph.
- **Connectors:** They gather metadata and push it into the Graph Database using the MDM Controller APIs.

3.4.2 Sub-components' Specification and Implementation

3.4.2.1 Graph Database

The Graph Database ([MDM/Graphdb](#)) is the backend storage of the MDM component. The metadata events from all MDM connectors are consolidated here, making it possible for other components to extract insights from the distributed system from a single pane of glass. It is,

¹⁹ <https://kafka.apache.org/>

of course, possible to request information by directly querying the database using cypher, but other than during development or exploration of the metadata, the MDM component is designed to offer this functionality through the MDM API.

3.4.2.1.1 Code structure

The main source files of the MDM GraphDB are presented in Table 17.

Table 17: of the main MDM GraphDB source code files.

File	Function
deployment/neo4j-helm.yaml	Example values to deploy the Neo4j Helm chart
Schemas/eu.codecohe/**/*.json	JSON schemas for the entities and relationships in the Knowledge Graph

3.4.2.1.2 Selected Technologies

The graph database is implemented using Neo4j:

- **Neo4j 4.4.20** or higher.
- **Neo4j APOC²¹**: Awesome Procedures on Cypher (APOC) is an add-on library for Neo4j that provides hundreds of procedures and functions adding a lot of useful functionality.
- **Cypher Graph Query language²²**: Cypher is a declarative graph query language that allows for expressive and efficient data querying in a property graph. It is the query language for Neo4j and the language opencypher²³ is based on.
- **JSON Schema**: It is used to define the entities, their properties, and relationships among them in a language-independent manner. The schemas are available online²⁴.

3.4.2.1.3 Pre-requisites

Detailed pre-requisites for running Neo4j in K8s can be found from the vendor directly²⁵. CODECO relies on Neo4j's Community Edition. Commercial utilization of Neo4j's Enterprise Edition may require a license from the vendor. Please see <https://neo4j.com/licensing/> for details.

3.4.2.1.4 Installation Guide

To install the [Graph database](#) refer to the Helm chart provided by Neo4j. The following steps are detailed in the [online documentation in Git](#):

Set the following environment variables:

```
export MDM_NAMESPACE=mdm
export MDM_CONTEXT=docker-desktop
```

Add Neo4j's Helm chart to the Helm repositories:

```
helm repo add neo4j https://helm.neo4j.com/neo4j
```

Update the yaml configuration file for your K8s environment (online version neo4j-helm.yaml)

²⁰ <https://neo4j.com/>

²¹ <https://neo4j.com/labs/apoc/>

²² <https://neo4j.com/developer/cypher>

²³ <http://opencypher.org>

²⁴ https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/metadata-manager-mdm/graphdb/-/tree/main/schemas/eu.codecohe?ref_type=heads

²⁵ <https://neo4j.com/docs/operations-manual/current/K8s/quickstart-standalone/Pre-requisites/>

- set the neo4j.password for the database user neo4j
- define the volumes StorageClass if required.
- adjust other parameters such as CPU and memory usage as required.

Install the Helm chart:

```
helm --kube-context=$MDM_CONTEXT install mdm-neo4j -n $MDM_NAMESPACE
neo4j/neo4j-standalone -f ./deployment/neo4j-helm.yamlf
```

3.4.2.1.5 Inputs & Outputs

The Graph database is fed metadata events from Kafka²⁶ by the mdm-controller subcomponent and offers a Cypher API to the mdm-api subcomponent. These interfaces are internal to MDM and declared here only for completeness.

3.4.2.2 MDM Controller (APIs)

The MDM controller provides the APIs for other CODECO components to query the metadata graph and for MDM connectors to provide metadata. The MDM Controller is thus a required sub-component for all scenarios where metadata analysis is required for the CODECO use-case. A selected set of MDM connectors depending on the use-case will provide metadata that allows through this subcomponent, allowing other CODECO components like PDLC to get summarize information about the systems and data in the form of parameters to models that provide the best scheduling for a given workload.

3.4.2.2.1 Code Structure

Table 18 and Table 19 provide a summary of the main MDM Controller source code files.

Table 18: Description of the main MDM Controller source code files.

File	Function
deployment/*.yaml	Example values to deploy the Kafka, Zookeeper and Neo4j Helm charts
controller/src/helm	Helm chart for the MDM controller
controller/src/python/*.py	Python code for the MDM controller
controller/src/python/ctrl.py	Main program for the MDM controller
controller/Dockerfile	Dockerfile to produce the MDM controller image
controller/requirements.txt	Python dependencies of the MDM controller

Table 19: Description of the main MDM API source code files.

File	Function
mdm-api/src/helm	Helm chart for the MDM API
mdm-api/src/python/*.py	Python code for the MDM API
mdm-api/src/python/app.py	Main program for the MDM API
mdm-api/Dockerfile	Dockerfile to produce the MDM API image
mdm-api/requirements.txt	Python dependencies of the MDM API

²⁶ <https://kafka.apache.org/>

3.4.2.2.2 Selected Technologies

The MDM metadata collection has materialized in data systems that make it convenient to manage and exploit the metadata. The key technologies used in the current MDM Controller implementation include:

- **Apache Kafka:** Distributed event store and stream processing.
- **Apache ZooKeeper**²⁷, for the overall Kafka management and coordination (e.g., configuration information, naming, providing distributed synchronization).
- **Python 3.9** or higher for the implementation of the APIs and the interaction with Kafka and the Graph database.
- **OpenAPI 3.0** as the standard for the REST API for both input and output.
- **Swagger** as the mechanism to programmatically produce the REST API implementation designs and their documentation.

3.4.2.2.3 Pre-requisites

No specific hardware requirements are needed to run the MDM Controller.

3.4.2.2.4 Installation Guide

The Graph database needs to be installed first. After that, the order of installation of the MDM Controller sub-components is important:

- **mdm-zookeeper:** This is the MDM zookeeper sub-component, installed using Helm from the Bitnami²⁸ chart repository. This is required by the mdm-kafka sub-component.
- **mdm-kafka:** This is the MDM Kafka sub-component, installed using Helm from the Bitnami chart repository. This is required by the mdm-ctrl sub-component.
- **mdm-controller:** The MDM API Controller sub-component. Receives the metadata events from Kafka and pushes them into the Graph database.
- **mdm-api:** Implements the MDM REST API to the Graph database and connector publication API.

Detailed installation information is provided in the [MDM API GitLab repository](#).

When developing the MDM subcomponents, the docker build and push description provided in the online documentation require providing the docker registry used to store the images. This, as well as the tag, may change when new versions are developed. Assuming that the mdm-api repository has been cloned locally and is the current directory, the following steps are the basis to install MDM:

Install the MDM controller: If you need to change the tag of the docker image, or any other value, provide it in your own YAML file.

```
cd mdm-controller
helm --kube-context=$MDM_CONTEXT -n $MDM_NAMESPACE install mdm-controller ./mdm-controller/src/helm [-f my_values.yaml]
```

Install the MDM API: If you need to change the tag of the docker image, or any other [value](#), provide it in your own YAML file.

²⁷ <https://zookeeper.apache.org/>

²⁸ <https://github.com/bitnami/charts/tree/main/bitnami>

```
cd mdm-api
helm --kube-context=$MDM_CONTEXT -n $MDM_NAMESPACE install mdm-api
./mdm-api/src/helm [-f my_values.yaml]
```

The Helm charts for the installation of the mdm-controller and mdm-api sub-components may become available in the future from an online Helm repository.

3.4.2.2.5 Inputs & Outputs

Events consist of an event envelope and a payload. While the envelope structure is given by MDM, the payload types are application specific. Payloads are either entities or relationships with minimal restrictions on their structure, i.e., they need to contain a type and unique identifier(s). Entities and relationships are defined in JSON schema for CODECO at [MDM/graphdb/schemas/eu.codecohe](https://mdm.graphdb/schemas/eu.codecohe).

The MDM API is based on OpenAPI REST (OAS REST API) and integrates the following endpoint groups:

- **Publish** which is the endpoint for connectors writing to the MDM.
- **Events** which are the endpoint to get events from MDM.
- **Graph** gets information by querying the data projection. Initially this would allow for Cypher queries to be performed on the knowledge graph. If because of the experience gained with partners the set of queries required for the CODECO operation can be defined in a closed set, they can be incorporated to this API at a later stage.
- **MDM** is the system information endpoint for getting status and resets or other system relevance functions.
- **PDLC** is the endpoint where the PDLC component can query the graph for specific metrics related to the pods in the CODECO application.
- **STORAGE** endpoint gets you information about storage classes supported by cluster and storage classes used by Pod Namespace and cluster.

All endpoints are protected and authorized usage enabled. The complete description is in swagger online documentation in MDM at the CODECO Eclipse GitLab (mdm-api/src/python/templates/swagger.yaml). Furthermore, note that the following API groups are not implemented, and responses will always be HTTP status 200 (OK): Groups, Lookup, Registration, Schemas and Versions.

Inputs:

POST /publish/event

Accept in the body a JSON structured event. The event payload object could be an entity or relationship structure.

Outputs:

GET /graph/entity/type

Get a JSON array of existing entity types in the metadata graph.

POST /graph/entity/type/{entitytype}

Get a list of entities in the metadata graph depending on the POST request JSON filter definition.

GET /graph/entity/attributes/{entitytype}

Get a JSON array of all existing attributes in the metadata graph for a given entity type.

GET /graph/path/{edf_id}

Get the graph structure as a JSON object for an entity identified by edf_id. As optional query parameter one can define the number of hops (depth) around the entity that will be included in the resulting graph.

POST /graph/cypher

The POST request body accepts a plain text base CYPHER query. The response will be the default JSON structure produced by the Graph database (Neo4j).

For **example**:

Request-body:

```
MATCH (a:compute)-[r]-(b) WHERE b.user_id = "Brandy.Neal@example.com" RETURN a as compute LIMIT 1
```

Response:

```
{
  "identity": 4,
  "labels": [
    "compute",
    "entity",
    "visible"
  ],
  "properties": {
    "_domain": "default",
    "identifier": "AFCF2B98D7",
    "serialNumber": "none",
    "city": "Zurich",
    "ritssDataClassification": "RII unclassified (Non-Confidential)",
    "_status": [],
    "networkClassification": "General Internal Enterprise Network",
    "country_code": "CH",
    "update_time": "2023-04-24T07:54:41.596286000Z",
    "entity_type": "compute",
    "dataClassification": [
      "Public"
    ],
    "name": "srv-22",
    "connector_id": "d79df9ea-efac-360c-b7cc-2cf0de386100",
    "exportClassification": "blue",
    "edf_id": "523e2537-b717-34e0-b303-638b159d7fcb",
    "_id": "523e2537-b717-34e0-b303-638b159d7fcb"
  },
  "elementId": "1"
}
```

GET /mdm

Get the running version of the mdm-api sub-component.

GET /mdm/state

Get the state of the different sub-components (neo4j/kafka/ctrl/etc)

DELETE /mdm/clean

Delete all metadata in the MDM component. Use with caution, only meant for development and testing purposes.

GET /events/sse

Server-Sent Events API-based filtered events from the serialized graph queue in Kafka. This is meant for components that need to be notified of specific metadata events as they happen, as opposed to gathering the current state from querying the metadata graph at time intervals.

GET /pdlc

This endpoint gets the metrics associated with the pods required by PDLC following a CRD format. The parameters are as follows:

cluster: The name of the cluster where the pod is running.

namespace: The namespace where the pod is running

pod: The name of the pod

rnd: (optional) If this is set to "true," the API provides random values for all metrics.

The result is provided in JSON as a K8s CR.

The output properties are:

- *pod_name*: The name of the pod, as provided as input.
- *freshness*: How fresh the data processed by pod is (see Prometheus connector below)
- *compliance*: Level of compliance of the pod given where it is running (see Compliance connector below)
- *portability*: A metric of how robust the execution of the pod is where it is running (see K8s connector below).

GET /storage/classes

This endpoint gets supported storage classes. The parameter as follows:

cluster: The name of the cluster where the pod is running.

The result is provided in JSON array of strings as storageclasses name.

GET /storage/pvc

This endpoint gets used storageclasses by pod. The parameter as follows:

cluster: The name of the cluster where the pod is running.

namespace: The namespace where the pod is running

pod: The name of the pod

The result is provided in JSON array with *pvc_name* and *storage_class_name*.

e.g.: [{"pvc_name": "data-mdm-neo4j-0", "storage_class_name": "gp2"}]

3.4.2.2.6 UML Diagram

The momentary interaction between the CODECO components and MDM and among the MDM subcomponents is depicted in Figure 42.

Figure 42: Interaction between MDM subcomponents.

Note that the connectors interact with the K8s API and the Prometheus API to obtain metadata, and the PDLC component uses the MDM API to obtain the metrics obtained from that metadata. As explained in Figure 5, also note that this interaction may happen inside a Kubernetes cluster or across clusters.

3.4.2.3 Connectors

Connectors send metadata to MDM in the form of events. Events are structured JSON documents. An event contains the following elements:

- The event type, either “insert” or “delete.”
- An identifier that uniquely identifies the connector that issued the event.
- A timestamp.
- The payload, i.e., the metadata.

Metadata is sent as entities and relationships. MDM imposes a basic structure on both entities and relationships to ensure that metadata can be stored as a graph. Entities must have a globally unique identifier and a type. It is the task of the connector to assign these. In addition, entities contain arbitrary numbers of attributes. The mandatory elements of a relationship are source and target entity identifier as well as a type. Relationships do not carry attributes.

MDM does not define or enforce a static data model. Instead, the graph data model is defined by the structure of the entities and relationships that are inserted into MDM.

Entities and relationships are defined in JSON schema for CODECO at [MDM/graphdb/schemas/eu.codecohe](https://mdm.graphdb.schemas.eu.codecohe).

3.4.2.3.1 Selected Technologies

Connectors may be implemented in any programming language, if they make metadata available following the data model of the application framework (in this case CODECO’s) and use the MDM Controller API conventions to make it available to the Graph database.

In the context of CODECO, the following technologies are considered:

- **Python 3.9 or higher** is the preferred programming language, as it will allow the connector developer to leverage the open-source connector SDK.
- **IBM Pathfinder SDK:** Available here²⁹, it provides YAML-based configuration, and the base communication means for the connector to send metadata events to the MDM API.

3.4.2.3.2 Pre-requisites

MDM Connectors do not have any hardware requirements. The MDM Controller component needs to be installed first so that connectors can send the metadata events.

3.4.2.3.3 Installation Guide

MDM Connectors are installed using Helm charts. The parameters required depend on the source of metadata to be inspected by the connector and thus cannot be listed extensively.

At a minimum, the following parameters need to be provided:

pathfinder.url: The URL of the MDM API. This may be a single string, or an array containing multiple MDM instances to report to.

pathfinder.K8sUrl: The Kube API of the K8s cluster where the connector runs.

For a complete list of parameters please refer to [pathfinder-python-sdk/ibm_pathfinder_sdk/pathfinderconfig.py](#).

3.4.2.3.4 Inputs & Outputs

MDM Connectors get input from the source of metadata inspected. The output is always provided in the form of metadata events sent to the MDM API using the **/publish/event** POST request.

For CODECO, helper classes are provided for Python connectors in [connectors/metadata-model/src/main/python/](#). This way, connector developers can use the MDM CODECO metadata model directly by instantiating these Python classes for entities and relationships.

3.4.2.4 CODECO Default Connectors

Users of the CODECO framework can install any connectors they develop or use the MDM APIs to provide metadata into the system to compute metrics or other information for their own purposes. Out of the box, CODECO provides three connectors that provide the metadata for certain metrics that are used by the scheduling mechanism in PDLC to decide on the placement of the CODECO application. These connectors are described in the following sections.

3.4.2.4.1 K8s connector

Information about the K8s environment managed by CODECO is essential to provide meaningful decisions as to how to schedule CODECO applications. The K8s connector gets all entities in a K8s cluster and includes them in the MDM metadata graph, together with the relationships among them.

The K8s connector collects among other data the number of restarts of a pod, which is used as a proxy for the portability metric of that pod running in that cluster and namespace.

²⁹ <https://pypi.org/project/ibm-pathfinder-sdk>

3.4.2.4.1.1 Code Structure

Table 20 provides a summary of the main MDM K8s connector source code files.

Table 20: Main MDM K8s connector source code files.

File	Function
connectors/k8s/src/main/helm	Helm chart for the MDM K8sconnector
connectors/k8s/src/main/python/*.py	Python code for the MDM K8sconnector
connectors/k8s/src/main/python/connector.py	Main program for the MDM K8sconnector
connectors/k8s/src/main/docker/Dockerfile	Dockerfile to produce the MDM K8sconnector
connectors/k8s/src/main/python/requirements.txt	Python dependencies of the MDM K8sconnector

3.4.2.4.1.2 Selected Technologies

The K8s connector is developed based on:

- **Python 3.9 or higher:** Python is the preferred programming language, as it will allow the connector developer to leverage the open-source connector SDK.
- **IBM Pathfinder SDK:** Available online³⁰, it provides YAML-based configuration, and the base communication means for the connector to send metadata events to MDM's API.
- **K8s watcher API:** This allows the K8s connector to receive as events all the entities created in the K8s cluster, including but not limited to pods, CRDs, deployments, etc.
- The K8s connector source code is available at [MDM/connectors/connectors/k8s/src/main](#).

3.4.2.4.1.3 Pre-requisites

The CODECO MDM K8s connector needs to run with enough privilege to get all events in a K8s cluster.

3.4.2.4.1.4 Installation Guide

The CODECO MDM K8s connector is installed using a Helm chart provided in the same repository where the code is available. Other than the default parameters required for all connectors, the following are required:

- **crawler.K8s.api_url:** The URL of the K8s API for the cluster being monitored.
- **crawler.K8s.sa_token:** If the connector is not running under a sufficiently privileged service account, the token with sufficient permissions to watch the K8s API must be provided in this parameter.

3.4.2.4.1.5 Inputs & Outputs

Using as input the events obtained by watching the K8s API, the K8s connector provides metadata about all K8s entities in the MDM graph following the metadata model described above.

³⁰ <https://pypi.org/project/ibm-pathfinder-sdk>

3.4.2.4.2 Compliance connector

The level of compliance of a K8s environment managed by CODECO is another metric required to schedule CODECO applications. The Compliance connector uses Kubescape³² to obtain a metric of compliance of the cluster and adds that information to the MDM metadata graph.

3.4.2.4.2.1 Code structure

Table 21 provides a summary of the main MDM Compliance connector source code files.

Table 21: Description of the main MDM Compliance connector source code files.

File	Function
connectors/kubescape/src/main/helm	Helm chart for the MDM compliance connector
connectors/kubescape/src/main/python/*.py	Python code for the MDM compliance connector
connectors/kubescape/src/main/python/connector.py	Main program for the MDM compliance connector
connectors/kubescape/src/main/docker/Dockerfile	Dockerfile to produce the MDM compliance connector
connectors/kubescape/src/main/python/requirements.txt	Python dependencies of the MDM compliance connector

3.4.2.4.2.2 Selected Technologies

The K8s connector is developed based on:

- **Python 3.9 or higher** is the preferred programming language, as it will allow the connector developer to leverage the open-source connector SDK.
- **IBM Pathfinder SDK:** Available online³¹, it provides YAML-based configuration, and the base communication means for the connector to send metadata events to MDM's API.
- **Kubescape:** Kubescape is an open-source technology that performs several tests (controls) following compliance rules from well-known security and compliance frameworks. By default, the MITRE and NSA frameworks are enabled³², which perform controls on configuration of worker nodes, K8s API, etc., and provide a level of coverage as a percentage.

3.4.2.4.2.3 Pre-requisites

The CODECO MDM K8s connector needs to run with enough privilege to access configuration information through the K8s API.

3.4.2.4.2.4 Installation Guide

The CODECO MDM Compliance connector is installed using a Helm chart provided in the same repository where the code is available. Other than the default parameters required for all connectors, the following are required:

- **crawler.K8s.api_url:** The URL of the K8s API for the cluster being monitored.

31 <https://pypi.org/project/ibm-pathfinder-sdk>

32 <https://kubescape.io/docs/frameworks-and-controls/frameworks/>

- **crawler.K8s.sa_token**: If the connector is not running under a sufficiently privileged service account, the token with sufficient permissions to obtain configuration information through the K8s API must be provided in this parameter.

3.4.2.4.2.5 Inputs & Outputs

Using as input the information available through the K8s API, the Compliance connector uses the Kubescape tool to provide a metric for the level of compliance of a K8s cluster and the worker nodes, which is attached to the corresponding MDM metadata graph entities.

3.4.2.4.3 Prometheus connector

CODECO components and use-cases may use Prometheus to make certain metrics available. The MDM Prometheus connector obtains configured metrics from Prometheus to enrich entities in the metadata graph with those values. In particular, the “freshness” metric is captured such that if a CODECO application is to be scheduled according to that metric, making it available in CODECO’s Prometheus will make it possible for PDLC to schedule the application to optimize the “freshness” of the data being processed.

3.4.2.4.3.1 Code Structure

Table 22 provides a summary of the main MDM Compliance connector source code files.

Table 22: Description of the main MDM K8s connector source code files.

File	Function
connectors/prometheus/src/main/helm	Helm chart for the MDM prometheus connector
connectors/prometheus/src/main/python/*.py	Python code for the MDM prometheus connector
connectors/prometheus/src/main/python/connector.py	Main program for the MDM prometheus connector
connectors/prometheus/src/main/docker/Dockerfile	Dockerfile to produce the MDM prometheus connector
connectors/prometheus/src/main/python/requirements.txt	Python dependencies of the MDM prometheus connector

3.4.2.4.3.2 Selected Technologies

The K8s connector is developed based on:

- **Python 3.9 or higher** is the preferred programming language, as it will allow the connector developer to leverage the open-source connector SDK.
- **IBM Pathfinder SDK³³** provides YAML-based configuration and the base communication means for the connector to send metadata events to the MDM API.
- **Prometheus**: Prometheus is an open-source technology³⁴ that records metrics in a time series database built using a pull model, where an endpoint is made available for applications and Prometheus queries periodically the endpoint to obtain the metrics.

3.4.2.4.3.3 Pre-requisites

³³ <https://pypi.org/project/ibm-pathfinder-sdk/>

³⁴ <https://prometheus.io>

The CODECO MDM K8s connector needs the required credentials to access the Prometheus query endpoint. The Prometheus service needs to be integrated with K8s so that the association between the metric and the pod producing it can be obtained and reflected in the Knowledge Graph.

3.4.2.4.3.4 Installation Guide

The CODECO MDM Compliance connector is installed using a Helm chart provided in the same repository where the code is available. Other than the default parameters required for all connectors, the following are required:

- **crawler.k8s.api_url**: The URL of the K8s API for the cluster being monitored.
- **crawler.prometheus.server.url**: The hostname of the Prometheus query API
- **crawler.prometheus.server.port**: The port of the Prometheus query API
- **crawler.prometheus.metric**: The name of the metric to capture (default is *CODECO_freshness*)
- **crawler.prometheus.entity**: The name of the entity in the metadata graph to attach the metric to.

3.4.2.4.3.5 Inputs & Outputs

Using as input the values obtained through the Prometheus query API; an arbitrary metric can be attached to arbitrary entities in the MDM metadata graph.

3.4.3 Next Cycle Features

MDM is a distributed system with components that may be deployed across multiple Kubernetes clusters. As such, the components need minimal adaptation for a federated cluster deployment. There is, however, work to do on the orchestration of the components themselves, which must be carefully configured for all to work together.

Next cycle features are provided in Table 23.

Table 23: MDM Next cycle features.

Sub-component	Feature enhancements
Connectors	A connector deployed on a managed cluster may have to report to more than one hub cluster MDM API, as the managed cluster may belong to multiple neighbourhoods that get mapped to different instances of MDM-FC. A flexible, backwards compatible deployment mechanism is to be implemented.
MDM Deployment	The configuration and deployment of all components of MDM need to be orchestrated with information from OCM, especially the exposed APIs from Hub clusters for connectors and PDLC to use.
Neighbourhood mapping mechanism	Given a collection of clusters where a multi-hub deployment of CODECO is to take place, a mechanism to assign neighbourhoods to hub clusters needs to be implemented so that MDM can scale to arbitrary cluster collection sizes.

3.5 SWM-FC: Scheduling and Workload Migration

This section extends the description of SWM. In the following “SWM” refers to SWM for the single-cluster case and “SWM-FC” to SWM for the multi-cluster case. The section contains the aspects that are *different* between SWM and SWM-FC, i.e., most of the definitions, terms, and components of SWM apply to SWM-FC as well. Their description is not repeated here for brevity’s sake (see D10 for further information [1]).

3.5.1 Component description

SWM-FC has the same task as SWM: place workloads on nodes and establish network connections between those workloads. The difference is that SWM-FC may now place workloads in one or more clusters as it sees fit. SWM-FC assumes that an application’s workloads may be placed in different clusters and that applications in a group may be put into different clusters.

Figure 43: An application with workloads in two clusters.

SWM-FC is concerned only with workloads and channels. It creates pods for workloads and establishes paths in suitable networks for the specified channels (with respect to a channels requirement). An application in Kubernetes may refer to a lot more objects (e.g., ConfigMaps, Secrets, Volumes). These objects are not part of SWM-FC’s application model. SWM-FC assumes that all these “secondary” objects are appropriately configured before an application is started or created on the fly based on the assignment plan.

SWM-FC supports placing a group of applications in a set of clusters considering the requirements specified (CPU, memory, latency, bandwidth...). The initial placement can now involve multiple clusters. An application’s workloads are not required to be all in the same cluster. Workload migration may be done between clusters. SWM-FC maintains the application’s requirements also in the multi-cluster case, i.e., a migration is done only, if SWM-FC finds a suitable placement.

Workload migration with SWM-FC is like the single-cluster case. SWM-FC migrates the workloads (i.e., the pods) and the corresponding network connections, but it does *not* take care of the state within a pod. This is consistent with how Kubernetes handles pods.

3.5.1.1 SWM-FC Application Model

A user or client like ACM-FC interacts with SWM-FC by specifying the desired state in custom resources (CRs). The custom resource definitions (CRDs) for SWM-FC are an extended version of those of SWM. There is only one new resource type with information about a cluster.

It includes some aggregated data that SWM-FC may use to distribute applications and workloads on a cluster level and other administrative information. A cluster has no associated FSM.

Clusters that SWM-FC should use for scheduling must be connected. SWM-FC uses CRs of type NetworkTopology for the links between clusters. There may be one network per service class connecting clusters (i.e., one best-effort network and one assured network). If clusters A and B are not connected by a network for instance of service class “assured”, it is not possible to set up an assured channel between a workload in cluster A and a workload in cluster B.

The network between clusters has a restriction that networks within a cluster do not have: The network does not support paths with more than one link. This means that two clusters are connected only if there is direct link between them. If clusters A, B, and C are connected by links $A \leftrightarrow B$ and $A \leftrightarrow C$, no channel can be built between clusters B and C. The network path consisting of the links $A \leftrightarrow B$ and $A \leftrightarrow C$ is *not* used for traffic between B and C.

Most new fields of SWM-FC’s resources should be used with care to give SWM-FC maximum flexibility to place workloads. An application for instance has a field `cluster` that fixes an application to a particular cluster. SWM-FC respects this setting but may not be able to come up with a placement in this case.

If a user has a set of resources for some applications for a single cluster, it sufficient to add a list of target clusters to an application group to indicate that SWM-FC should place the applications in those clusters, i.e., the applications should run in a multi-cluster environment.

3.5.1.2 SWM-FC Instances

SWM-FC aligns with the CODECO view of cluster management that is the one from OCM. There are two kinds of clusters: hub clusters and managed clusters. A hub cluster is used for managing a set of clusters. Only the managed clusters are used to run workloads of a CODECO application. The hub cluster controls its set of clusters (e.g., install software).

SWM-FC runs in each cluster, i.e., one instance is running in the Hub cluster, and one instance is running in each managed cluster. Each instance can act as an SWM instance for its cluster. SWM-FC can only access detailed information about a cluster when it is running within that cluster, i.e., a cluster’s internal structure is not visible outside the cluster. This is due to privacy and scaling reasons.

While the installed software is identical, the roles of the two instances in SWM-FC are different. Only the instance in the hub cluster handles requests to place an application group in a set of clusters. The instances in the managed clusters forward any multi-cluster request to the hub cluster and place workloads within their cluster. The instance in the hub cluster orchestrates the actions of the instances in the managed clusters when placing a group in a set of clusters.

3.5.1.3 Federated Scheduling with SWM-FC

SWM-FC places a new group in a set of clusters in three steps. If any of the steps fails, no placement is found, and SWM-FC tries again later. Only the final step actually allocates cluster resources. The target set of clusters may not be changed once a group has started placing workloads in clusters. The set of target clusters is called a neighbourhood.

1. Order the neighbourhood’s clusters.
2. Assign workloads within the target clusters, cluster by cluster.

3. Implement the place in the target clusters.

SWM-FC places workloads within clusters considering the other clusters of a neighbourhood (a so-called *L2 problem*). An L2 problem for SWM-FC is like a problem that SWM handles but it needs to take workloads in other clusters into account. In an L2 problem a cluster is represented by a node with some aggregate information about the corresponding cluster.

Figure 44: Event-sequence diagram for a placement of an application.

Step 1 puts a neighbourhood's clusters in a suitable order for placing the workloads. The ordered sequence of clusters S may not include all clusters in a neighbourhood as some may not be applicable for the current placement (e.g., a cluster lacks a required label). This step does *not* assign any workloads to clusters based on the aggregated information about the clusters.

The order for clusters in S depends on the number of recommendations for workloads of a cluster and on the latency of inter-cluster links. SWM-FC uses clusters with node recommendations before clusters without recommendations and fast inter-cluster links before slow ones.

Step 2 assigns workloads to nodes in a managed cluster, i.e., it solves an L2 problem. The first cluster assigns greedily all workloads it can support considering any node recommendations and assigns all other workloads tentatively to other managed clusters based on aggregate information.

The SWM-FC instance running in a managed cluster sends its solution back to SWM-FC running in the hub cluster. This instance modifies the placement problem to include the solution from the managed cluster and asks the next managed cluster to solve the enhanced problem. If all workloads are assigned, the placement is complete and can be executed (i.e., step 3 gets executed).

It is not a problem if SWM-FC cannot place a single workload in a managed cluster. The set of workloads does not shrink, but the number of clusters to visit is smaller. If all clusters were visited and there are still some workloads to place, this is a failure unless SWM-FC goes for increased robustness. This is the default but can be configured when SWM is deployed.

Assigning channels between workloads running in the same cluster is easy. SWM-FC can do this in the same way as SWM. Channels connecting workloads in different clusters are harder. Consider a channel connecting workloads in cluster A and B. As information about cluster B is not available when solving the L2 problem for cluster A, SWM-FC can only check whether the part of the channel in the cluster A has no problems. The final check for a channel's bandwidth and latency is done when SWM-FC places the second workload in cluster B.

Figure 45: A channel connecting workloads in two clusters has three parts as far as the latency is concerned.

For this check, cluster B must know the channel's latency in cluster A. The total latency of the channels is the latency in cluster A, the latency of the link connecting clusters A and B, and the latency in cluster B. SWM-FC can guarantee that the channels' requirements are met. Note that this works even if cluster B is changed to cluster C during the scheduling process for some reason. The latency in cluster A is added to the specification of the placement.

SWM-FC tries to minimize the latency in a channel's first cluster (i.e., cluster A in this case). This increases the flexibility at the other end. Increased flexibility is important especially if a workload must be moved to another cluster (e.g., cluster C) which might have a different inter- and inner-cluster latency.

If SWM-FC can solve all L2 problems, it is guaranteed that the final solution satisfies the requirements of all workloads, channels within clusters, and channels between clusters.

To increase robustness, SWM-FC reconsiders the ordered set of clusters S when it could not assign all workloads. For all workloads that could not be assigned, SWM-FC relaxes the placement restrictions and asks all clusters in S in the same order to assign the remaining workloads. If this second round does not place all workloads, the placement fails.

Executing a second round of placement requests in S is not as expensive as it seems at the first glance. The information for all problems is already available and the problem to solve is smaller. The instances in the managed cluster use the same infrastructure information as for the first round.

When all L2 problems are solved, the placement found must be implemented in the different clusters. While solving L2 problems, cluster resources are *not* reserved. The final step to set up communication channels in the corresponding networks and create pods for workloads. If one of the implementation steps fails, all allocations (i.e., in all managed clusters) are reverted and the placement fails.

For channels connecting workloads in two clusters, the reservation for the part between clusters is managed by the cluster with the source workload.

SWM-FC handles workload migration in a similar way. PDLC triggers migration by adding or modifying node recommendations to workloads in an application's CR. SWM-FC executes the same three steps, but the final step is a bit more complex. SWM-FC reserves resources for any migrated workload *before* the old instance is stopped. This requires more resources but allows to switch from old to new instances swiftly. It also avoids problems with a service's availability when an old instance is released early but a new instance to replace it cannot be created for some reason.

3.5.1.3.1 Scheduling Example

This section shows how to place application `app` with two workloads `w1` and `w2` in neighbourhood `NH` having three clusters `C1`, `C2`, and `C3`. For brevity's sake the example has only a single network. The language used to show the problem is Solver's text format for assignment problems.

```
workload assignment v2
model example
application app
workload w1,w2 needs cpu:500 ram:1GiB
channel c12:w1->w2 needs lat:10ms bw:10Mb
```

The neighbourhood `NH` is defined in a custom resource of type `ApplicationGroup`. SWM-FC operates on groups that can contain more than one application. A group is treated as a unit, i.e., all its applications are placed in the federated environment.

```
apiVersion: qos-scheduler.siemens.com/v1alpha1
kind: ApplicationGroup
metadata:
  name: example
  namespace: default
spec:
  minMember: 1
  neighbourhood:
    - C1
```

- C2
- C3

The clusters in NH are identical. They have three worker nodes N1, N2, and N3 connected by an L2SM network. Node N1 in each cluster is the so-called *network edge device* (NED)³⁵. All traffic to other clusters goes through the NED. The links in the inter-cluster network are the links between NEDs.

```

infrastructure
node N1 provides ram:2GiB cpu:400 // NED
node N2 provides ram:3GiB cpu:900
node N3 provides ram:2GiB cpu:400

network l2sm
link l12,l21:N1<->N2, l13,l31:N1<->N3, l23,l32:N2<->N3
  with lat:1ms bw:100Mb
paths (p12:l12 p21:l21 p13:l13 p31:l31 p23:l23 p32:l32)

```

Two links form the inter-cluster network between clusters C1, C2, and C3 (see Figure 46). This network does *not* connect every cluster to every other cluster. For making a placement, it is not necessary for the graph of the inter-cluster network to be a complete graph.

Figure 46: Topology of the infrastructure for the SWM-FC example placement.

The placement starts with step 1 in the SWM-FC instance in the hub cluster. It orders the clusters in NH. In this case the order is C1, C3 and C2. C1 is the first cluster for the placement as there are no node recommendations and C1 is the first cluster in NH. C3 is the second cluster as its link to C1 is faster than the link between C1 and C2. It is *not* checked in this step that the link between C1 and C2 is not fast enough to support channel c12.

The placement continues with step 2 that iterates through the cluster in NH. The SWM-FC instance in C1 solves the L2 problem shown below. It places workload $app \cdot w_1$ on node $C1 \cdot N_2$ and $app \cdot w_2$ on C3. This yields a latency of 1 ms for channel c12 within C1 (i.e., from $C1 \cdot N_2$

³⁵ NEDs are one of the components of secure connectivity, not yet implemented. NEDs are responsible for the secure inter-cluster tunnelling.

to C1•N1 which is the NED). In contrast to a problem for a single cluster, the L2 problem contains nodes for clusters C2 and C3, the links of the inter-cluster network, and paths between the nodes in C1 and the cluster nodes.

```

workload assignment v2
model example-L2-problem-in-C1
application app
workload w1 needs cpu:500 ram:1GiB
workload w2 needs cpu:500 ram:1GiB
channel c12:w1->w2 needs lat:10ms bw:10Mb

infrastructure
node N1 provides ram:2GiB cpu:400 // NED
node N2 provides ram:3GiB cpu:900
node N3 provides ram:2GiB cpu:400
cluster C2,C3
  provides cpu:1700 max-cpu:900 ram:7GiB max-ram:3GiB
  with lat:1ms gw-lat:0ms bw:600Mb max-bw:100MiB

network l2sm
link lN1N2,lN2N1:N1<->N2, lN1N3,lN3N1:N1<->N3, lN2N3,l32:N2<->
N3
  with lat:1ms bw:100Mb
link lC2C2:C2->C2, lC3C3:C3->C3
  with lat:1ms bw:600Mb
link lN1C2,lC2N1:N1<->C2 with lat:10ms bw:10Mb
link lN1C3,lC3N1:N1<->C3 with lat:5ms bw:10Mb
paths (
  pN1N2:lN1N2 pN1N3:lN1N3 pN2N3:lN2N3 // paths i
n C1
  pN2N1:lN2N1 pN3N1:lN3N1 pM3N2:lN3N2 // path in
C2
  pN1C2:lN1C2 pN2C2:lN2N1,lN1C2 pN3C2:lN3N1,lN1C2 // paths t
o C2
  pC2N1:lC2N1 pC2N2:lC2N1,lN1N2 pC2N3:lC2N1,lN1N3 // path in
C3
  pN1C3:lN1C3 pN2C3:lN2N1,lN1C3 pN3C3:lN3N1,lN1C3 // paths t
o C3
  pC3N1:lC3N1 pC3N2:lC3N1,lN1N2 pC3N3:lC3N1,lN1N3)

assignment
workload app•w1 on N2
workload app•w2 on C3
channel c12 on l2sm•pN2C3 with lat:1ms

```

With the solution from cluster C1, SWM-FC proceeds to solve the L2 problem in C3. Workload app•w1 is fixed within cluster C1 and cannot be assigned to a node in C3. The inter-cluster network does not have a link between C2 and C3, so C2 is not part of this assignment problem. SWM-FC assigns workload app•w2 to node N2. Channel c12 between workloads app•w1 and app•w2 is now complete (both workloads placed) and fulfils the specified requirements.

```

workload assignment v2
model example-l2-problem-in-C3
application app
workload w1 on C1
workload w2 needs cpu:500 ram:1GiB
channel c12:w1->w2 with lat:1ms needs lat:10ms bw:10Mb

infrastructure
node N1 provides ram:2GiB cpu:400 // NED
node N2 provides ram:3GiB cpu:900
node N3 provides ram:2GiB cpu:400
cluster C1
  provides cpu:1200 max-cpu:400 ram:6GiB max-ram:2GiB
  with lat:1ms gw-lat:0ms bw:600Mb max-bw:100MiB

network l2sm
link lN1N2,lN2N1:N1<->N2, lN1N3,lN3N1:N1<->N3, lN2N3,lM3N2:N2<->N3
  with lat:1ms bw:100Mb
link lC1C1:C1->C1
  with lat:1ms bw:600Mb
link lN1C1,lC1N1:N1<->C1 with lat:5ms bw:10Mb
paths (
  pN1N2:lN1N2 pN1N3:lN1N3 pN2N3:lN2N3 // paths in
  n C3
  pN2N1:lN2N1 pN3N1:lN3N1 pM3N2:lN3N2
  pC1C1:LC1C1 // path in
  C2
  pN1C1:lN1C1 pN2C1:lN2N1,lN1C1 pN3C1:lN3N1,lN1C1 // paths t
  o C1
  pC1N1:lC1N1 pC1N2:lC1N1,lN1N2 pC1N3:lC1N1,lN1N3)

assignment
workload app•w2 on N2
channel c12 on l2sm•cp2C1

```

SWM-FC placed all application workloads in NH. In this case it is not necessary to visit cluster C2 or perform the second round. The instance in the hub cluster tells the instances in the managed clusters to implement the solution found.

3.5.1.3.2 Alternatives

SWM-FC's method of placing workload in a neighbourhood is just one solution to the placement problem. It is a rather simple approach that does not probe clusters and keeps cluster internals private. This section lists some other methods that may be used. This list is not comprehensive.

- **Avoid multiple problems:** If the neighbourhood and the clusters are small, it might be possible to place workloads by looking at all resources at the same time. This solution does not keep the internal structure private and is feasible only for small environments.
- **Reserve resources immediately:** SWM-FC allocates resources only after a proper placement is found. Reserving the resources may take some time. If placements succeed in most cases or overall time for a placement should be reduced, SWM-FC could allocate

resources while working on a placement. If a placement fails, any resources allocated must be disposed of. This solution reduces the total time needed for a placement but might leak resources in case of some errors.

- **Solve L2 problems in parallel:** With this approach the initial L2 problem is given to all clusters that determine a solution. The SWM-FC instance in the hub clusters combines the solutions to come up with a solution for the whole problem. Combining the partial solutions is complex and might take some time. This solution might be faster due to the parallel work in the managed clusters but could trigger too much work in managed clusters. It is hard to guess how long it takes to build a complete solution from the partial solutions.
- **Distributed placement:** SWM-FC has a central component orchestrating a placement in a neighbourhood. If the SWM-FC instance given a multi-cluster specification performs the placement's orchestration, there is no need to forward the request to the Hub cluster. This solution is completely distributed but is more complex as some administrative details are harder to implement when a component like OCM is not available.

3.5.1.4 Interaction with Other Components

SWM-FC provides the same interface as SWM, i.e., clients specify the desired deployment in custom resources. SWM-FC does not collect or determine information about clusters or networks; it only makes use of it. It is agnostic to where the information comes from. SWM-FC does not directly trigger other CODECO components.

SWM-FC reacts to changes to an application's specification or the clusters' infrastructure. PDLC can trigger workload migration by changing an application's node recommendations. NetMA can update the topology of a network (e.g., the available bandwidth of a link) and this might cause a workload migration as an application's requirements are no longer met.

When placing workloads in a multi-cluster environment, the different SWM-instances must communicate. Communication is needed while placing workloads and to forward multi-cluster specifications and changes to them to the SWM-FC instance running in the hub cluster. SWM-FC uses OCM either directly or via ACM to establish the communication channels between the different SWM-FC instances.

OCM can transfer information from the managed clusters to the hub cluster and vice versa. This transfer is however not suitable for SWM-FC's purposes. There is no way for the hub cluster to push information to the managed clusters. Managed clusters periodically pull the hub cluster to get any new information. This frequency is too low for SWM-FC's purposes (in the range of minutes) and user-controlled.

SWM-FC uses OCM facilities to set up a bi-directional communication channel between the different instances. These channels must allow both instances to initiate a transmission at any time that the other end receives with any delay.

3.5.2 Sub-components' Specification and Implementation

SWM-FC has the same components as SWM. There is one additional component that does the orchestration for multi-cluster placements.

- **Extended K8s API/CODECO CRs.** The interface for SWM-FC is the same as that of SWM, i.e., it uses CRs to communicate with other components. There is one new resource with information about a cluster. Resources defined by SWM are extended to support multi-cluster placements.

- **QoS model.** SWM-FC has the same model for applications, workloads, channels and the infrastructure as SWM.
- **Workload Placement Solver.** SWM-FC extends SWM's interface for solvers to handle multi-cluster placements. The interface has some new fields (e.g., the neighbourhood in a group) but is essentially the same. There is one new type of node to represent clusters when solving L2 problems. SWM-FC's solver is the one from SWM adapted to the new interface. It is deployed as a pod. The more sophisticated optimizer is adapted for SWM-FC and is available for CODECO partners as a container image.
- **Federated Placer.** This component implements SWM-FC's method for placing workloads in a neighbourhood. It is deployed as a pod. The placer's interface between SWM-FC's instances is an extension of the interface to the placement solver. The extension is concerned with forwarding specifications and implementation and rolling back an assignment in a cluster.

SWM-FC supports the extension mechanism of SWM. The solver or optimizer provided by SWM-FC may be replaced by a custom component that implements the interface for a solver. SWM-FC uses this interface when solving L2 problems, i.e., a custom solver can take part in federated scheduling.

SWM-FC's placer reuses SWM components. When implementing a placement in a cluster, it creates a single-cluster assignment. The controller for an assignment plan is adapted to handle some special cases (e.g., channel between clusters).

3.5.2.1 Changes to the Custom Resources

SWM-FC reuses the CRDs of SWM. It adds some fields needed for multi-cluster placements. A CR for SWM-FC is still a valid CR for SWM with some unknown fields as far as SWM is concerned. If a resource of SWM-FC is given to SWM, SWM treats it as a single-cluster CR.

- **Application Group.** A group's placement starts when there are enough applications for the group and there is information for all clusters in the neighbourhood available.
 - *neighbourhood:* A list of cluster names. After placing has begun, the neighbourhood must not be changed.
 - *single-cluster:* A flag indicating whether all workloads of the group must run in the same cluster.
- **Application.**
 - *cluster:* Name of a cluster. If specified, SWM-FC places all workloads of an application in the given cluster. If there is no cluster with this name, the application cannot be placed.
 - *single-cluster:* A flag indicating whether all workloads of the application must run in the same cluster.
- **Cluster.** A cluster resource holds information about a cluster. Cluster resources are only used by SWM-FC's instance running on the hub cluster. A cluster resource contains aggregated and administrative information about a cluster. Resources for clusters are stored in SWM-FC's namespace. When solving an L2 problem, any information needed for solving it is given in the request. An SWM-FC instance running in a managed cluster needs no cluster resources.
- **NetworkTopology.**
 - *cluster-network:* A flag indicating whether the network topology's node are clusters instead of worker or network nodes. If this flag is set, the topology can be used only when all nodes refer to cluster resources.
- **Workload.** There is no separate resource definition. Workloads are part of an application.

- *cluster*: Name of a cluster. If specified, SWM-FC places the workload in the given cluster. If there is no cluster with this name, the application cannot be placed.

3.5.2.2 Changes To Solver Interface

The interface used to talk to a workload placement solver is extended to include the new fields in the custom resources. In addition, there is a latency field in a channel assignment to return the channel's latency in the cluster.

3.5.3 Next Cycle features

SWM-FC provides placement of workload in a set of clusters considering applications' compute and network requirements including migration of workloads with respect to changes in the specification or node recommendations. SWM-FC can be extended or enhanced as described below, but in CODECO these extensions cannot be implemented.

1. **Different placement strategies.** SWM-FC'S current placement strategy is rather simple. Other strategies may be a better fit for certain projects or circumstances. SWN-FC should define an interface for placers. This allows to use a custom placer, i.e., a different strategy, more easily.
2. **Support multiple hub clusters.** SWM-FC supports currently only a single hub cluster, i.e., environments with multiple hub clusters are not supported. SWM-FC can be extended to support neighbourhoods that include clusters managed by more than one hub cluster. Cluster names may include the name of a hub cluster. When SWM-FC's placer wants to talk to cluster managed by another hub, it needs to forward this to the placer in the other hub.
3. **Decentralized Scheduling.** Instead of a central placer running in a hub cluster, the placer can be run in the cluster that "sees" the request for a multi-cluster deployment. The same algorithm for placing workloads can be used but the parts that establish communication between SWM-FC instance must be changed to no longer rely on OCM. Peer-to-peer technologies can be used to set up the communication channels.

4 Continuous Integration, Testing, Deployment Preparation and Releasing

This section presents the integration methodology, the automation processes that support the development, continuous integration, system testing, deployment preparation and release of the CODECO Federated Toolkit v1.0. It builds upon the OSS integration best practices and CI/CD foundation established during the development of the Basic Toolkit (D11 and D12) and extends it to accommodate the complexities of a federated, multi-cluster orchestration environment.

The official CODECO repository is provided by partner Eclipse (CODECO Eclipse GitLab). For testing and integration of the overall framework, the consortium agreed in addition to consider the offered ICOM infrastructure. ICOM contributes here in two ways. Namely, through:

- A dedicated CI/CD server, which is linked to the CODECO Eclipse GitLab through Gitlab Runners and enables automatic unit and system testing.
- A Private Container Registry. This is necessary for CI/CD Pipelines with a considerable number of intermediate docker images and is not supported by ECL Gitlab.

At this stage of the project, partners push their code directly to the Eclipse CODECO Repository, and GitLab Runners are fully incorporated to the repository for automated testing, building, and deployment of the components to the connected Integration Cluster (provided by IBM). In addition, the private repository hosted by ICOM is still utilized as it provides an intermediate private Container Registry using Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipelines.

As described in this section, the process of work is as follows:

- CODECO partners upload their OSS contributions (sub-component level) to the official CODECO repository. New commits/merges enable CI/CD Pipelines, as designed by the designated partners in the `.gitlab-ci.yml` file of the repository.
- The ICOM GitLab environment is used to support continuous integration, assisting in a faster deployment of all CODECO components and interfaces.
- The overall process is described in the next subsections, where more details for the CI/CD procedures followed are explained in Section 4.2.

4.1 Testing Methodology

CODECO adopted a continuous integration - system testing/deployment - release methodology, to allow for an early release of results in the form of software. This methodology consists of the following:

- **Feature – Unit Testing.** Unit testing involves testing individual internal CODECO sub-components by simulating or mocking all the other components in the framework. This practice enables early detection of failures caused by changes in specific parts of the code or functions. Developers conduct unit testing locally in their development environments, and these tests are also automatically invoked by the Continuous Integration (CI) server. The development teams create the necessary job definitions for use by the **CI/CD server**, using `.gitlab-ci.yml` files.
- **Integration Testing.** Integration testing verifies the proper functioning of a service and its features by examining the seamless interaction of subsystems, while simulating only other services. All CODECO components and sub-components need to successfully pass

the integration tests specified before releasing a new software version. Development teams provide instructions on accessing their components' interfaces and functionalities for testing purposes, as well instruction on how these components can be deployed. Such tests triggered automatically by the Continuous Integration server for components with updated dependencies.

- **System testing**, which involves deploying all components and assessing fundamental features and user interactions. The purpose of system testing is to evaluate the compliance of the integrated system with the specified requirements. CODECO components and applications will be deployed in decentralised K8s clusters. Experimenters can explicitly define the requirements of the K8s cluster on which they desire to deploy and test CODECO components. System tests aim to evaluate if predefined requirements are met.

4.2 Deployment and CI/CD Methodology

4.2.1 Deployment

The CODECO OSS Toolkits, both the Basic (Single Cluster) and the Federated (Multiple interconnected Clusters) follow a modular design, involving different communicating and yet independent components, and each CODECO component consists of one or more sub-components.

Each CODECO sub-component is encapsulated in a container image to be deployed independently in the form of a K8s deployment object. In case it acts as a K8s controller, the deployment of the container image also requires the application of the corresponding CRDs.

Containerization allows applications to be packaged into containers, ensuring secure and isolated execution. This facilitates portability across different computing environments, regardless of the specific hardware and operating system used. Along with each CODECO sub-component, the developers provide a Dockerfile, which builds the Docker images of the CODECO services. These Dockerfiles are used both by a contributor/tester of CODECO, and by automated testing pipelines that build and use those images. The CODECO Docker Images are stored in the public hecodeco repository in Dockerhub.

To deploy the CODECO OSS Toolkits, we use a multitude of Kubernetes flavours for a complete evaluation of the Framework. Namely, we have utilized the following:

- **KinD** (Kubernetes in Docker) for initial integration, local deployments, and Gitlab Pipelines.
- **kubeadm**, for evaluating CODECO in a production environment with real nodes (in contrast to KinD that uses local docker containers as nodes).
- **K3s**, as a lightweight Kubernetes framework that also supports arm64 architectures. This way we managed to use Raspberry Pi nodes in our CODECO deployment, and thus, mobile robots, allowing us to exploit the full Edge-Cloud Continuum.

Deployment-wise, the major distinction of the Federated Toolkit compared to the Basic Toolkit is the deployment in a multi-cluster setting. Even though individual components are developed, they are not yet fully integrated in this early release. In this phase, the team has managed to create a multi-cluster environment and install the OCM tool, which will coordinate inter-cluster activities.

For the multi-cluster environment, we exploit the KinD tool, as well as several virtual machines in the shared infrastructure.

4.2.2 CI/CD Methodology

GitLab Runners have been set up by partner ICOM in the CODECO Eclipse GitLab research project. Gitlab Runners are located on an ICOM-hosted server and interact directly with the CI Cluster. The CODECO GitLab also utilizes the private Container Registry hosted by ICOM, for the purpose of building images during CI/CD jobs. The CODECO ICOM private GitLab environment is fully aligned with the official CODECO Eclipse GitLab structure. The code is available to the consortium and EC representatives.

In addition, within each CODECO sub-component a Dockerfile is provided to build the Docker images of the CODECO services. The Dockerfile of each CODECO sub-component is then be used to automatically build the images within Gitlab CI. Developers can configure the respective `.gitlab-ci.yml` files to automate the tasks of building, testing, packaging, and deploying artifacts on the integration testbed K8s cluster. If any tests or builds encounter failures, the CI server notifies the respective developer to address the issues, through an email. In addition, GitLab container registry is used to share and rebuild container images and perform automated deployment.

Every subcomponent leader is responsible to create a `.gitlab-ci.yml` file at the root of the repository. This file contains stages such as build, test, and deploy, and specified jobs within each stage. These jobs are designed to run scripts for building the code, running the previously mentioned automated tests, and deploying to the designated CI Cluster. ICOM ensures that pipelines are triggered on every commit, merge request, or tag creation, providing continuous feedback on code quality. GitLab's environment variables are used to manage sensitive data securely and connect the repositories to an intermediate private Container Registry to save images during building stages. All the different CI/CD processes run on Gitlab Runners hosted by ICOM. This setup enables consistent, repeatable processes and helps catch issues early, ensuring smoother deployments and higher code quality.

An example for a `gitlab-ci.yml` file is [p3-mec-enablement/.gitlab.ci.yaml](#).

Currently, when the code is uploaded (in each ECL repository) and all the tests are executed successfully, a merge request is sent by the contributor to the sub-component leader (task leader), to update the main branch of each project within CODECO public repo. At the end of each implementation cycle, a new tag is created, and a new code version, utilizing the tag, is published/ released, using only the code that is available in the “main” branch of each CODECO subcomponent. Moreover, at the end of each implementation cycle, the images of sub-component are uploaded to the CODECO dockerHub, hecodeco. More details regarding the release version of each subcomponent are provided in Annex II

4.3 Integration and Testing Facilities

The integration and testing infrastructure for the Federated Toolkit reflects the architectural shift toward multi-cluster orchestration and inter-cluster communication. The CODECO testbeds have evolved from isolated validation environments into distributed infrastructures that support federated deployment topologies. These include local testbeds maintained by individual partners and a shared cloud-based testbed provided by IBM and managed collaboratively by the consortium.

At the core of the integration process remains the ICOM private Kubernetes cluster, which continues to be used for system-wide integration testing and validation. The GitLab Runners

are directly attached to ICOM's server and execute CI/CD workflows as described in the previous section. This setup provides rapid feedback to developers and ensures that all components pass integration checks before release.

Beyond the ICOM cluster, the consortium has made significant progress in setting up a shared cloud-based environment intended for federated system-level testing and cross-cluster experimentation. These clusters are configured to support OCM-based federation and are capable of hosting various topologies reflecting CODECO's neighbourhood and deployment policies. The shared infrastructure is geographically located within Europe and supports secure interconnectivity among clusters, as well as connectivity with CI/CD Pipelines for automated deployment.

The combination of private and cloud-based shared infrastructures ensures that the Federated Toolkit is tested across a wide range of conditions, covering security, scalability, mobility, and resilience, key attributes of the Edge–Cloud continuum that CODECO aims to orchestrate.

5 Summary and Next Steps

This deliverable has presented the initial version (v1.0) of the CODECO OSS Federated Toolkit, marking a significant step in the extension of CODECO's orchestration capabilities towards multi-cluster, federated deployments. The document has described the software design and implementation of the core CODECO components adapted for federated operation—ACM, PDLC, SWM, NetMA, and MDM—highlighting their architectural positioning, inter-component interactions, and early-stage capabilities. It also offered practical workflow examples to assist the development and integration community in experimenting with and deploying the federated version of CODECO.

The report has further elaborated on the CI/CD methodologies and deployment preparation workflows that are being leveraged by the consortium, as well as on the environments used for integration and system validation, including the ICOM private Kubernetes cluster and the CODECO federated cloud testbed.

Overall, this release provides a stable foundation for partners and external developers to explore and test CODECO's federated orchestration logic, while offering opportunities for feedback and iteration in preparation for the final version in D14.

In the next phase of the project, the development team will focus on refining the CODECO federated components based on feedback from integration testing, usage scenarios, and deployment feedback.

Deliverable D14 (due in M36) will present the final release of the CODECO Federated Toolkit v2.0, incorporating the planned features and completing the overall CODECO software framework as defined in the project work plan.

6 References

- [1] C. Sofia (Ed.) et al., R. (2024). CODECO Deliverable D10 - Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Open-source Ecosystem Design. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12819444>
- [2] Georgios, S. (Ed .) . et . al . (2024). CODECO D12 - Basic Operation Components and Toolkit version 2.0. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12819424>
- [3] R. Alimi, R. Penno, Y. Yang, S. Kiesel, S. Previdi, W. Roome, S. Shalunov, R. Woundy. "Application-Layer Traffic Optimization (ALTO) Protocol". IETF RFC 9274, September 2014.

Annex I – CODECO Cross-Layer Metrics

This annex provides a revision of the CODECO cross-layer metrics presented in Deliverable D10. A description of the metrics presented is as follows:

- Table 24 presents the minimum subset of parameters considered in CODECO that define an application – [CAM parameters](#). Examples for CAM formulations are provided in the CODECO Eclipse GitLab. The [full schema](#) for the CAM is also provided in the GitLab, in [acm/config/crd/bases/codeco.he-codeco.eu_codecoapps.yaml](#).
- Table 25 describes the metrics collected in MDM, and available via Prometheus. The [schema for MDM](#) is available in the gitlab.
- Table 26 describes the metrics collected in NetMA, and available via Prometheus.

Table 24: CODECO Application Model Attributes, spec, and status, minimum subset of parameters.

Attribute	Former (D10)	Description	Values	Units
Spec				
Uid	UserId	User ID (UID) typically refers to the Linux user ID under which a containerized process runs inside a Pod. This is a security-related setting, not a Kubernetes-specific user concept (like in RBAC), but rather the UID inside the container runtime environment. Available in K8s (runasUser), but should be provided by other CODECO components by ACM	Positive integer; 0 not to be used (root); 1000, first regular user in UNIX; 1001 and above for non-root users.	n.a.
Gid	Usergroup	When dealing with Kubernetes Role-Based Access Control (RBAC), user groups are used to define authorization rules for groups of users who interact with the Kubernetes API server. Identification of the group of user DEV	Available in K8s (runasGroup), should be made available if required.	
performanceProfile	targetProfile	Desired performance profile for the application. CODECO defines greenness, resilience, UserDefined	Greenness, Resilience, UserDefined (string)	n.a.
qosClass	qos	Preferred QoS level. A scale 1-5 is provided to the user and converted to a desired QoS model, e.g., Diffserv codepoints.	Gold, Silver, BestEffort36 string	n.a.
securityClass	securityClass	Desired level of security based on a scale of 1-5	High, Good, Medium, Low, None (string)	n.a.
appEnergyLimit	appEnergyLimit	Maximum desired level of energy expenditure for the overall k8s infrastructure associated with an application (percentage).		W (J/s)

³⁶ The next version will map with the usual Diffserv classes: AF, EF, CS, and EXP.

Attribute	Former (D10)	Description	Values	Units
complianceLevel	complianceclass	expected level of compliance, based on a scale of 1-5. Checked by MDM.	Positive integer, 1.5	n.a.
Status				
avgAppCpu	avgAppCPU	Aggregation of the CPU usage of all the services in the app (in vCPU units) Provided by ACM	string-encoded value in cores, e.g., 0.75	Millicores, vCPU = millicores / 1000
avgAppMemory	avgAppMemory	Aggregation of the memory usage of all the services in the app	string	MiB
numPods	numPods	The number of the pods instantiated for the application	Positive integer	n.a.
avgServiceCpu	avgServiceCpu	Average CPU usage per micro service pod	string-encoded value in cores, e.g., 0.75	Millicores, vCPU = millicores / 1000
avgServiceMemory	avgServiceMemory	Average memory usage per micro service pod	string	MiB
clusterName	n.a.	Cluster name (unique, assigned by K8s)	string	n.a.
nodeName	nodeName	Node name (unique, assigned by K8s)	string	n.a.
podName	podName	Pod name (unique, assigned by K8s)	string	n.a.
serviceName	serviceName	Service name, user assigned in the app model	string	n.a.
errorMsg	n.a.	CODECO application error message	string	n.a.
avgNodeCpu	avgNodeCpu	Avg CPU consumption of the application on this node	string-encoded value in cores, e.g., 0.75	Millicores, vCPU = millicores / 1000
avgNodeEnergy	avgNodeEnergy	Avg energy consumption of the node	string	mJ
avgNodeFailure	avgNodeFailure	Node failures averaged over time (EMA)	String (positive integer)	n.a.
avgNodeMemory	avgNodeMemory	Avg memory consumption of the application on this node	string	MiB

Table 25: CODECO metrics being collected by MDM.

Attribute	Former (D10)	Description	Values	Units
nodeName		identifier of the node in K8s	string	n.a.
freshness		Age of data since last change	String (numeric between 0 and 1)	n.a.
Compliance_state	Compliance	The compliance_state schema describes the compliance status of a resource	string	n.a.

Attribute	Former (D10)	Description	Values	Units
		(like a Pod or Deployment) within a system. It includes the source system and regulation under evaluation, the name and type of the resource, and an overall status (e.g., "compliant", "non-compliant"). It also lists detailed controls, each with an ID, status (like "passed" or "failed"), and optional severity and description. All fields are textual—there are no numeric values or units . The schema is designed to represent qualitative compliance information , not metrics.		

Table 26: CODECO metrics being collected by NetMA.

ID (attribute)	Former (D10)	Description	Values	Units
nodeName		Identifier of the node in K8s	string	n.a.
name (inside link)		Identifier of the link of a node	string	n.a.
NSM: netma-nsm-mon (underlay metrics at a node level)				
uLinkFailure		Number of failures of a link	String (integer)	n.a.
uPacketLoss		<u>Amount of packet losses in a connection.</u>	String (float)	
uNodeNetFailure		Sum of elink_failure and link_failure	String (integer)	n.a.
uNodeBand-Width		Egress bandwidth for a node - sum of bw for all Egress links on that node	String (integer)	Bytes, e.g., KB, MB
uNodeDegree		In a network, the degree of a node is defined as the sum of all edges connected to it (later, ingress and egress links)	String (integer)	n.a.
uLatencyNanos		Latency (EMA) for all egress links of a worker node	String (float)	ns
uLinknergy		The average expenditure of energy over a time window (EMA) for a specific link	String (float)	W (J/s)
NSM (netma-nsm-npp) and Secure Connectivity				
oNodeBand-Width		Ingress bandwidth for a node - sum of bw for all ingress links on that node	String (integer)	B, KB, MB
oNodeDegree		Sum of all Channels for a source node	String (integer)	n.a.
oLatencyNanos/		average latency derived from elink latency; can be based on RTT	String (integer)	ns
uPathLength		Number of hops traversed; Average Shortest Path Length	String (integer)	n.a.

Annex II – Release Versioning

Table 27 provides a list of the current CODECO sub-components, URLs for open-source code, and images in Docker. The notation in the Table is as follows:

- **C**: CODECO component acronym.
- **SC**: Sub-component abbreviation.
- **OSS**: GitLab Repo URL for the open-source code.
- **DH URL**: URL for the respective Docker Hub image.
- **Tag**: Image tag.

Table 27: CODECO sub-components.

Component	Sub-Component	URL	OSS
ACM	ACM Operator	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/acm	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/acm/-/releases/3.0.0
PDLC	PDLC-DL-GNNs	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/-/releases/3.0.0
	PDLC-MARL	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-rl	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-rl/-/releases/3.0.0
	PDLC-CA	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-ca	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-ca/-/releases/3.0.0
	PDLC-DP	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-dp	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-dp/-/releases/3.0.0
SWM	QoS Scheduler	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/scheduling-and-workload-migration-swm/qos-scheduler	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/scheduling-and-workload-migration-swm/qos-scheduler/-/releases/3.0.0
	Workflow Placement Solver	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/scheduling-and-workload-migration-swm/workload-placement-solver	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/scheduling-and-workload-migration-swm/workload-placement-solver/-/releases/3.0.0
NetMA	Nemesys FC	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/network-management-	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/network-management-and-

		and-adaptation-netma/nemesys-fc	adaptation-netma/nemesys-fc/-/releases/3.0.0
	Network State Management	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-state-management	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-state-management/-/releases/3.0.0
MDM	Connectors	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/metadata-manager-mdm/connectors	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/metadata-manager-mdm/connectors/-/releases/3.0.0
	Graphdb	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/metadata-manager-mdm/graphdb	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/metadata-manager-mdm/graphdb/-/releases/3.0.0
	MDM API	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/metadata-manager-mdm/mdm-api	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/metadata-manager-mdm/mdm-api/-/releases/3.0.0